

URBAN-WASTE – 690452 – D6.1

URBAN-WASTE

Urban strategies for Waste Management in Tourist Cities

D6.1 – Public Private Partnerships

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Editors:	BONO Lorenzo		
Contributing authors:	Laura ANDREAZZOLI, Lorenzo BONO, Yoann BILLON, Busch Thomsen Birte, Rute CARVALHO, Paraskevi GIOURKA, Lorella Lentucci, Celia GILSANZ GOMEZ, Javier LÓPEZ-MURCIA, Alejandro MOLOWNY, Maxime KAYADJANIAN, Gisela Nascimento , Iva POZNIAK, Barbara SARNARI, Emma SCHEMBARI, Maria THISEOS		

Abstract

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) have been signed in each pilot city in order to enhance the success of the implementation of strategies, in order to strengthen the stakeholders' involvement defining the roles and responsibilities of each party involved on a voluntary basis.

The form and the commitments required to the stakeholders signing the PPPs have been different: in some cases the commitments have been more focused on a general support in communication or organization activities, while in other cases they have been more related to specific actions, detailed in an operative plan.

In fact, each PPP contains or refers to an operative plan for the development of the measures, which was drafted collecting input from the local stakeholders.

In general, these agreements were signed during the 4th meeting of the Community of Practices, together with the launch of the URBAN-WASTE measures' implementation phase in each pilot city. More than 150 stakeholders signed the PPPs in the 11 pilot cities.

Contributors

NAME	COMPANY	CONTRIBUTIONS INCLUDE
Laura ANDREAZZOLI	Ambiente Italia	Support drafting PPPs and operative plans
Lorenzo BONO	Ambiente Italia	Coordination and review of the report
Yoann BILLON	MCNA	Draft of the MNCA PPP and operative plan
Busch Thomsen Birte	City of Copenhagen	Draft of the Copenhagen PPP and operative plan
Rute CARVALHO	Lisbon Municipality	Draft of the Lisbon PPP and operative plan
Paraskevi GIOURKA	DIAAMATH SA	Draft of the Kavala PPP and operative plan
Lorella Lentucci	Tuscany Region	Draft of the Florence PPP and operative plan
Celia GILSANZ GOMEZ	Santander Municipality	Draft of the Santander PPP and operative plan
Javier LÓPEZ-MURCIA	Consulta Europa	Support drafting PPPs and operative plans
Alejandro MOLOWNY	Cabildo de Tenerife	Draft of the Tenerife PPP and operative plan
Maxime KAYADJANIAN	ORDIF	Support drafting PPPs and operative plans
Gisela Nascimento	Fundo Regional para a Ciência e Tecnologia	Draft of the Ponta Delgada PPP and operative plan
Iva POZNIAK	Dubrovnik Neretva Regional Development Agency – DUNEA	Draft of the Dunea PPP and operative plan
Barbara SARNARI	Ambiente Italia	Support drafting PPPs and operative plans
Emma SCHEMBARI	Siracusa Municipality	Draft of the Syracuse PPPs and operative plans
Maria THISEOS	Nicosia Municipality	Draft of the Nicosia report

Introduction

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) have been signed in each pilot city in order to enhance the success of the implementation of strategies, in order to strengthen the stakeholders' involvement defining the roles and responsibilities of each party involved on a voluntary basis.

A PPPs common template was created in order to standardize the partnerships. However, pilot cases were given the freedom to modify and adapt it according to their needs. In this sense, the form and the commitments agreed with the stakeholders signing the PPPs have been different. For example, in France the PPP is a process which is ruled by the administrative law and the sense is totally different, like the management of a highway. For this reason, in Nice it was decided to draft a sort of Engagement Chart just taking inspiration from the PPP template. In the same way, partnerships were signed either in English or in the local language.

More in general, referring to all the other pilot cities, we can find some cases when the commitments have been more focused on a general support in communication or organization activities, while in other cases they have been more related to specific actions, detailed in an operative plan.

In any case, each PPP contains or refers to an operative plan for the development of the measures, which was drafted collecting input from the local stakeholders. This operative plan is divided into several parts:

- managing team: identification of the human resources that are needed for the implementation of the measure and their different roles and responsibilities;
- target audience: definition of the different categories of tourist service providers to be addressed;
- involvement of the actors: how to get the operative involvement of the different actors identified as target audience;
- target setting: identification (whenever possible) of different targets related to the management process (e.g. number of facilities involved, number of waste prevention actions applied, number of reuse initiatives organised, etc.); the quantification of items/equipment (e.g. number of doggy bags distributed, number of compost bins distributed); the evaluation of the tourists (citizens) reached by communication initiatives, the evaluation of the avoided production of waste (in % or kg);
- setting up the measures: specification of the operative steps foreseen to set up the measures in order to achieve the target defined;

- resources available and needed: evaluation of the financial and logistic resources needed, underlying the budget available, other resources available (e.g. voluntary work, free spaces, etc.), further financial or logistic resources which have to be acquired (public funding, private sponsorships etc.);
- timing: defining the timeline and the milestones;
- monitoring: identification of a monitoring procedure collecting data and information from the different actors in relation to the targets which have been set.

In general, these agreements were signed during the 4th meeting of the Community of Practices, together with the launch of the URBAN-WASTE measures' implementation phase in each pilot city/region. More than 150 stakeholders signed the PPPs in the 11 pilot cities.

The following pages report all the PPPs signed in each pilot city/region, in this order:

- Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur
- Santander
- Tenerife
- Syracuse
- Florence
- Copenhagen
- Lisbon
- Ponte Delgada
- Dubrovnik Neretva County
- Nicosia
- Kavala

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

NICE CÔTE D'AZUR

Charte d'engagement des acteurs locaux du projet Urban Waste

La Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur, sous l'impulsion de son président Christian Estrosi, poursuit ses démarches en faveur de la protection de l'environnement et du développement durable au travers de nombreuses initiatives innovantes et reproductibles. L'objectif est de construire, en collaboration avec les acteurs locaux, une collectivité exemplaire.

Elles relèvent aussi du projet « Urban Waste » financé par le programme européen de recherche et développement Horizon 2020 qui cible spécifiquement les villes touristiques. La Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur a adhéré à ce projet et souhaite y participer par des actions concrètes visant à réduire la quantité de déchets produite par les touristes. Parallèlement cette démarche s'inscrit également dans les objectifs de la Loi de Transition Energétique qui impose notamment une réduction de 10 % de la quantité des déchets produits entre 2015 et 2020.

Au sein de la Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur, la population touristique représente près de 5,7 million de visiteurs par an, leur production de déchets n'étant par définition pas négligeable elle doit être maîtrisée par des actions spécifiques de sensibilisation des touristes à la bonne gestion de leurs déchets en essayant, autant que faire se peut, de limiter en amont leur production de déchets.

Dans le cadre du projet Urban Waste suite à l'élaboration d'un plan opérationnel les offices de tourisme du territoire serviront de relais lors de la mise en place des mesures suivantes :

- Promotion d'une application smartphone à destination des touristes : « Waste App » qui facilite la bonne gestion des déchets des touristes de plusieurs manières :
 - Géolocalisation des fontaines publiques d'eau potable ; des points d'apport volontaire pour le verre et le papier ainsi que les emballages recyclables...
 - Incitation à boire l'eau du robinet ;
- Consignes de tri des déchets en plusieurs langues dont le Français :
 - Mise à disposition au sein des meublés touristiques du territoire
- Campagne de communication sur les déchets marins.

Dans ce cadre.....
s'engage à mettre en œuvre une gestion plus vertueuse de ses déchets.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

Operative Plan - Promotion of doggy bag

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure 1: PROMOTION OF DOGGY BAG
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>MNCA ROLE :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide doggy for the measure for all the restaurants involve. • Make an awareness raising on the measure: newspapers. • Involve the city in the measure • Dissemination of the doggy bag (and bag for the bottle of wine as well) <p>Cities role :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • official representatives of cities will be involved in the communication actions <p>Restaurants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • propose to clients doggy bag every time that the waiter see not consumed food in the plates
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restaurants of the following coastal cities: Nice, Villefranche-sur-Mer, Saint Jean-Cap-Ferrat, Beaulieu-sur-Mer, Cap d'Ail, Èze, Saint Etienne-de-Tinée • Mainly tourists and local people
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MNCA proposes the doggy bags for free to everybody all the time in order to work against wasting food and work on reducing waste • Selection of restaurants: all restaurants of eastern cities of MNCA. In Nice, selected restaurants are those located in the surroundings of the old seaport. This selection results from the combination of data coming from other services that carried out waste reduction and sorting actions and also available budget • Restaurants were visited and convinced to participate to the measure
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50 restaurants • Number of doggy bag distributed 8000
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purchasing of doggy bags by MNCA (6000 in May + 6000 probably in September) • Press releases • Media event organised by MNCA during the first delivery of doggy bags in some of the selected restaurants with the presence of city representatives • About 100 doggy bags will be distributed to each restaurant? 100 x 50

	<p>restaurants= 5.000 it seems you will purchase 8000, please check.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular follow up visits of restaurants to ensure the correct use of doggy bags • Provision of additional doggy bags to restaurants as soon as it is required
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project manager and associated project manager • Local politician and referring persons in the involved cities • Budget for doggy bag kits: 10 000€ (encompassing bag for bottles, bag for food, bag design and stickers to be displayed in involved restaurants)
Timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2017: identification and mobilization of restaurants • April / May: purchasing of doggy bags (public contract) and mobilization of restaurants • May: communication about the measure • June: distribution of the doggy bags to involved restaurants • Follow up of restaurants until September
Monitoring	<p>Remarks on indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total number of restaurants in the pilot area: it will be the total number of those in the surroundings of the old seaport and in the other 6 cities (entire area) • Average weight of the food contained by the doggy bag: it will be measured once in each restaurant • Doggy bags printed and distributed to restaurants: the entire kit will be accounted • Organic waste produced (weighted) : impossible to measure because no equipment foreseen to this aim • Data on « unsorted waste produced (weighted) » or « bins/bags (collecting unsorted waste) filled in daily » will be collected only for restaurants under special waste fee regim

Operative Plan - Tap Water

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure 13: Promotion of tap water
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>MNCA ROLE :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide cups in the tourism offices • Make an awareness raising on the measure: newspapers.... • Involve the city in the measure • Localize the fountain in the city (address) • Add the localization in the waste app <p>Management water department is be informed of the measure</p> <p>Cities: participation to communication actions</p> <p>Tourism offices: participation to communication actions and distribution of cups</p>
Target audience	<p>About the target audience :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mainly tourists. In France tap water is distributed for free in bars and restaurants, therefore customers of these establishments are not targeted <p>tourism office of the cities where public fountains distributing drinking water could be identified: Nice, Beaulieu-sur-Mer, Villefranche-sur-Mer, Èze</p>
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MNCA selects the fountains, purchases the cups and display stickers on selected fountains • Tourism offices distribute the cup to tourists that have win points through the Waste App
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 tourism offices involved • Number of cups reusable distributed : 2000 • Number of public fountains with the Urban Waste sticker: 31
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customization of the cups according to the Urban waste visual identity: by the communication department • MNCA will distribute the cups in several tourism offices in Metropole Nice Cote d'Azur • Advertising the initiative: articles in newspaper, organization of events
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget available for buying the cups/reusable flasks and bottle: around 1000 euros.

<p>available and needed</p>	
<p>Timing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • November 2017 / February 2018: definition of the fountains list • June: communication about the measure and promotion of the Waste App • End of June: promotion of Urban Waste and the Waste App at the “Innovative City” exhibition in Nice where MNCA will be present • August: display of stickers on selected fountains • September 2018: launch of the measure and distribution of the cups in the tourism offices
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p>Remarks on indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing public potable water fountains that are placed in tourist areas: fountains located in the 7 above mentioned cities. Information is not available in the other cities • Bars and restaurants serving tap water: this item will not be filled because tap water is distributed for free in France • Number of cups/flaks distributed • Evaluation of people potentially reached by the communication campaign and surveys on the use of tap water: this will be assessed from the number of Waste App downloaded and the number of distributed cups. For this evaluation you can also consider, for example, the average number of people going daily to a tourist office multiplied per the number of days when information about tap water are available (posters showed, brochure distributed, etc) • Quantity of water distributed through the automatic public water fountains: this information will be provided from only 2 fountains that are equipped with a tap and a water flow counter

Operative Plan - Waste sorting instructions translated for the tourists

Measure 14: Waste sorting instructions translated	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>MNCA and its project team is in charge of the coordination of the measure implementation and monitoring.</p> <p>This activity will be implemented in collaboration with MNCA's cities and tourism offices.</p> <p>MNCA role:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying the main tourist nationalities to define the languages in which the instructions will be translated • Providing sorting instructions translated in tourism offices and cities • Involving the cities in the measure • Obtaining the contact of the owners and renters of tourist accommodations • Disseminating the instructions in multiple languages through the contacts identified <p>Tourism offices role:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing owners contacts • Disseminating the instructions in multiple languages <p>MNCA's cities role:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminating the instructions in multiple languages <p>Owners and renters of tourist accommodations role:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminating the instructions in multiple languages in their premises
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourism offices: Nice, Beaulieu-sur-Mer, Villefranche-sur-Mer, Saint Jean-Cap-Ferrat, Èze. Optional for the following cities: Saint Jeannet, Saint Etienne-de-Tinée, Vence, Cap d'Ail, Cagnes-sur-Mer • Owners and renters of tourist accommodations • Tourists staying more than one day
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourism offices are contacted directly or by email • Tourism offices have a database with the owner of tourist accommodations: we are working with tourism offices in order to meet all the owners and provide waste sorting instructions and a "sorting bag". The instructions and bag will be provided by the waste collection department to all the accommodations. We have already started to launch the measure in Nice

	<p>We have to meet the tourism office of Nice to check how many accommodations have been visited and sensibilized</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Next step : duplicate the measure in the other tourism offices in the MNCA
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 tourism offices • 7 coastal cities • Number of owners: 200 minimum (identified from the data base)
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft the sorting instructions in several languages by MNCA • Distribution of the instructions in tourism offices and private facilities: MNCA and tourism, offices • Distribution during events involving tourists organised by MNCA (beach events and “Wednesday of Environment” where instructions will be distributed from a stand) or by the cities themselves
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget available for creating and printing sorting instructions : 1500 euros • People involved in the distribution of the sorting instructions : MNCA (3 persons: a project manager, a graphist, one person in charge of communication), tourism offices (1 to 2 persons in each tourism office)
Timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • December 2017: finalization of the sorting instruction brochure • March / September: dissemination in the different MNCA cities in particular during specific events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 16th and 30th of May, 20th of June and other dates in July & August: “Wednesday of Environment” on the Promenade du Paillon (coulée verte), information about Urban Waste project will be displayed ○ 8th of June: beach event on the beach of Carras (Nice) ○ July & Augusts: other events organised in different cities with a stand for displaying the instructions and information about Urban Waste project
Monitoring	<p>Remarks on some indicators proposed by Ambiente Italia:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste e-instructions downloaded : this information will not be available because of problem with the company managing the web site • Number of owners and renters of tourist accommodation provided with waste sorting instructions? • Number of brochure with waste sorting instruction distributed? • Evaluation of people potentially reached by communication initiatives: will be evaluated according to the number of distributed instructions and the number of tourist accommodations’ renters • Who is the ultimate decision maker in accommodation?: the owner

Operative Plan - Awareness campaign on marine litter

	Measure 19: Awareness campaign on marine litter
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>MNCA ROLE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of the stakeholders (port authorities, cities and waste management department) and the flow waste generated • Meet the environmental department of Metropole for explaining the measure and get advices • Meet the port managers of the Metropole for explaining the measure and get advices • Definition of an awareness campaign with the communication department <p>Centre de découverte du monde marin (discovery center of the marine world): provide advices on the identification of topics, the design of communication and the organisation of beach events</p> <p>Cities: participation to communication actions</p> <p>Tourism offices: participation to communication actions</p> <p>Port authorities: coordination and participation to communication actions</p>
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mainly for the tourists and local people as well
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with the waste collection department to create an awareness raising consistent with the needs expressed by the stakeholders • Organizing events, in cooperation with environmental department and the Centre de découverte du monde marin
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of the awareness campaign in the ports of the MNCA and public areas closed to the sea • 7 seaports: Nice, Villefranche-sur-Mer, Beaulieu-sur-Mer, Saint-Jean Cap Ferrat, Èze, Cap d'Ail, Saint Laurent du Var • Number of attending people : about 200 • Number of communication materials (brochures? Promocard?gadgets?) distributed:
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement with the seaport authorities and signature of an Engagement Charter for the Urban Waste Project • Distribution of communication materials in tourism offices, in cities and in

	<p>seaports</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of events involving tourists and “beach clean-up” events • Distribution of waste sorting instructions in several languages in the seaport and involved cities
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget available for creating and printing communication materials/gadgets: about 5 000 euros • Budget for the promotional events/activities: no cost because MNCA organizes the event.
Timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2017: discussion and mobilisation of seaport authorities, tourisme offices and Centre de découverte du monde marin • May: Finalization of the communication materials/gadgets • June: signature of Charters (seaports), communication actions (cities, tourism offices and seaports) • 8th of June: beach event • Date to be defined : second beach event • July: Communication campaign. Display of posters on panels of MNCA, cities, tourism offices and seaports
Monitoring	<p>In addition to the proposed indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of seaports signing the charter • Number of places where posters of the awareness campaign have been displayed • <u>Weight of waste collected in seaports (conditioned by the availability of data provided by seaport authorities)</u> • Number of communication materials(brochres? Promocard? Gadgets?) distributed? • Number of people attending the events? <p>Method for carrying out the survey:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • choose 3 or 4 beaches • visit one beach per day the same week at the same time (e.g. 3 pm) each second week of June, July and August • estimate the number of tourists on the beach: count the number of people in one or two squares of 10x10m, extrapolate to the entire beach area • interview 5% of people randomly located

Charte d'engagement pour lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire

La Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur, sous l'impulsion de son président Christian Estrosi, poursuit ses démarches en faveur de la protection de l'environnement et du développement durable au travers de nombreuses initiatives innovantes et reproductibles. L'objectif est de construire, en collaboration avec les acteurs locaux, une collectivité exemplaire.

Elles relèvent aussi du projet « Urban Waste » financé par le programme européen de recherche et développement Horizon 2020 qui cible spécifiquement les villes touristiques. La Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur a adhéré à ce projet et souhaite y participer par des actions concrètes visant à réduire la quantité de déchets produite par les touristes. Parallèlement cette démarche s'inscrit également dans les objectifs de la Loi de Transition Énergétique qui impose notamment une réduction de 10 % de la quantité des déchets produits entre 2015 et 2020.

Au sein de la Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur, la population touristique représente près de 5,7 millions de visiteurs par an, leur production de déchets n'étant par définition pas négligeable elle doit être maîtrisée par des actions spécifiques de sensibilisation des touristes à la bonne gestion de leurs déchets en essayant, autant que faire se peut, de limiter en amont leur production de déchets.

Dans le cadre du projet Urban Waste et suite à l'élaboration d'un plan opérationnel des restaurants volontaires et soucieux de lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire s'engagent à mettre à disposition de leurs clients des "doggy bag"

Le restaurant,

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

Le projet a reçu des fonds dans le cadre du programme européen de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 sous la convention de subvention no 690452

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La Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur, sous l'impulsion de son président Christian Estrosi, poursuit ses démarches en faveur de la protection de l'environnement et du développement durable au travers de nombreuses initiatives innovantes et reproductibles. L'objectif est de construire, en collaboration avec les acteurs locaux, une collectivité exemplaire.

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Dans le cadre du projet Urban Waste et suite à l'élaboration d'un plan opérationnel des restaurants volontaires et soucieux de lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire s'engagent à mettre à disposition de leurs clients des "doggy bag"

Le restaurant,

LE CAFÉ DE LA PLACE
11, Place Garibaldi
06300 NICE
Tél : 04 92 04 18 02
SARL RODALEX - SIRET : 534 322 391 00010

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

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Le restaurant,

LE BAR À MANGER
RESTAURANT
4, rue Martin Seytour - 06300 NICE
Tél. 09 80 74 42 72
SIRET 479 622 318 00018 - APE 5610 A

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

Le petit Napoléon

19, rue Bonaparte
06300 Nice

siret 789 399 94b 00019 - APE 5610C

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

SARL L'AM
RCS NICE 820 434 736
7 Rue Bonaparte - 06300 NICE
gossipbar.reservation@gmail.com
Tél : 06.27.777.649 - 04.83.45.72.15

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

L'UZINE

Restaurant & Bar

18, rue François-Guisol - 06300 NICE

Tél. 04 93 56 42 39

SIRET 789 656 790 00019

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

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Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

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URBAN WASTE

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Le restaurant,

**RESTAURANT - PIZZERIA
D'AQUI D'AIA
12, RUE CASSINI 06300 NICE
TEL. 04 83 45 46 48
SIRET 510 717 242 00018**

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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SARL YASBAHA
Restaurant influence
31, rue Bonaparte - 06300 NICE
Tél. 09 82 57 39 66
SIRET 818 925 063 00014

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

SAS LE CAFE DE LA PLACE

Rue Gayolle

06660 St Etienne de Tinée

06 83 84 44 84 - 06 77 41 04 98

SIRET 819191313 00017

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

SARL LOU BEN MANJA
Hôtel Bar Restaurant
Place San Menth
06660 St Etienne de Tinée
Siret 518 630 827 - RCS NICE

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,
HÔTEL - RESTAURANT
LE STÉPHANOIS
06660 SAINT-ETIENNE-DE-TINÉE
Tél. 04 93 02 40 26
SIREN 751 815 853

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Dans le cadre du projet Urban Waste et suite à l'élaboration d'un plan opérationnel des restaurants volontaires et soucieux de lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire s'engagent à mettre à disposition de leurs clients des "doggy bag"

Le restaurant,

Restaurant - Glacier
1 av. du Général de Gaulle
06660 ST ETIENNE DE TINÉE
Tél. 04 93 02 44 80
SIRET 829 041 448 00048

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

Ce projet a reçu des fonds dans le cadre du programme européen de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 sous la convention de subvention no 690452

Charte d'engagement pour lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire

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Le restaurant,

Restaurant Lou San Jean
5, rue des communes de France
06660 ST ETIENNE DE TINEE
Tél. 04 93 05 10 48
RCS Nice 504 968 629 - APE 5610 A

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

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Le Régaliyou
Le restaurant
Hotel Restaurant
8, Boulevard d'Auron
06660 ST ETIENNE DE TINÉE
Tél/Fax 04 93 02 49 00
RCS NICE 97 B 00454

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

**BISTROT
L'ÉTOILE DU PORT**
PORT SAINT-JEAN-CAP-FERRAT
SIRET 350 895 454 00014

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

Restaurant **Le Pirate**

Nouveau Port
06230 - Saint-Jean Cap Ferrat

Tél : 04 93 76 12 97

Port : 06 15 49 08 17

Siret : 39472070000019 - APE 553B

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

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Le restaurant,

RESTAURANT LE PINOCCHIO
1 Avenue du Jardin Exotique
06360 EZE
Siret 481 739 597 00021
Tél : 04 93 41 16 42

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

LE SERRE
16, rue de May
06230 Villefranche-sur-Mer
Tél. : 04 93 76 79 91
Siret : 484 859 046 00019

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

PLUS
Avenue Foch
Ville-sur-Mer
087 89 49
822 310 032 RCS Nice

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Le restaurant,

 LA CHICORÉE
BISTROT
31, 33 bd Maréchal Leclerc - 06310 Beaulieu sur Mer
Tél : 04 93 01 01 27
Siret n° 750 956 641 00013

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

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Le restaurant,

LE CATALAN

Restaurant - Pizzeria

52 boulevard Maréchal Leclerc

06310 BEAULIEU SUR MER

Tél 04 93 01 02 78 - Mobile 06 74 67 59 77

RCS NICE 443 810 866 000 225 610

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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LE FABULEUX DESTIN
Le restaurant
SARL AUBERGE DU PORT au capital de 30 000 €
tél : 04 93 01 13 23
Port de Plaisance - 06310 BEAULIEU-SUR-MER
SIRET 429 233 316 00028 APE 553 A

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

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Elles relèvent aussi du projet « Urban Waste » financé par le programme européen de recherche et développement Horizon 2020 qui cible spécifiquement les villes touristiques. La Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur a adhéré à ce projet et souhaite y participer par des actions concrètes visant à réduire la quantité de déchets produite par les touristes. Parallèlement cette démarche s'inscrit également dans les objectifs de la Loi de Transition Énergétique qui impose notamment une réduction de 10 % de la quantité des déchets produits entre 2015 et 2020.

Au sein de la Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur, la population touristique représente près de 5,7 millions de visiteurs par an, leur production de déchets n'étant par définition pas négligeable elle doit être maîtrisée par des actions spécifiques de sensibilisation des touristes à la bonne gestion de leurs déchets en essayant, autant que faire se peut, de limiter en amont leur production de déchets.

Dans le cadre du projet Urban Waste et suite à l'élaboration d'un plan opérationnel des restaurants volontaires et soucieux de lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire s'engagent à mettre à disposition de leurs clients des "doggy bag"

Le restaurant,

TRASTEVERE
Qual Courbet
16230 VILLEFRANCHE/MEF

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

Ce projet a reçu des fonds dans le cadre du programme européen de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 sous la convention de subvention no 690452

Charte d'engagement pour lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire

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Dans le cadre du projet Urban Waste et suite à l'élaboration d'un plan opérationnel des restaurants volontaires et soucieux de lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire s'engagent à mettre à disposition de leurs clients des "doggy bag"

Le restaurant,

Restaurant Spalato
SAS ANTE
Quai amiral Courbet
06230 Villefranche sur mer
SIRET : 639 093 754
RCS Nice

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

Ce projet a reçu des fonds dans le cadre du programme européen de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 sous la convention de subvention no 690452

Charte d'engagement pour lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire

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S.A.R. Le restaurant
CÔTÉ JARDIN
4 Place de la République
06230 VILLEFRANCHE-SUR-MER
06.50.75.95.53
RCS Nice 528 008 311

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

Ce projet a reçu des fonds dans le cadre du programme européen de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 sous la convention de subvention no 690452

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Le restaurant **ACHILL'S**
Quai Amiral Courbet
06290 VILLEFRANCHE-SUR-MER
032 597 991 RCS NICE

certifie avoir reçu ce jour un kit de 100 "doggy bag".

Ce projet a reçu des fonds dans le cadre du programme européen de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 sous la convention de subvention no 690452

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Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

Ce projet a reçu des fonds dans le cadre du programme européen de recherche et d'innovation Horizon 2020 sous la convention de subvention no 690452

Charte d'engagement pour lutter contre le gaspillage alimentaire

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Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

**MÉTROPOLE
NICE CÔTE D'AZUR**

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Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

SANTANDER

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the **Ayuntamiento de Santander**(or Santander City Council), in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Santander Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 17th May 2018 between Ayuntamiento de Santander and

ASCAN-GEASER

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure **n. 19 Awareness campaign on marine litter**, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders located in Santander Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree, to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure **n. 19 Awareness campaign on marine litter** in Santander Municipality limits and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

COMMITMENTS OF THE ASCAN-GEASER

- To support the operative plan
- To monitor the implementation of the actions
- To be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
- To disseminate/promote the communication material

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 17th May and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on September 2018

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure [no. 19 Awareness campaign on marine litter]
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Specifically in Santander the measure nº 19 will be carried out through recycling workshops for kids on the Sardinero beaches during summer time, following the lessons learned from the pilot experience organized in august last summer, under Urban Waste project guidelines and the label: #YoRecicloTambien#Vacaciones #Santander #UrbanWasteEU</p> <p>The workshop will be developed in different sections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Introduction to the recycling workshop and the waste manage and sorting rules in Santander- Brainstorming about recycling

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste sorting game - Mural painting - Sorting of waste in the correct bins in the mural - Thanks for collaborating and distribution of promotion materials (postcards, t-shirts, caps) for children and waste sorting information brochures for parents. <p>Coordinators: Celia Gilsanz from Santander City Council in cooperation with the Environmental Service of the municipality (Belen Domingo) in order manager the organization of the recycling workshops on the beach during summer time.</p> <p>ASCAN-GEASER will be in charge of set up the recycling workshops for kids on the Sardinero beaches. The contact person in charge of the coordination in Ascan-Geaser will be Marco Casaos (Technical Director of ASCAN-GEASER).</p> <p>Public and private entities will provide voluntary services for the promotion of the workshops mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.</p>
Target audience	<p>Children from all over Spain and abroad (internal and international tourism) who coming to Santander to enjoy the Sardinero beach during summer time. Tourism Visiting Santander is mainly national Tourists, followed by English and French tourism.</p> <p>This measure will be implemented in the most touristic beaches of the city, Sardinero beaches.</p>
Involvement of the actors	<p>A mailbox, URBANWASTE@santander.es was created to maintain active communication with stakeholders throughout the project, informing of CoP's events, webinars, Newsletter, workshops and the most important activities or news related to waste management and tourism in the city etc.</p> <p>Promotion of the measure through their website, social networks and their offices.</p>
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of recycling workshops <i>organised</i> on beaches (33) • <i>Number of people attending to recycling workshops (250)</i> • <i>Brochure and leaflets distributed (250)</i>
Setting up the measures	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary meetings. - Elaborate the guidelines for recycling workshops - Visits organizing for implementation phase follow up - Print the communication material. <p>Implementation and Monitoring phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution of communication material. - Promoting the workshop through municipal web portal and tourist offices. - Conducted recycling workshops for kids on the Sardinero beaches during summer time - Weekly indicators collection
Resources available and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Santander City Council personnel cost will be covered by the direct personnel cost' category of the project budget.

<p>needed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Printing the flyers and other communication materials, (600 caps, 2 flags) will be covered by the subcontracting part of the project budget. - Stakeholders will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.
<p>Timing</p>	<p>Start-up phase: January- final of May 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducted a successful pilot experience in August 2017 in Sardinero beaches. - Organisation of preliminary meetings. - Working on monitoring indicators - Signing the PPP - Finalisation of the new communication materials by first of June 2018. - Distribution of the new communication materials to stakeholders by beginning of June. <p>Public launch: during the 4CoP event ->17th May 2018</p> <p>Full implementation phase: From July until September 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducted recycling workshops for kids on the three beaches during summer season. - Promotion of the workshops through the website, social networks and offices by stakeholders. - indicators collection
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p>Quantitative indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of recycling workshops <i>organised</i> on beaches (<i>Number</i>) • <i>Number of people attending to recycling workshops (Number)</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>origin</i> ○ <i>gender</i> ○ <i>age range</i> • Brochure and leaflets distributed (<i>Number</i>) <p>Qualitative indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback of the involved facilities about the implemented strategy.

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

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Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Santander Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 17/05/2018, between Ayuntamiento de Santander and

- *Non-profit entities: (receiving entities)*
Nuevo Futuro
- *Non-profit entities of an environmental nature (exhibiting entities)*
AMICA
SEO/BirdLife
- *Collaborating entities (logistic and organization)*
Ascan-Geaser
UTE Jardines de Santander

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure **n. 9 Communication campaign on reuse through swap markets**, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders located in Santander Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree, to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure **n. 9 Communication campaign on reuse through swap markets** in Santander Municipality limits and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- **COMMITMENTS OF THE AYUNTAMIENTO DE SANTANDER**

- To ensure that the regulation of the swap market compliant with different laws (data protection, security ...)
- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide consultancy support for the implementation of the actions;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.
- Organization of preliminary meetings.
- Determine the possible barriers and constraints for the development of the measure.
- to monitor the implementation of the actions

- **COMMITMENTS OF THE NUEVO FUTURO,**

- to support the operative plan
- To accept the regulation of the Santander Swap market
- During the swap market, the receiving entities may accept or exclude from their reception table the objects, in the latter case it will be deposited in the municipal system of collection of urban waste.
- At the end of the day the receiving entity will port rom its reception table to their installations those objects that want to keep. The discarded object will be removed by the municipality as waste urban.

- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

- **COMMITMENTS OF THE AMICA**

- to support the operative plan
- To accept the regulation of the Santander Swap market
- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

- **COMMITMENTS OF THE SEO/BIRDLIFE**

- to support the operative plan
- To accept the regulation of the Santander Swap market
- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

- **COMMITMENTS OF THE ASCAN-GEASER**

- to support the operative plan
- To accept the regulation of the Santander Swap market
- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

- **COMMITMENTS OF THE UTE JARDINES DE SANTANDER**

- to support the operative plan
- To accept the regulation of the Santander Swap market

- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 17/05/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on 9th June 2018, date foresee for the Santander swap market (weather permitting).

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure [no. n 9 Communication campaign on reuse through swap markets]
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Specifically in Santander the measure <i>nº 9 will be carried out through the organization of the first Santander Swap Market.</i></p> <p>The Swap Market will be celebrated on 9th June 2018 framed in the World Environment Week. The idea of the Santander City Council is to celebrate the Santander Swap Market annually from now on.</p> <p>Coordinators: Celia Gilsanz from Santander City Council in cooperation with the Environmental Service of the municipality (Belen Domingo and Julia Benito) for the organization, development and promotion of the swap market.</p> <p>The coordinators will cooperate with the Environmental Service of the municipality for all the activities needed for the organization of the Swap Market.</p> <p>The public and private entities will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.</p>
Target audience	<p>Santander Citizens and tourists visiting Santander.</p> <p>This measure will be implemented open air in Alfonso XIII square-Botin Center zone</p>

	one of the most touristic zones of the city.
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To ensure that the regulation of the swap market is compliant with different laws (data protection, security ...) - Translation and promotion of information material. - Public Organisations and touristic/environmental entities for the promotion of the swap market through their website, social networks and their offices. - A mailbox, URBANWASTE@santander.es was created to maintain active communication with stakeholders throughout the project, informing of CoP's events, webinars, Newsletter, workshops and the most important activities or news related to waste management and tourism in the city etc.
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Swaps markets organised 1 annual • Swapped material kg <p>We don't have any reference as a target. After the first Santander Swap market we will be able to fix the reference for the next</p>
Setting up the measures	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary meetings. - Write the regulation of the swap market - To ensure that the regulation of the swap market compliant with different laws (data protection, security ...) - to involve the local activities/stakeholders - Visits organizing for implementation phase follow up - Translate and print the communication material. <p>Implementation and Monitoring phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution of communication material, to tourism offices and to public and private organisations. - Promoting the swap market through municipal web portal. - indicators collection
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Santander City Council personnel cost will be covered by the direct personnel cost' category of the project budget. - Communication materials will be covered by the subcontracting part of the project budget: 2 flags, 1 roll up, 500 bracelets and 3.000 brochures. - Logistic aspect like tables for the collaborating organizations, digital scale to weight, screen to show the material swapped, will be covered by the Environmental service of the Santander City council. - The public and private entities (stakeholders) will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.
Timing	<p>Start-up phase: January- final of May 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary audits. - Working on monitoring indicators - Signing the PPP - Finalisation of the new communication materials by first of June 2018.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution of the new communication materials to stakeholders by beginning of June. <p>Public launch: During the 4CoP event ->17th May 2018</p> <p>Full implementation phase: From May until June 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion of information material through the website, social networks and offices by stakeholders. - 9th June 2018 from 10:00-16:00 will take place Fist Santander Swap Market (weather permitting)
Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Swaps markets organised</i> <i>number</i> • <i>People attending the event</i> <i>number</i> • <i>People donating during the event</i> <i>number</i> • <i>People taking items during the event</i> <i>number</i> • <i>Total weight of the swapped goods</i> <i>kg</i>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 **the Ayuntamiento de Santander**(or Santander City Council), in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Santander Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 17th May 2018 between Ayuntamiento de Santander and

Aqualia

Parques y jardines de Santander (URBASER)

Ascan-Gaesser:

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure **n. 13 Promotion of Tap Water**, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders located in Santander Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree, to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure **n. 13 Promotion of Tap Water** in Santander Municipality limits and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE AYUNTAMIENTO DE SANTANDER:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide consultancy support for the implementation of the actions;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.
- Organization of preliminary meetings.
- Determine the possible barriers and constraints in each business.

- COMMITMENTS OF THE AQUALIA

- to support the operative plan
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to provide digital information about the public fountains
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

- COMMITMENTS OF THE URBASER

- to support the operative plan
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to provide information about the public fountains
- to monitor the implementation of the actions
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

- COMMITMENTS OF THE ASCAN-GEAESER:

- Financing reusable bottles for rewarding good practices
- to support the operative plan
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 17th May and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on end of November 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure [no.13 Promotion of Tap Water]
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Specifically in Santander the measure nº 14 will be focused on the promotion of the consumption of the water of the public fountains located mainly in public gardens and playgrounds.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinators: Celia Gilsanz and Juan Echevarria from Santander City Council in cooperation with the Environmental Service of the municipality (Belen Domingo and Julia Benito). The coordinators will cooperate with the stakeholders in order to develop and promote the measure. - Aqualia will provide the digital information of the public fountains to include it into WasteAPP. - Parques y Jardines (Urbaser) will stick the communication material on the public fountains of the touristic zones. - ASCAN-GEAESER Financing reusable bottles for rewarding good practices. - The public and private entities will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.

Target audience	Tourism Visiting Santander (internal and international tourism). This measure will be implemented in the in the most touristic zones of the city.
Involvement of the actors	Translation, development and promotion of information material. Stakeholders for the promotion of the material through their website, social networks and their offices. An mailbox, URBANWASTE@santander.es was created to maintain active communication with stakeholders throughout the project, informing of CoP's events, webinars, Newsletter, workshops and the most important activities or news related to waste management and tourism in the city etc.
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reusable bottle swapped by WhatsApp points: 100 • Reusable bottle distributed (workshops and events): 500
Setting up the measures	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary meetings. - Provide the digital information of the public fountains to include it into WasteAPP - A GIS web application has being developed to update the information of existing fountains in real time. The operator in the street can use a mobile device (tablet) to update the information and it is uploaded directly in the fountains database. - Visits organizing for implementation phase follow up - Translate and print the communication material. <p>Implementation and Monitoring phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promoting the measure through the WhatsApp application, including the georeferenced information of the fountains in the city and also awarding good practices with reusable bottles. - Promoting the measure through municipal web portal. - Distribution of communication material, to tourism offices and to public and private organisations - Monthly indicators collection
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Santander City Council personnel cost will be covered by the direct personnel cost' category of the project budget. - Printing the communication materials needed, will be covered by the subcontracting part of the project budget. - The public and private entities (stakeholders) will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.
Timing	<p>Start-up phase: September 2017- December 2017</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary meetings. - To design and buy reusable bottles for awarding good practices - Including in the Waste APP the georeferenced information of the fountains in the city - Promotion in municipal web portal. - Looking for public sponsors

	<p>Public launch: during the 3CoP event ->11th December 2017</p> <p>Full implementation phase: From January 2018 until the 30th of November 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Looking for public/private sponsors - Promotion in local TV, local newspaper, municipal web portal, video on municipal buses. - Signing the PPP - Finalisation of the new communication materials by first of June 2018. - Distribution of the new communication materials to stakeholders by beginning of June - Promotion of new information material through the website, social networks and offices by stakeholders. - Special effort during summer time and bank holidays - indicators collection
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p>Quantitative indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reusable bottle swapped by WhatsApp points (number) • Reusable bottle distributed (number) • Existing public water fountains (number) • Number of promotional stickers placed in fountains (number) • Number (estimated) of people reached by the communication campaign (number) <p>Qualitative indicators: Feedback of the involved facilities about the implemented strategy</p>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the **Ayuntamiento de Santander** (or Santander City Council), in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Santander Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 17th May 2018 between Ayuntamiento de Santander and

AFID CONGRESOS

CITY SIGHTSEEING SANTANDER

SANTANDER BAHIA TOURS

AMICA

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure **nº. 14 Translation and dissemination of waste sorting instructions in other languages**, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders located in Santander Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree, to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure **n. 14 Translation and dissemination of waste sorting instructions in other languages** in Santander Municipality limits and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will

enhance the measure's implementation; to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*

By signing the present *voluntary agreement*, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE AYUNTAMIENTO DE SANTANDER:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure.
- to provide financial support for the implementation of the actions.
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials.
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.
- to translate the information and design/develop new information material.
- to monitor the implementation of the actions.

- COMMITMENTS OF THE AFID CONGRESOS

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

- COMMITMENTS OF THE CITY SIGHTSEEING SANTANDER

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

- COMMITMENTS OF THE SANTANDER BAHIA TOURS

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

- COMMITMENTS OF THE AMICA
 - to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
 - to disseminate/promote the communication material

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 17th May 2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on end of November 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure [no.14 Translation and dissemination of waste sorting instructions in other languages]
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Coordinators: Celia Gilsanz and Juan Echevarria from Santander City Council in cooperation with the Environmental Service of the municipality (Belen Domingo and Julia Benito) for the development and promotion of the information material.</p> <p>The coordinators will cooperate with the Environmental Service of the municipality for the translation and the development / design of new material in Spanish and two foreign languages (English and French).</p> <p>The public and private entities will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.</p>
Target audience	<p>Tourism Visiting Santander is mainly national Tourists, followed by English and French tourism (internal and international tourism).</p> <p>This measure will be implemented in the most touristic zones of the city (Sardinero</p>

	beaches zone, Magdalena palace, Botin Center zone)
Involvement of the actors	<p>A mailbox, URBANWASTE@santander.es was created to maintain active communication with stakeholders throughout the project, informing of CoP's events, webinars, Newsletter, workshops and the most important activities or news related to waste management and tourism in the city etc.</p> <p>Translation, development and promotion of information material. Public Organisations and touristic/environmental entities for the promotion of the material (Santander City Council, Department of Tourism, Department of Environment, Hospitality sector Association of Cantabria, Magdalena Palace, Touristic Bus, Santander Bahia Tours, Botin Center) through their website, social networks and their offices.</p> <p>Through this process the information material distribution points will be gradually increased.</p>
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste instructions leaflets printed (2000) • Waste instructions leaflets distributed (1500) • Public and private points of distribution (info point, etc) involved (6)
Setting up the measures	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary audits. - Visits organizing for implementation phase follow up - Translate and print the communication material. - <p>Implementation and Monitoring phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution of communication material, to tourism offices and to public and private organisations. - Promoting the instructions through municipal web portal. - Promoting the translated information through the WasteApp application - Monthly indicators collection
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Santander City Council personnel cost will be covered by the direct personnel cost' category of the project budget. - Printing the 2000 flyers and other communication materials needed, will be covered by the subcontracting part of the project budget. - The public and private entities (stakeholders) will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.
Timing	<p>Start-up phase: January- final of May 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary audits. - Working on monitoring indicators - Signing the PPP - Finalisation of the new communication materials by first of June 2018. - Distribution of the new communication materials to stakeholders by beginning of June. <p>Public launch:</p>

	<p>during the 4CoP event ->17th May 2018</p> <p>Full implementation phase: From June until the 30th of November 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion of information material through the website, social networks and offices by stakeholders. - Special effort during summer time and bank holidays - Promoting the instructions through Municipal website
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p>Quantitative indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste instructions leaflets distributed (Number) - Public and private points of distribution (info point, etc) involved(Number) - Number of tourists potentially informed (e.g. number of visits in municipal (or stakeholder's) website <p>Qualitative indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback of the involved facilities about the implemented strategy.

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the **Ayuntamiento de Santander**(or Santander City Council), in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Santander Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 17th May 2018 between Ayuntamiento de Santander and

Grupo Deluz y Compañía

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure **n.20 Food tracking device**, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders located in Santander Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure **n.20 Food tracking device** in the restaurants EL MACHICHACO, DELUZ, DIAS DESUR, EL ITALIANO y LA CASETA DE BOMBAS which are situated in Santander Municipality limits and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- **COMMITMENTS OF THE Ayuntamiento de Santander:**

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide consultancy support for the implementation of the actions;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.
- Involved to the distribution of waste tracker and to personnel training in cooperation with SLU.
- Organization of preliminary audits.
- Determine the possible barriers and constraints in each business.

COMMITMENTS OF THE Grupo Deluz y Compañía

- to support the operative plan specifically in the restaurants where the measure will be implemented (EL MACHICHACO, DELUZ, DIAS DESUR, EL ITALIANO y LA CASETA DE BOMBAS)
- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- adding new food waste reduction actions for systematic improvement
- collection of guest's number data and / or served portion data during the implementation phase
- collection of food waste data (kg) during the implementation phase

- to use the waste tracker and fill in the relevant database

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 17th May and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on November 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

<p>Ayuntamiento de Santander</p> <p>AYUNTAMIENTO DE SANTANDER</p>	<p>Grupo Deluz y Compañía</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;"> <p>Deluz y Compañía</p> <p>GRUPO de RESTAURACIÓN SOSTENIBLE</p> </div>
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ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

Measure [no.20 Food tracking device]	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Coordinator: Celia Gilsanz from Santander City Council. The role of the coordinator is acting as interface between urban waste consortium and local stakeholders to set up the measure.</p> <p>The technical consultant The leader of this measure is Mattias Eriksson from Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU). Two colleague of Mr Eriksson from SLU, Samuel Lindgren and Petra Sieber, will introduce the food waste tracker to the food businesses in Santander as well as they will provide technical support throughout the implementation of the measure.</p>

	<p>Stakeholder involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grupo Deluz y Compañia is a familiar company with 9 restaurants in Santander and Madrid and one social catering. Each restaurant has its own ambient, way to cook its personality and is focused on different client profiles. - The contact person in charge of the coordination among the Grupo Deluz y Compañia restaurants is Zaira Gomez. - Each business or kitchen manager must monitor the implementation of the actions and adding new waste reduction actions for systematic improvement. - Promotion and dissemination <p>The public and private entities will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.</p>
<p>Target audience</p>	<p>Five restaurants in Santander Municipality: EL MACHICHACO – c/Calderón de la Barca 9 DELUZ – c/Ramón y Cajal 18 DIAS DESUR – c/ Hernán Cortés 47 EL ITALIANO – c/Calderón de la Barca 9 LA CASETA DE BOMBAS – c/Gamazo s/n</p> <p>These food businesses belong to the same family company group but each of the restaurants has their own personality and ambience. The five restaurants are located in different touristic areas in the city, that are, some in the city center, some near the pedestrian Botin Center area , and some others near Peligros and Sardinero beaches.</p>
<p>Involvement of the actors</p>	<p>A mailbox, URBANWASTE@santander.es was created to maintain active communication with stakeholders throughout the project, informing of CoP's events, webinars, Newsletter, workshops and the most important activities or news related to waste management and tourism in the city etc.</p> <p>Santander City Council is going to support and coordinate the measure.</p> <p>Researchers from SLU they will provide technical support throughout the implementation of the measure also they will provide periodic reports for monitoring purpose of the measure.</p> <p>Grupo Deluz y Compañia, will use the waste tracker and fill in the relevant database, will collect the food waste data (kg) during the implementation phase.</p> <p>In addition, the public and private entities will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices</p>
<p>Target setting</p>	<p>Totally, there will be involved 5 restaurants.</p> <p>We will not involve more food businesses in this measure during the implementation process. Each food business will be handled separately and evaluated as a unit.</p> <p><i>It will be adjusted according to each restaurant special characteristics and needs</i></p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary audits. - Determine any possible barriers and constraints in each business. - Visits organizing for implementation phase follow up <p>Implementation and Monitoring phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Distribution of waste tracker (a scale to store data in a database) to food businesses

	<p>to quantify food waste.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Personnel training by SLU for the proper use of the device and how to use the general statistics results for further improvement to contribute to less waste generation. -Daily measure of waste -Weekly reports
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Santander City Council personnel cost will be covered by the direct personnel cost' category of the project budget. - In case of any additional actions or needs, the cost will be covered by the subcontracting part of the project budget. - The stakeholders will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.
Timing	<p>Start-up phase: January- final of May 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary audits. - Working on monitoring indicators - From 25/04/2018-28/04/2018 SLU stay in Santander to set up the experiment. - Signing the PPP - Finalisation of the new communication materials by first of June 2018. - Distribution of the new communication materials to stakeholders by beginning of June. <p>Public launch: during the 4CoP event ->17th May 2018</p> <p>Full implementation phase: From May November 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Measure monitoring: Upon the entire application will be ready by SLU (probably from May to November 2018) - Promotion of information material through the website, social networks and offices by stakeholders.
Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Quantity of food waste per day/week.(kg)</i> • <i>Quantity of food waste per served portion (kg)</i>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the **Ayuntamiento de Santander**(or Santander City Council), in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrmaton Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta

Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Santander Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 17th May 2018 between Ayuntamiento de Santander and

Ascan-Geaeser:

AMICA

ecovidrio

Grupo Deluz y Compañía

Santander Bahía Tours

City Sightseeing Santander

Turybike

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure **n.21 WasteAPP**, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders located in Santander Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree, to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE **measure n.21 WasteAPP** in Santander Municipality limits and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE AYUNTAMIENTO DE SANTANDER:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide consultancy support for the implementation of the actions;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- Involved to the distribution of Waste APP and to personnel training in cooperation with ULPGC.
- Organization of preliminary audits.
- Determine the possible barriers and constraints for the use of the WasteAPP

- COMMITMENTS OF THE ASCAN-GEAESER:

- To be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
- To disseminate/promote the Waste APP
- To award best practice through sponsoring the Waste APP

- COMMITMENTS OF THE AMICA

- To be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
- To disseminate/promote the Waste APP

- COMMITMENTS OF THE ECOVIDRIO

- To be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
- To disseminate/promote the Waste APP
 - COMMITMENTS OF THE GRUPO DELUZ Y COMPAÑÍA
 - To be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
 - To disseminate/promote the Waste APP
 -
 - COMMITMENTS OF THE SANTANDER BAHÍA TOURS
 - To be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
 - To disseminate/promote the Waste APP
 - COMMITMENTS OF THE CITY SIGHTSEEING SANTANDER
 - To be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
 - To disseminate/promote the Waste APP
 - COMMITMENTS OF THE TURYBIKE
 - To be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels and promoting gender sensitive communication;
 - To disseminate/promote the Waste APP

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 17th May and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on November 2018].

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure [no.21 Waste APP]
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>The Waste APP was launched in Santander during the 3CoP (11th December 2017) as the municipal new awareness campaign based on a mobile App that rewards users for their good practices. We presented the purpose of the APP, the location of the bins in the city, the QR codes in place and the public sponsors that are collaborating so far.</p> <p>Coordinator: Celia Gilsanz from Santander City Council. The role of the coordinator is acting as interface between urban waste consortium and local stakeholders to set up the measure in cooperation with the Environmental and Tourist Services of the municipality.</p> <p>The technical consultant The leader of this measure is Rafael Pérez Jimenez from Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC). Two colleagues of Mr Perez, Lidia Aguiar and Alberto Clavijo, introduced the Waste APP in a specific workshop held on 7th November 2017 in Santander with more than 20 friend users from the Santander municipal workshop school. The purpose of these event was testing the APP and gathering feedback and new insight, and to be ready to launching the WasteAPP to the real final users. ULPGC will provide technical support throughout the implementation of the measure.</p> <p>Stakeholder involved: The public and private entities will provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Voluntary services for the promotion of the waste APP mainly through their website, social networks and their offices. - Prices, discounts or gifts to awards citizens good practices
Target audience	<p>Tourism visiting Santander is mainly internal tourism (more than 88%), followed by English and French tourism.</p> <p>This measure will be implemented in the most touristic zones of the city (Sardinero beaches zone, Magdalena Palace, Botin Center zone)</p>
Involvement of the actors	<p>A mailbox, URBANWASTE@santander.es was created to maintain active communication with stakeholders throughout the project, informing of CoP's events, webinars, Newsletter, workshops and the most important activities or news related to waste management and tourism in the city etc.</p>

	<p>Public Organisations and touristic/environmental entities for promoting the WasteAPP and for awarding visitors (Santander City Council, Department of Tourism, Department of Environment, Hospitality Association of Cantabria, Magdalena Palace, Touristic Bus, Santander Bahia Tours, Botin Center)</p> <p>Through this process sponsors entities as well as the dissemination collaborators will be gradually increased.</p>
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>WasteAPP instructions leaflets distributed: 3500 uds</i> • <i>Public and private sponsors involved: 4</i> • <i>Public and private points of information involved: 6</i> • <i>Waste APP Downloads from markets: >200</i> • <i>Registered users >150</i> • <i>Prizes swapped for points: >100</i>
Setting up the measures	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to Test the Waste APP with local friend users. - to design and to print the stickers with the QR codes. - to look for public/private sponsors. <p>Implementation and Monitoring phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To stick the QR in the selected bins in the city - To fill in the Data base with the georeferenced points in the map (bins, sponsors, public fountains) - Translation and printing the information material. - Promotion in local TV, local newspaper, municipal web portal, video on municipal buses. - Looking for public/private sponsors - Weekly indicators collection
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Santander City Council personnel cost will be covered by the direct personnel cost' category of the project budget for WP5 - Printing the QR vinyl stickers (786,5 Euros) - Printing the flyers (6.000 uds) and other communication materials needed, will be covered by the subcontracting part of the project budget. - The Waste APP is the municipal new awareness campaign .The public sponsors that are, environmental department and tourist department in the Santander City Council, provide awards to promote WasteAPP. The initial awards are books of the city, umbrellas, backpacks and bottles with the urban waste project logo. - The private and public entities (stakeholders) will provide services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website, social networks and their offices.
Timing	<p>Start-up phase: September 2017- December 2017</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of preliminary meetings. - To test the Waste APP with local friend users - To design and to print the stickers with the QR codes. - To look for public/private sponsors: - To Stick the QR in the selected bins in the city

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To Fill in the Data base with the georeferenced points in the map (bins, sponsors, public fountains) - Translation and printing the information material. - Promotion in municipal web portal. - Looking for public sponsors <p>Public launch: during the 3CoP event ->11th December 2017</p> <p>Full implementation phase: From January 2018 until the 30th of November 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Looking for public/private sponsors - Promotion in local TV, local newspaper, municipal web portal, video on municipal buses. - Signing the PPP - Finalisation of the new communication materials by first of June 2018. - Distribution of the new communication materials to stakeholders by beginning of June - Promotion of new information material through the website, social networks and offices by stakeholders. - Special effort during summer time and bank holidays
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p>Quantitative indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>WasteAPP instructions leaflets distributed (Number)</i> • <i>Public and private sponsors involved(Number)</i> • <i>Public and private points of information involved (Number)</i> • <i>Waste APP Downloads from markets (Number)</i> • <i>Registered users (Number)</i> • <i>Prizes for points (number)</i> <p>Qualitative indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback of the involved facilities about the implemented strategy.

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

TENERIFE

Public-Private agreement for Implementing URBAN-WASTE measures

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URBAN-WASTE. OBJECTIVE

URBAN-WASTE is a European project financed by the Horizon 2020 program which aims to support policy makers to meet the challenges of tourism in terms of production and waste management.

Minimizing waste production is an important component in the valuation of tourism supply and the promotion of intelligent and sustainable growth in European tourist cities. However, tourism flows bring a number of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to the prevention and management of waste due to their geographical, climatic conditions, the Seasonality of the tourist flow and its specificity.

Considering that:

In June 2016, Cabildo de Tenerife, in cooperation with 27 members [Government of the Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association of Citizens and Regions for the recycling and sustainable management of resources (ACR +), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Santander City Council (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE-Diaamath (Diaamath), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioblue (Bioblue), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), European consultation-Projects and Innovation srl (CE), Agenced'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia S.R.L. (AI), Hotel Association and Extrahotela de Tenerife, la Palma, la Gomera and El Hierro (Ashotel), Perifereialpeiroy (EPI), Regional Fund for Science and Technology (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Nicosia Municipality (NI), Regione Tuscany (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea d.o.o. Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (dunea), Lisbon Municipal Chamber (LI), Métropole Nice Côte D'Azur (MNCA)] began the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the URBAN-WASTE project are:

1. Develop new ecoinnovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim to reduce the amount of municipal waste and further support the reuse, recycling, reuse and disposal of waste in cities Tourist. These strategies are implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisboa (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (es), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik-Neretva County (HR), Tenerife (en)] and the results will be Monitored and disseminated, facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the results of the project.
2. Organize local actors in a committee, called the Community in Practice (CoP), through a participatory process aimed at involving the different stakeholders, and in which there will be a balance between women and men in the tourism industry, Authorities linked to waste management, NGOs, etc., for the design of waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP has chosen the measures to be implemented in Tenerife, defining the operational Plan for each measure to be implemented.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the URBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement to promote the implementation of URBAN-WASTE project measures dated May 28, 2018.

Between:

- Ecoembalajes España (Ecoembes)
- Fundación Canarias Recicla
- Hotel El Tope
- Hotel Marte
- Hotel Noelia
- Hotel Tigaiga
- Jose E. Ascanio
- Limpiezas Apeles
- Parque Vacacional Edén
- Restaurante Nielsen
- Valoriza Servicios Medioambientales
- Hotel La Paz
- Cabildo Insular de Tenerife

On the aforementioned date, the voluntary agreement was signed to promote the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE project measure [N. 690452, Urban Strategies for WASTE MANAGEMENT in TOURIST CITIES], especially aimed at involving local stakeholders [Public bodies, waste management companies, tourist service providers, local NGOs, etc... located in Tenerife to apply specific actions aimed at reducing waste production and improving waste management.

Commitment

Therefore, the parties agree, support the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE project measures (n. 690452, Urban Strategies FOR WASTE MANAGEMENT in TOURIST CITIES) in Tenerife and participate in the CoP, which will participate in the implementation of the measures chosen, recognize the actions to be implemented, the role and the tasks defined in the operative plans contained in the annexes, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement respect and fulfil the commitments established for their own organization, finding them coherent with the institutional or commercial mission respective.

By signing this voluntary agreement, the Parties assume the commitments to be described and specified in the operative plans:

- General Commitments
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - to provide financial support for the implementation of the actions;
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures in my activity/organization;

- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

Term

This agreement is voluntary and can be amended by mutual agreement.

Its validity will be developed from the signature by the directors of the Cabildo of Tenerife, as a partner of the URBAN-WASTE project, and the various organizations that adhere, until it is modified or cancelled by any of the partners and common Agreement. Otherwise, it will end on November 30, 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this document.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of demonstration measures for the prevention and management of waste

	Measure 2 + 20: Food waste prevention at buffets and restaurants and the Food Waste Tracking Device
Management team: Roles and responsibilities	<p>Hotel Establishment (Hotel El Tope, Hotel Marte and Hotel Edén)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Management staff of the Hotel in charge of coordinating and supervising the compliance with the ecoinnovatory measure and organizing the human resources and materials necessary for its implementation. - Support staff for coordination tasks and to be in charge of data collection through the waste tracker - Staff responsible for serving food <p>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - -Installation of the food waste monitoring device and on-site training to the staff of the hotel El Tope, Hotel Marte and Hotel Eden - Technical support and periodic reports during the implementation phase. <p>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personnel for the monitoring and advising of the implementation of the measure, as well as for the management of the promotion of the entities involved in different means of communication. Specifically this will be carried out by the head of the technical Service of Sustainable Development (Alejandro Molowny López-Peñalver) and D. Ángel Montañés, Councillor of Puerto de la Cruz City Council
Target Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Foreign, national or local tourists staying in the following hotel establishments on a bed and breakfast basis, half board or full board: Hotel El Tope, Hotel Marte, Hotel La Paz and Hotel Eden - Personnel with responsibility in the tourist establishment in the area of the environment - Hotel personnel linked to the production of waste (gardening, kitchen, etc.)
Involvement of stakeholders	<p><i>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife has involved the tourist establishments by sending invitations to participate in the COPs and meetings that they had with the councillor with competence in the management of municipal waste</i></p> <p><i>The progress of the implementation has been carried out by conducting several meetings in which they have been explained in detail the project and the</i></p>

	<p><i>commitments it implies, as well as phone calls and email where they are advised to fill the documentation and resolve doubts</i></p> <p><i>The monitoring of the implementation is carried out by Cabildo Insular de Tenerife through the periodic remission of email, telephone calls and visits.</i></p> <p><i>Puerto de la Cruz City Council, through the councillor D. Ángel Montañés, will promote the implementation of the measure carrying out the calls for meetings, taking the pertinent decisions for the proper execution of the same and spreading the itself through its website, social networks and its office</i></p> <p><i>The dissemination of the results obtained will be carried out through the social networks linked to Cabildo Insular de Tenerife and municipalities involved, in the strict and digital press and in the webs of the aforementioned institutions the involvement of new hotels will be taken directly out the city council involved, because they are the agents that have more direct contact with them.</i></p>
<p>Target setting</p>	<p>Quantitative objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce the amount of food deposited in the container by 10% - Percentage of original presentations, colorful and elegant with reduced amounts of food 10% - Percentage of foods given a second Life: 10% - Percentage of smaller dishes used 10% - Percentage of convex trays 10% <p>Qualitative objectives (yes/NO)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Obtain exemplary results that are favorable publicity for the tourist establishment - Participation of the hotel in donations for animal feed - Incentives or penalties to avoid waste
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Inform by means of posters of the participation of the hotel establishment in the ecoinnovation measure.</i> - <i>Conducting talks to sensitize the hotel staff of the importance of avoiding waste</i> - <i>Carrying out actions to reduce food wastage:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Hotel El Tope:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Reduce the amount of food that is deposited in the container by 10%</i> ● <i>Percentage of foods that are given a second Life: 10%</i> ● <i>Percentage of smaller plates used 10%</i> ● <i>Percentage of convex trays 10%</i> ○ <i>Hotel Marte:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Reduce the amount of food deposited in the container by 10%</i> ● <i>Percentage of original presentations, colorful and elegant with few amounts of food 10%</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Percentage of foods given a second Life: 10%</i> ○ <i>Hotel Eden:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Reduce the amount of food deposited in the container by 10%</i> ○ <i>Hotel La Paz: The hotel does not use the Food Waste Tracking Device</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Reduce the amount of food deposited in the container by 10%</i> • <i>Percentage of original presentations, colorful and elegant with few amounts of food 10%</i> • <i>Percentage of smaller rations 10%</i> - <i>Make weekly collection of data</i> - <i>Make an initial diagnosis</i> - <i>Detect the improvements after the implantation of the ecoinnovation measure</i> - <i>Advertise the participation of the hotel in the project</i>
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p><u><i>Hotel Establishment</i></u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>The available resources are: hotel staff</i> - <i>Part of the crockery is smaller</i> <p><u><i>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife</i></u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Resources available:</i> <p><i>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife will allocate a total of €5,500 for the acquisition of communication material as well as deposits of selective collection of the different fractions of waste, , allocation to each of the 11 signatories of the memorandum an amount of €500.00</i></p>
<p>Timing</p>	<p><i>Hotels applying the Food Track device system: Hotel El Tope, Hotel Marte and Hotel Edén</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Distribution of waste tracker to quantify food waste (March 2018)</i> 2. <i>Training of personnel by the SLU for the proper use of the device and how to use the general statistical results for a further improvement to contribute to a lower generation of waste (March-April 2018)</i> 3. <i>Initial meeting for the establishment of objectives, commitments, etc. (May 2018)</i> 4. <i>Completion of the initial diagnosis (June 2018)</i> 5. <i>Implementation of food waste prevention actions and monitoring of measures (June – October 2018)</i> 6. <i>Data-Taking (June-October 2018)</i> 7. <i>Final diagnosis and analysis of results (October 2018)</i>

	<p>8. <i>Publication and dissemination of results (October 2018)</i></p> <p><i>Hotels that do not apply the system Food Track device: Hotel La Paz</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Initial meeting for the establishment of objectives, commitments, etc. (May/June 2018)</i> 2. <i>Completion of the initial diagnosis (June 2018)</i> 3. <i>Implementation of food waste prevention actions and monitoring of measures (June-October 2018)</i> 4. <i>Data collection (June-October 2018).</i> 5. <i>Final diagnosis and analysis of results (October 2018)</i> 6. <i>Publication and dissemination of results (October 2018)</i> 																										
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Measure 3: On-site composting in tourist establishment	
Management team: Roles and responsibilities	<p>Hotel Establishment (Hotel Tigaiga)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Hotel Management: It will carry out the management of the personnel in charge of maintenance, feeding and evacuation of the organic matter in composting machine and inform about the materials that form the bio-waste</i> - <i>Personnel of maintenance of installations and equipment that will take care of the operations of weighing, supervision of the operation of the composting machine according to Manual of Instructions</i> - <i>Personnel of the kitchen and restaurant, which will carry out the operations of loading of bio-waste and absorbent material according to instruction manual</i> - <i>Personnel of maintenance of gardens: responsible for the operations of weighing, collection, transfer, maturation and Compost application</i> <p>Valoriza Servicios Medioambientales</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>-Personnel responsible for measuring indicators and analysis of achievement of objectives from the programmed actions.</i> <p>Berca Canarias</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Supervision of composting process</i> - <i>Training concerning materials that form the bio-waste, operation of the composting machine and application of compost (analytical and ripening time)</i> <p>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> = <i>Personnel for the monitoring and advising of the implementation of the measure, as well as for the management of the promotion of the entities involved in different media (the head of the technical Service of sustainable development: Alejandro Molowny López-Peñalver)</i>
Target Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Environmental authorities: promotion through/programs plans of the self-compost of commercial waste, study and development, as appropriate, in regulating ordinance of the Management, study of application of the polluter pays principle and use of the compost produced from waste and environmentally safe in gardening to replace other organic amendments and mineral fertilizers.</i> - <i>Large generators of bio-waste: incorporation of preventive measures preventing that the bio-waste enters the circuit of collection of residues, pilot demonstration of treatment in situ and use of the compost produced from waste and Environmentally safe in gardening in lieu of other organic amendments and mineral fertilizers, communication of results to customers and sector.</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Foreign, national or local tourists staying at the tourist establishment - Hotel personnel with responsibility in the tourist establishment in the area of the environment - Hotel personnel linked to the production of waste (gardening, kitchen, etc.)
<p>Involvement of stakeholders</p>	<p><i>Cabildo insular de Tenerife has involved the tourist establishments by sending invitations to participate in the COPs and with meetings that they had with the councillor with competence in the management of municipal waste</i></p> <p><i>The progress of the implementation has been carried out by conducting several meetings in which the project and the commitments involved have been explained in detail, as well as the telephone calls and the electronic mail where they are advised to fill the documentation and solving questions</i></p> <p><i>For the follow-up will be held monthly work meetings between City Council, Berca Canarias, Hotel Tigaiga (direction and responsible for quality) and Valoriza Servicios Medioambientales for the analysis of the measurement of indicators of the previous month and possible corrections.</i></p> <p><i>The monitoring of the implementation is carried out by the Cabildo Insular de Tenerife through the periodic remission of email, telephone calls and visits.</i></p> <p><i>The dissemination of the results obtained will be carried out through the social networks linked to Cabildo Insular de Tenerife and municipalities involved, in the written and digital press and the websites of the aforementioned institutions.</i></p> <p><i>The involvement of new hotels will be carried out directly by the city Council, because they are the agents that have the most direct contact with them.</i></p>
<p>Target setting</p>	<p><i>Quantitative objectives:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Train 31% of Hotel Tigaiga's staff - Reduction of the quantity of organic waste generated by 10% with respect to 2010, within the framework of the law 20/2011 that marks this objective in the reduction of all the waste generated in 2020 - Remove from the collection circuit the total amount of food waste generated and treated by domestic composting (22.94% of the mass residue generated; 54.20 Kg/day in 2018) - Kg of separate bio-waste in situ treatment (food waste weighing) per inhabitant a day, a week, a month and a year - Reduce the amount of improper to 2% per day, week and month - Percentage of reduction in the number of non-biodegradable plastic bags for the collection of bio-waste in the collecting circuit, after the application of the on-site composting measure with respect to the previous month <p><i>Qualitative objectives (yes/no)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Obtain exemplary results that are favorable publicity for the tourist establishment - Removing or not leaching and bad smells

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Minimization of smells</i>
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Inform by means of posters of the participation of the hotel establishment in the ecoinnovation measure.</i> - <i>Make an initial diagnosis</i> - <i>Installation of the composting machine</i> - <i>Detect improvements after the implementation of the ecoinnovation measure</i> - <i>Explain what is considered improper in the selective collection of organic matter</i> - <i>Advertise the participation of the hotel in the project</i> - <i>Educate and to inform about the materials that form the waste and to contribute knowledge about the composting process.</i> - <i>Separate in the kitchen and restaurant the food waste.</i> - <i>Controlling the improper ones.</i> - <i>Weighing,</i> - <i>Collection without bag,</i> - <i>Transport to composting machine</i> - <i>Tank in composting machine</i> - <i>Compost evacuation of composting machine,</i> - <i>Maturation, application and follow-up</i> - <i>Make the collection of the data</i>
Resources available and necessary	<p><i>Hotel Establishment (Hotel Tigaiga)</i></p> <p><i>Available resources:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Composting machine, Shredder, Biofilters: As a pilot test, it has been chosen to rent a composting machine with the capacity equivalent to the daily generation of bio-waste. There are no rental options in the market of these characteristics except that offered by the company BERCA Canarias. The rental price is not a deterrent in relation to the municipal waste collection rate faced by the user of the waste collection service, so it is not envisaged to design, measure or analyse an indicator on the economic benefit of the measure. The rental price amounts to €374.37/month</i> - <i>Cubes of selective collection of organic matter in the kitchen and in the restaurant</i> - <i>Containers for the transport of the compost that comes out from the machine</i> <p><i>The necessary resources would be: selective collection trays and posters</i></p> <p><u><i>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife</i></u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife will allocate a total of €5,500 for the acquisition of communication material as well as deposits of selective collection of the different fractions of waste.</i>
Timing	<p><i>April 2018:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Initial meeting for the establishment of objectives, commitments, etc.</i> - <i>Placement of composting machine-personal training</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information through graphic material - Measurement monitoring - Supervision of the materials present in the bio-waste and the elimination of improper - Management for the availability of storage elements, transport capable of allowing the supervision of the materials present in the bio-waste and the elimination of impropers, quality absorbent material and measuring elements for the control of the contribution - Measurement for input control <p>May 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set-up composting machine - Tank of organic matter until reaching the maximum capacity - Visual Control and manual disposal at the time of contribution of existing unfit <p>June 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tank of organic matter until reaching the capacity - Visual Control and manual disposal at the time of contribution of existing unfit <p>July 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get 44 kg/day bio-waste and 1 kg/day improper - Application of compost in gardening <p>August 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get 50 kg/day bio-waste and 1 kg/day improper - Application of compost in gardening <p>September 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get 54 kg/day bio-waste and 0 kg/day improper - Application of compost in gardening <p>October 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysis of the results and dissemination of the same - Application of compst in gardening 									
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Measure 5: Selective collection of biowaste from hotels and restaurants	
Management team: Roles and responsibilities	<p><i>Hotel Establishment (El Tope, Hotel Marte, Hotel Eden and Hotel La Paz)</i></p> <p><i>-Personnel in charge of coordinating and supervising the implementation of the ecoinnovation measure and organizing the human resources and materials necessary for its deployment.</i></p> <p><i>-Personnel to support the coordination tasks and to be responsible in addition to the collection of data-the personnel responsible for depositing organic waste correctly in the containers enabled for the purpose.</i></p> <p><i>The Cabildo insular de Tenerife</i></p> <p><i>-personnel for the monitoring and advising of the implementation of the measure, as well as for the management of the promotion of the entities involved in different media, specifically the head of the technical service of Sustainable Development (Alejandro Molowny López-Peñalver)</i></p> <p><i>Valoriza Servicios Medioambientales</i></p> <p><i>Municipal company responsible for the collection of waste which will be responsible for carrying out its transfer to the transferring plants and where the concessionaire of the waste management of the island of Tenerife will take it to the environmental complex of Tenerife where it will be treated on the organic matter plant.</i></p>
Target Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>- Foreign, national or local tourists staying in the hotel establishment on a bed and breakfast basis, half board or full board.</i> <i>- Personnel with responsibility in the tourist establishment in the area of the environment</i> <i>- Hotel personnel linked to the production of waste (gardening, kitchen, etc.)</i>
Involvement of stakeholders	<p><i>Cabildo insular de Tenerife has involved the tourist establishments by sending invitations to participate in the COPs and several meetings that they had with the councillor with competence in the management of municipal waste.</i></p>

	<p><i>The progress of the implementation has been carried out by conducting several meetings in which they have been explained in detail the project and the commitments it implies, as well as telephone calls and email where they are advised to fill the Documentation and resolve doubts.</i></p> <p><i>The monitoring of the implementation is carried out by Cabildo Insular de Tenerife through the periodic remission of email, telephone calls and visits.</i></p> <p><i>The dissemination of the results obtained will be carried out through the social networks linked to the Cabildo Insular de Tenerife and municipalities involved, in the strict and digital press and in the websites of the aforementioned institutions.</i></p> <p><i>The involvement of new hotels will be carried out directly by the city Council, because they are the agents that have the most direct contact with them.</i></p>
<p>Target setting</p>	<p>Quantitative objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Hotels to imply: 6 -Number of hotels to be involved until the end of phase: 2 -Number of containers destined for the selective collection of organic matter installed: 5 -Percentage of employees formed in selective collection 25% -Percentage of increase in the quantity of organic matter deposited in the containers of selective collection: 10% -Percentage of selective collection of organic material produced: 80% <p>Qualitative objectives (yes/NO)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the knowledge and practices carried out - Obtain exemplary results that are favorable publicity for the tourist establishment
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform by means of posters of the participation of the hotel establishment in the ecoinnovation measure. - Sensitize both the hotel staff and the tourists staying, of the importance of their involvement in the correct separation in origin-to explain what is considered improper in the selective collection of organic matter. - Make an initial diagnosis and follow up on the selective collection of organic matter - Detect improvements after the implementation of the ecoinnovation measure - Determine container needs: typologies, number, locations, etc. - Collect the data related to the quantity of organic matter collected. - Manage the necessary actions to be withdrawn this waste by the municipal company in charge-to advertise the participation of the hotel in the project
<p>Resources available and necessary</p>	<p><u>Hotel Establishment</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The available resources are the selective collection containers and the personnel responsible for depositing them

	<p><u>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife</u></p> <p>- Cabildo Insular de Tenerife will allocate a total of €5,500 for the acquisition of communication material as well as deposits of selective collection of the different fractions of waste.</p>															
<p>Timing</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Initial meeting for the establishment of objectives, commitments, etc. (May/June 2018) 2. Initial diagnosis (June 2018) 3. Training of employees for the correct separation of organic matter and installation of necessary cubes (June 2018) 4. Implementation and monitoring of the measure: Separation in origin of organic waste, collection and transfer to treatment plant (June-October 2018) 5. Final analysis of results obtained (October 2018) 6. Publication of the results (October 2018) 															
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p>Continuous monitoring of waste production (6 months: 180 days)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="638 1086 1204 1205"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><i>Variable 1</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Number of containers destined for the selective collection of organic matter installed (n)</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Separate organic waste collection (KG)</i></td> </tr> </table> <p>In the case of not having a weighing system, fill in the variables N^o 3 and 4</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="638 1361 1204 1458"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><i>Variable 2</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Percentage of employees formed in selective collection (%)</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Number of clients and guests</i></td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" data-bbox="638 1518 1204 1615"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><i>Variable 3</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Quantity of cubes (organic fraction) filled daily</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Number of clients and gues</i></td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" data-bbox="638 1641 1204 1704"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><i>Variable 4</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Capacity of organic fraction cubes</i></td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" data-bbox="638 1738 1204 1856"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><i>Variable 5</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Who makes the last decisions in the establishment?</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Gender sensitivity in advertising/communication?</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Approximate gender distribution in extra work</i></td> </tr> </table>	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Number of containers destined for the selective collection of organic matter installed (n)</i>	<i>Separate organic waste collection (KG)</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>	<i>Percentage of employees formed in selective collection (%)</i>	<i>Number of clients and guests</i>	<i>Variable 3</i>	<i>Quantity of cubes (organic fraction) filled daily</i>	<i>Number of clients and gues</i>	<i>Variable 4</i>	<i>Capacity of organic fraction cubes</i>	<i>Variable 5</i>	<i>Who makes the last decisions in the establishment?</i>	<i>Gender sensitivity in advertising/communication?</i>	<i>Approximate gender distribution in extra work</i>
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Measure 11: Recycling advisors for tourist establishments	
Management team: Roles and responsibilities	<p>Staff in charge of the trainings: Fundación Canarias Recicla, Ecoembes, Limpiezas Apeles y José E. Ascanio</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Responsible personnel who will be in charge of planning and monitoring the actions to be carried out as well as to determine/organize the necessary human and material resources.</i> - <i>Support staff for the Coordinator</i> - <i>Personnel responsible for developing training and awareness-raising activities.</i> <p>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Personnel for the monitoring and advising of the implementation of the measure, as well as for the management of the promotion of the entities involved in different means of communication by the head of the technical Service of sustainable development (Alejandro Molowny López-Peñalver)</i>
Target Audience	<p><i>Foreign, national or local tourists staying at the following hotel establishments:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Hotel El Tope</i> - <i>Hotel Marte</i> - <i>Hotel La Paz</i> - <i>Bahía Príncipe San Felipe</i> - <i>3 hotels in the municipality of Adeje</i> <p><i>Personnel with responsibility in the tourist establishment in the area of the environment</i></p> <p><i>Hotel staff linked to waste production (gardening, cooking, etc.)</i></p> <p><i>Authorized waste managers that are linked to the hotel</i></p> <p><i>Concessionaires of municipal waste collection work</i></p> <p><i>Companies subcontracted by hotels and linked to waste generation</i></p>
Involvement of stakeholders	<p><i>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife has involved the entities responsible for implementing the ecoinnovation measure through COPs, as well as regular meetings.</i></p> <p><i>The progress of the implementation has been carried out by conducting several meetings in which they have been explained in detail the project and the commitments it implies, as well as telephone calls and email for filling in the documentation</i></p>

	<p><i>The monitoring of the implementation is carried out by the Cabildo Insular de Tenerife through telephone calls and accompaniment/visits.</i></p> <p><i>The dissemination of the obtained results will be carried out through the social networks linked to the Cabildo Insular de Tenerife, on the web, in strict and digital press, a press conference or communiqué, etc.</i></p> <p><i>The involvement of new entities will be carried out by sending the Insular Council of Tenerife and the Council of invitations to participate in the project and by the entity responsible for the advice, through the provision of information.</i></p>
<p>Target setting</p>	<p>Quantitative objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Number of hotels to be formed: 7 -Percentage of hotel staff to form: 25% -Number of tourists informed: 25% -Increase the percentage of waste paper/paperboard collected selectively by 20% -Increase the percentage of glass waste collected selectively by 20% -Increase the percentage of organic matter waste collected selectively by 20% -Increase the percentage of packaging waste collected selectively by 20% -Reduce the percentage of mixed waste collected by 20% <p>Qualitative objectives (yes/NO)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Improve waste management processes in hotel establishments -Minimize the amount of waste generated -Reduction of the level of improper in each of the fractions of waste collected -Improve the knowledge, practices and involvement of the organization -Obtain exemplary results that are favorable publicity for the tourist establishment
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform by means of posters of the participation of the hotel establishment in the ecoinnovation measure. - Make an initial diagnosis on the selective collection of each type of waste - Draft customized didactic material to the needs of each establishment to carry out the trainings in reduction, reuse and correct sorting of the waste - Sensitize the hotel staff to the importance of the reduction, reuse and correct sorting of waste through lectures or training activities - Expose by means of stickers in the waste bins which clearly indicate the type of waste to be deposited. - Collection of monitoring data - Detect improvements after the implementation of the ecoinnovative measure
<p>Resources available and necessary</p>	<p>Agency responsible for the trainings</p> <p><i>The resources available are the full-time monitors who will voluntarily perform the work and the didactic material for the training</i></p>

	<p><i>The necessary resources will be didactic guides and posters</i></p> <p>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Cabildo Insular de Tenerife will allocate a total of €5,500 for the acquisition of communication material as well as deposits of selective collection of the different fractions of waste.</i> 												
<p>Timing</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Initial meeting for the establishment of objectives, commitments, etc. (June 2018)</i> 2. <i>Elaboration of the initial diagnosis and the capacity to improve the organization (June 2018)</i> 3. <i>Design of the training content and preparation of the delivery schedule (June 2018)</i> 4. <i>On-site trainings (July – August 2018)</i> 5. <i>Intermediate Diagnostics (August 2018)</i> 6. <i>Carrying out complementary actions according to the intermediate diagnosis (August 2018)</i> 7. <i>Final diagnosis (September 2018)</i> 8. <i>Measurement of results</i> 9. <i>Determination of improvements to be carried out at the Hotel (October 2018)</i> 10. <i>Dissemination of results (October 2018)</i> 												
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p><i>Continuous monitoring of waste production (6 months: 180 days)</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="636 1292 1203 1496" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><i>Variable 1</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Number of hotels formed</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Percentage of hotels formed</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Number of hotel staff trained</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Number of tourists informed</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Number of trainings taught</i></td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" data-bbox="636 1653 1203 1888" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><i>Variable 2</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Plastic waste collected (weight)</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Paper waste collected (WT)</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Glass waste collected</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Organic waste collected (WT) unsorted waste collected (weight)</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Plastic waste collected (weight)</i></td> </tr> </table> <p><i>If weighing system is available, fill in variable 2. If not, fill in variables 3 and 4.</i></p>	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Number of hotels formed</i>	<i>Percentage of hotels formed</i>	<i>Number of hotel staff trained</i>	<i>Number of tourists informed</i>	<i>Number of trainings taught</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>	<i>Plastic waste collected (weight)</i>	<i>Paper waste collected (WT)</i>	<i>Glass waste collected</i>	<i>Organic waste collected (WT) unsorted waste collected (weight)</i>	<i>Plastic waste collected (weight)</i>
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Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

SYRACUSE

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Municipality of Syracuse, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Københavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Københavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociación Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereialpeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be

monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Syracuse and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 26th April 2018,

between

Subscriber A, Municipality of Syracuse

and

Subscriber B, IGM rifiuti industriali

Subscriber C, Ionica Ambiente

Subscriber D, Local Tourist Association like Proloco, Sicilia Turismo per tutti, Noi Albergatori e Associazione guide turistiche di Siracusa

and

Touristic facilities (holiday apartments, hotels, B&Bs, etc.)

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure, in particular n° 12 - Sorting bins in public and touristic places, n° 14 - Waste sorting instructions in foreign languages and n° 4 - Collection points for used cooking oils, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...]

located in Syracuse to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree:

- to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE,
Measure 12 - Sorting bins in public and touristic places;
Measure 14 - Waste sorting instructions in foreign languages;
Measure 4 - Collection points for used cooking oils in Syracuse and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;
- to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF SUBSCRIBER A, Municipality of Syracuse:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measures;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - to provide financial support for the implementation of the actions;
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials (involving schools in particular for Measure 4);
 - to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures in my activity/organization;
 - to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
 - to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.
- COMMITMENTS OF SUBSCRIBER B, IGM rifiuti industriali:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measures;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - to provide and adapt the bins to be placed in relevant touristic places for the implementation of the Measure 12;
 - to translate in English and print about 500 leaflet about separate waste collection in Syracuse (instructions, timeline, general info) to distribute to the tourists together with the promo-card of the measures 12 and 14;
 - to integrate the communication of these measures on the regular communication activities and to distribute communication materials together with the promocard of the measures 12 and 14, further than 4;
 - to supply periodically data for monitoring the development of the measure according with the official file of the project (i.e., capacity of bins and number of emptying, number of promocard distributed to the stakeholders);
 - to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures in my activity/organization;
 - to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
 - to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
 - to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.
- COMMITMENTS OF SUBSCRIBER C, Ionica Ambiente:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide the tailored bin and place it in the selected area and supply technical support for the implementation of the Measure 4;
 - to update the existing leaflet with the new bin for collecting used cooking oils and to translate it in English;
 - to supply periodically data for monitoring the development of the measure according with the official file of the project (i.e., kg of used cooking oils collected).

• **COMMITMENTS OF SUBSCRIBER D, Local Tourist Associations like Proloco, Sicilia Turismo per tutti, Noi Albergatori e Associazione guide turistiche di Siracusa:**

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measures;
- to support the organization of communication activities, training sections with touristic operators and the distribution communication materials to the tourists;
- to supply periodically data for monitoring the development of the measure according with the official file of the project (i.e., number of promocard distributed, number of people trained and/or informed);
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE SUBSCRIBER, Touristic facilities (holiday apartments, hotel, B&Bs, etc.):

- to involve the tourists in the implementation of the measures distributing the promocard and supply them any further related information about the separate collection in Syracuse;
- to participate to the communication activities, training sections;
- to supply periodically data for monitoring the development of the measure according with the official file of the project (i.e., number of promocard distributed);
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

Measure 12 - Sorting bins in public and touristic places	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>It is important to make clear what are the human resources that we need for the implementation of measure and their different role and responsibilities. In particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the person in charge of the measure's implementation and monitoring (manager) - the staff supporting the manager (if needed) - the most important stakeholders that need to be involved in the implementation of the measure order to get organisational and, if possible, financial support.
	<p>The managing team is composed by: Syracuse Municipality, IGM (the enterprise in charge of the waste management in Syracuse), tourism associations (Proloco, Sicilia Turismo per tutti and Noi Albergatori) and the Tourist Guide Association, in particular the role are divided as follow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Syracuse Municipality and IGM: are the structures in charge of the measure's implementation and monitoring (manager), in particular the referents are: Antonio Di Stefano(IGM), Stefano Selleri (IGM) and Nunzio Marino (Syracuse Municipality). - The tourism associations (Sicilia Turismo per tutti, Proloco and Noi Albergatori) and the Tourist Guide association will guarantee the promotion and the dissemination of the measure distributing the promocard related to the measure by means of events, info-point, guided visits of the city and attending the informative activities about the measure and waste management related issues.
Target audience	<p>Please define what are the different categories of tourist service providers you are going to addresses and the target you want to reach for each of them. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - hotels serving breakfast (can be clustered according to the different categories or the position): 20 in the historical centre + 10 in the new shopping district, and/or 25 three star hotels + 5 four/five star hotels etc etc. - hotels serving breakfast and meals: - restaurants: - bars: - camping sites: <p>In case it is required the support of other private or public actors, please specify who do you want to involve.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - <p>For some measures, it is also important to consider what kind of tourist your measure is targeting, in order to arrange the appropriate communication approach and materials. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - foreign/local - young people/families/elderly

The main target of this measure is the tourist who visiting the city produce waste and she/he will carry out for separate waste according with the local instructions. In particular **5 touristic points of interest have been identified**: "scalagrega", Archaeological Park, Santuario Madonna delleLacrime, the touristic harbour and MoloSant'Antonio.

For placing the separate bins no further support is necessary, so IGM can implement the action as soon the layout of the bins has been decided with Syracuse municipality.

Normally the kind of target tourists are foreign but a part of communication will be addressed also to national tourists and local people.

Involvement of the actors

Once defined the target audience, please specify how do you plan to get the operative involvement of the different actors identified as target audience: for example, organization of informative initiatives, collection of expressions of interest through personal contacts, specific commitments/agreements with trade associations or single chains etc.

Being the tourists our target, the main activities for reaching them, making useful and winning the implementation of the measure are:

- To Make an appealing design of the separate waste collection bins, integrating them in the general context (cultural and natural heritage)
- To integrate the information about this measure in the regular info addressed to tourists by means of promocard of the project (in particular Measure 14), into the maps of the city distributed to the tourists and into the waste APP
- To inform people working as guide and in the touristic info points to communicate this measure showing the pilot places (physically or in the map).
- To distribute and inform touristic facilities about the measure, involving them distributing the promocard and informing the tourists.

So the actors to involve: IGM (the enterprise in charge of the waste management in Syracuse), tourism associations (Sicilia Turismo per Tutti, Proloco and Noi Albergatori) and the Tourist Guide association will sign the PPP for committing themselves to follow this operative plan.

The total number of touristic facilities (i.e., hotels, B&B and apartments) in Syracuse are about: 808 (about 40/45 in Ortigia) (Fonts: infocamere). A public announcement has been done for involving and select these facilities.

Target setting

When setting the targets you want to achieve during the implementation phase of the measure, it is important to discuss and agree them with all the stakeholders and actors involved in the process. The targets can be related to:

- the management process (e.g. number of waste prevention actions applied by hotels/restaurants, number of reuse initiative organised, etc.);
- the quantification of items/equipment (e.g. number of flasks/carafes or doggy bag distributed; number of waste sorting street bins installed; number of compost bins distributed);
- the evaluation of the tourist (citizens) reached by communication initiative
- the evaluation of the avoided production of waste (kg of organic waste, kg of plastic, kg of unsorted waste etc...)

The idea is to start, during the project implementation with the installation of these 5 waste collection points in high touristic places, as above mentioned. IGM will supply the bins for separate paper – plastic and cans – glass - unsorted and the municipality will decide the appropriate design for the covertures. Before the end of April the 5 places will be equipped.

Taking in account that normally the pilot places: "scalagrega", archaeological park, "Santuario Madonna delleLacrime", the touristic harbour and Molo Sant'Antonio are visited by 1000 tourists per day (more than 2000 during spring/summer) (normally from north of Europe) and that we can estimate for 1/5 of the tourists will use the bins and that they will produce 50 gr of waste per day, in general, we estimate to avoid 10kg per day of unsorted waste, separating it in the right way.

Thanks to the guided visits and the info points, Syracuse Municipality will try to collect also the feedback of tourists: in case they are visiting or visited the pilot places, if they are see the bins,if they used them and if they believe it can be useful or not.

We estimate to interview at least 1500tourists (the 10% of received tourists during the implementation period) before October 2018 and to share these feedback with IGM and tourist related associations and service providers for meeting the advice and the needs of the tourists in order to reach the best separation of waste and show the city in a sustainable and clean way.

We plan to involve tourists (citizens) during specific communication initiatives and distributing communication materials or gadgets.

Setting up the measures

Please specify what are the operative steps foreseen to set up the measure. An approximate list of actions (to be tailored according to the different kind of measures) can include:

- organization of training activities,
- setting up of help-desk activities,
- design and customization of communication materials,
- distribution of communication materials,
- purchase/distribution of equipment (when needed),
- logistic management,
- organization of preliminary audits

- operative meetings between IGM and Syracuse municipality for identifying the final places, the layout of the bins, the related communication tools (as posters, promo card, map and so on) and planning agenda of the communication and training events
- Launching an initial communication campaign to raise awareness on waste sorting and to inform on the new system being implemented, during the public signature of the PPP (during the 4th COP event, 26th of April 2018)
- Placing the sorting bins in the 5 selected areas(in the touristic harbour will be developeda bigger area): 2 areas will be equipped in april
- Creating a map compiling all the sorting bins located on a touristic area and providing the tourist offices/touristic establishments with it.
- informing the guide, the people working on the info points and the owners of touristic facilities to communicate the measure (together with the measure 14) to the tourists, and collect their feedback (foreseen 1/2 questions and a place where noting down the answers)
- Distributing communication materials (promocard measure 12+14)
- Organization of preliminary audits (where unsorted bins are present, they will be monitored daily before installing the other bins).

After this implementation period, the next autumn it will be discussed the possibility to equip other 2. touristic areas with separate bins, following also the feedback of the involved tourists, in particular Corso Umberto and Piazzale Marconi.

<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p>It is important to evaluate the financial and logistic resources needed, underlying:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the budget available, according to the different financial sources: project's budget, public funding, private contribution etc. - the other resources available: voluntary work, free spaces, etc. - the further financial or logistic resources which have to be acquired (public funding, private sponsorships etc.)
<p>No financial resources are needed as regard to the sorting bins, they will be furnished directly by the private enterprise of waste management.</p> <p>As for communication material, municipality will use the related project resources for printing 2000 promocard (measure 12 and 14 together) (about € 300) and by means of the internal staff of the municipality a communication event (including training section) will be organised for tourist guides, info point coordinators, touristic facilities. In particular touristic facilities will be invited to express their interest to participate in the project and collaborate in the distribution of communication material.</p> <p>Some informative events will be organized by means of a Urbanwaste corner, during the main cultural events of Syracuse (as on the Greek theatre during the drama agenda): around 1500 euro will be used for printing the tailored corner and animate it (promoting all measures).</p>	
<p>Timing</p>	<p>When defining the timeline, please consider at least the following steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organization of a public initiative/launch event (could be during or in parallel with the 4thCoP event); February-April 2018 - start-up phase (about 2 months): final design of materials, organisation of training activities and (if needed) testing of the actions foreseen within a sample of tourist facilities; January-April 2018 - full implementation phase involving all the selected tourist facilities and targeting the different tourist categories with dedicated communication activities which will last for, at least, 6 months; April-October 2018
<p>The municipality planning the activities according with the following timeline:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organization of a public initiative/launch event (probably in parallel with the 4thCoP event); 26th April 2018 - start-up phase (about 2 months): final design of materials, organisation of event/training activities addressed to tourist operators/associations; end of April 2018 - first monitoring, before the implementation of the measure (last week of March) - full implementation phase and communication activities April-October 2018 - monitoring April-October 2018 - final evaluation and possible replication in other areas: September 2018 	
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p><u>In relation to the targets which have been set</u> (e.g. number of waste prevention actions applied by hotels/restaurants; number of flasks/carafes or doggy bag distributed; tourists (citizens) reached by communication initiative; kg of organic waste avoided; kg of unsorted waste produced), a monitoring procedure collecting data and information from the different actors (waste and water management utilities, tourist service providers, etc) need to be developed.</p> <p>The monitoring period have to be referred to the 6-8 months of the implementation phase and it should be organized through dedicated monitoring procedures using qualitative and quantitative indicators.</p> <p>In each measure form you can find a set of suggested indicators that can be useful both for monitoring the implementation of the measure and for defining the targeted objectives.</p>

	<p>Qualitative indicators This kind of information is usually collected through simple questionnaires/interviews that can be done before (if needed) and at the end of the implementation phase (e.g. number of actions implemented, evaluation of the results reached using a qualitative scale, etc)</p> <p>Quantitative indicators Quantitative information can be collected, when possible, <u>during all the implementation phase</u>, in relation to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the items/equipment, e.g. pieces of furniture donated to charities, number of ashtrays/flasks/doggy bag distributed to tourists, that can be collected on a weekly or monthly basis; • the quantity of waste generated/collected using weight scales; • when it is not possible to use weight scales, data about the quantity of waste can be evaluated using an average coefficients of waste avoided/generated related to the items (furniture, doggy bag, ashtrays) and, for some measures, collecting the number of waste bags, and the related volumes and materials contained. <p>When it is not possible to collect data related to the whole implementation period, the <u>data collection phase can be focused in three different moments</u>: a week (from Monday to Sunday) BEFORE the start of the implementation phase, a week DURING the implementation phase, a week at THE END of the implementation phase.</p> <p>Regarding the measures involving tourist facilities like hotels and restaurants, it is important to monitor also the number of guests/customers in order to calculate a per capita value.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N° of sorting bins installed • Quantity of waste collected per week or month per waste fraction [Kg] • Mapping all the public sorting bins located on a touristic area [Address of each bin]

Measure 4 - Collection points for used cooking oils	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>It is important to make clear what are the human resources that we need for the implementation of measure and their different role and responsibilities. In particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the person in charge of the measure's implementation and monitoring (manager) - the staff supporting the manager (if needed) - the most important stakeholders that need to be involved in the implementation of the measure order to get organisational and, if possible, financial support.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most important stakeholder in charge of the measure's implementation and data monitoring (manager) will be Ionica Ambiente, private enterprise managing hazardous and non-hazardous waste and selection platform in Syracuse • the staff supporting the manager will be IGM, the enterprise of waste management service in Syracuse, in order to promote the measure • the most important stakeholders that need to be involved in the implementation of the measure in order to get organisational support will be tourist facilities (holiday apartments, hostels), citizens, etc. • the municipality of Syracuse will develop the communication campaign supplying ad hoc

communication items (promocard, stickers and map) further than supervise the entire implementation and monitoring phases.

Target audience	<p>Please define what are the different categories of tourist service providers you are going to address and the target you want to reach for each of them. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - hotels serving breakfast (can be clustered according to the different categories or the position): 20 in the historical centre + 10 in the new shopping district, and/or 25 three star hotels + 5 four/five star hotels etc etc. - hotels serving breakfast and meals: - restaurants: - bars: - camping sites: - <p>In case it is required the support of other private or public actors, please specify who do you want to involve.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - <p>For some measures, it is also important to consider what kind of tourist your measure is targeting, in order to arrange the appropriate communication approach and materials. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - foreign/local - young people/families/elderly -
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The category we are going to address the measure will be in particular citizens and holiday apartments owners of the historical and touristic centre.

In particular the holiday apartments owners will be involved for distributing the promocard into their apartments explaining how tourists can collect and waste used cooking oils. It's foreseen in a first stage the involvement of 20 apartments located in Ortigia and until the end of measures' implementation other 20 apartments around the pilot area. Taking in account that the total number of B&Bs and apartments in Ortigia are 40/45.

While citizens will be involved during tailored events (as info days) organized in order to explain why it's important to collect used cooking oils and how doing it. 3 events are foreseen, promoted by social networks and MEDIA.

Our target audience will be 1 area in the historical and touristic centre of the city close to the open food market.

The kind of tourist our measure is targeting will be foreign but mostly local and families. The number of families living in the target area are 3500, and during the measure implementation at least 350 families will be reached by the communication activities and at least 150 will deliver their used cooking oil to the convenient bin.

Involvement of the actors	<p>Once defined the target audience, please specify how do you plan to get the operative involvement of the different actors identified as target audience: for example, organization of informative initiatives, collection of expressions of interest through personal contacts, specific commitments/agreements with trade associations or single chains etc.</p>
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The Municipality of Syracuse is signing an agreement (PPP) with Ionica Ambiente, IGM and the tourist facilities (holiday apartments, hostels), involved for implementing, monitoring and promoting the measure.

Syracuse Municipality will implement awareness info days on the thematic involving high schools. The sub-mentioned actors will be involved during the communication events (informative initiatives) for inform them about the communication strategy to share with their contacts/local workers and for integrating this communication into their regular communication strategy. The involvement of the apartments' owners will be useful to distribute the promocards, explaining them how involving tourists into the measure implementation.

The info points (their managers and involved workers) will be involved for distributing the promocard/map and promoting the initiatives by means of operative meetings and informative initiatives.

Also some small supermarket close to the pilot area will be involved for distributing the promocard and/or showing a poster related to the measure

This measure will be promoted together with the other measures.

Target setting

When setting the targets you want to achieve during the implementation phase of the measure, it is important to discuss and agree them with all the stakeholders and actors involved in the process. The targets can be related to:

- the management process (e.g. number of waste prevention actions applied by hotels/restaurants, number of reuse initiative organised, etc.);
- the quantification of items/equipment (e.g. number of flasks/carafes or doggy bag distributed; number of waste sorting street bins installed; number of compost bins distributed);
- the evaluation of the tourist (citizens) reached by communication initiative
- the evaluation of the avoided production of waste (kg of organic waste, kg of plastic, kg of unsorted waste etc...)

Close to the open food market in Ortigia area will be installed 1 collection point (bin with a capacity of 230 liter) and 3 informative initiatives will be organized for promoting the measure, involving tourists and citizens to collect and deliver their used cooking oil. At least about 150 families will deliver their UCO during the informative initiatives and other 350 reached by communication campaign. Specific posts and MEDIA communications will be shared for promoting the measures and related initiatives.

In a first phase (april/june) 20 Apartments' owners will be involved and at the end of the implementation period 20 apartments will be reached by the communications strategy (with a coverures of about the 95% of the total number of apartments in Ortigia and target area and the 5% related to all Syracuse).

1 Info points will distribute the promocards. (100% of infopoints)

In total 10.000 (2000+8000)promocards/maps are foreseen to be distributed.

Taking in account that each family in Italy produce about 3kg of used cooking oil each year (data CONOU 2015<http://www.dire.it/17-05-2017/121951-rifiuti-eni-conoe-uso-oli-vegetali-biocarburanti/>) and that the implementation period is long 7 months (thus about 1,7kg per family), that about 5% of the families in the target area are about 350 (families in ortigia) and the apartments for tourists are 30/35. During the implementation phase about the 10% of the target groups will be involved, thus about 300 Kg of UCO can be collected.

Setting up the measures

Please specify what are the operative steps foreseen to set up the measure. An approximate list of actions (to be tailored according to the different kind of measures) can include:

- organization of training activities,
- setting up of help-desk activities,
- design and customization of communication materials,
- distribution of communication materials,
- purchase/distribution of equipment (when needed),
- logistic management,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organization of preliminary audits
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launching an initial communication campaign to raise awareness on used oil sorting; • Distributing oil collection points in the selected areas. • Implementing possible promotional activities to increase participation. To discuss. • Distributing communication materials. • Organization of preliminary audits.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • operative meetings and training between IONICA ambiente, IGM and Syracuse municipality for identifying the final place (where place the bin) and the related communication tools (as posters, promo card, map and so on) and planning agenda of the communication and informative initiatives • Launching an initial communication campaign to raise awareness on waste sorting and to inform on the new system being implemented, during the public signature of the PPP (normally during the 4th COP event) • Placing the sorting bin in the selected area: close to the open food market in Ortigia • Integrating the map with this measure indication • Inform the guide, the people working on the info points and the owners of touristic facilities to communicate the measure (together with the measure 12 and 14) to the tourists, and collect their feedback (foreseen 1/2 questions and a place where noting down the answers) • Distributing communication materials (with promocard measure 12+14) • Organization of preliminary audits <p>After this implementation period, the next autumn it will be discussed the possibility to equip another collection point in a touristic areas with UCO bin (near maritime areas like FontaneBianche), following also the feedback of the involved tourists.</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>It is important to evaluate the financial and logistic resources needed, underlying:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the budget available, according to the different financial sources: project's budget, public funding, private contribution etc. - the other resources available: voluntary work, free spaces, etc. - the further financial or logistic resources which have to be acquired (public funding, private sponsorships etc.)
	<p>No financial resources is needed as regard to the oil collecting points, they will be furnished directly by the private enterprise IONICA.</p> <p>As for communication material (2000 promocard, 2000 maps, 50 stickers, 300 t-shirts etc) about €2000: municipality will use the related project resources, as for the communication initiatives the Municipality will exploit public spaces.</p> <p>The Municipality will exploit the budget in communication for the organization of the 3 informative initiatives (about all the measures, but in particular measure 4) creating a Urbanwaste corners and involving experts in animation/communication related activities (about €1500).</p> <p>The Info points (staffs), tourists guides, apartments owners will participate to the informative initiatives for free.</p>
Timing	<p>When defining the timeline, please consider at least the following steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organization of a public initiative/launch event (could be during or in parallel with the 4thCoP event); February-April 2018 - start-up phase (about 2 months): final design of materials, organisation of training activities and (if needed) testing of the actions foreseen within a sample of tourist facilities; January-April 2018 - full implementation phase involving all the selected tourist facilities and targeting the different tourist categories with dedicated communication

	<p>activities which will last for, at least, 6 months; April-October 2018</p>
	<p>The municipality will respect the following timeline:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - start-up phase (about 2 months): final design of materials, organisation of informative activities: March 2018 - meeting with the involved actors: March/April 2018 and September 2018 - distribution of communication material to the apartments' owners and info points: April/May 2018 and during all the implementation phase (according with the new facilities involved) - organization of a public initiative/launch event (probably in parallel with the 4th CoP event); 26th April 2018 - full implementation phase involving all the historical centre, at least, 6 months; April-October 2018 - organization of the 3 informative initiatives: May –June – September 2018. - Monitoring phase: during the 3 informative initiatives and at the end in October.
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p><u>In relation to the targets which have been set</u> (e.g. number of waste prevention actions applied by hotels/restaurants; number of flasks/carafes or doggy bag distributed; tourists (citizens) reached by communication initiative; kg of organic waste avoided; kg of unsorted waste produced), a monitoring procedure collecting data and information from the different actors (waste and water management utilities, tourist service providers, etc) need to be developed.</p> <p>The monitoring period have to be referred to the 6-8 months of the implementation phase and it should be organized through dedicated monitoring procedures using qualitative and quantitative indicators.</p> <p>In each measure form you can find a set of suggested indicators that can be useful both for monitoring the implementation of the measure and for defining the targeted objectives.</p> <p>Qualitative indicators This kind of information is usually collected through simple questionnaires/interviews that can be done before (if needed) and at the end of the implementation phase (e.g. number of actions implemented, evaluation of the results reached using a qualitative scale, etc)</p> <p>Quantitative indicators Quantitative information can be collected, when possible, <u>during all the implementation phase</u>, in relation to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the items/equipment, e.g. pieces of furniture donated to charities, number of ashtrays/flasks/doggy bag distributed to tourists, that can be collected on a weekly or monthly basis; • the quantity of waste generated/collected using weight scales; • when it is not possible to use weight scales, data about the quantity of waste can be evaluated using an average coefficients of waste avoided/generated related to the items (furniture, doggy bag, ashtrays) and, for some measures, collecting the number of waste bags, and the related volumes and materials contained. <p>When it is not possible to collect data related to the whole implementation period, the <u>data collection phase can be focused in three different moments</u>: a week (from Monday to Sunday) BEFORE the start of the implementation phase, a week DURING the implementation phase, a week at THE END of the implementation phase.</p>

	<p>Regarding the measures involving tourist facilities like hotels and restaurants, it is important to monitor also the number of guests/customers in order to calculate a per capita value.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of collection points installed • Quantity of UCO generated (using weighing scales) per week/month/year [Litre] • Number of communication/promotion campaigns and other activities during implementation phase [Number] • Number of citizens and tourists reached • Numbers of facilities involved (apartments and supermarkets)

Measure 14 - Waste sorting instructions in foreign languages	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>It is important to make clear what are the human resources that we need for the implementation of measure and their different role and responsibilities. In particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the person in charge of the measure's implementation and monitoring (manager) - the staff supporting the manager (if needed) - the most important stakeholders that need to be involved in the implementation of the measure order to get organisational and, if possible, financial support.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manager: IGM, the enterprise of waste management service in Syracuse which will supply the contents of the promocard and share the promocard around the involved facilities together with the regular waste collection instructions. It will integrate the information on the measure during the planned events. • Supporters: Tourist offices (info points) which will distributes the promocard and support tourists to separate waste correctly supplying information related to the promocard. • Stakeholders: Owners and renters of tourist accommodations and secondary residences, Companies, marketplaces of holiday rentals, Local authorities in charge of collecting visitors' tax (Questura, police headquarters) which will distributes the promocard and info about the waste collection system of the apartments. • the municipality of Syracuse will develop the communication campaign supplying ad hoc communication items (promocard, stickers and map) further than supervise the entire implementation and monitoring phases.
Target audience	<p>Please define what are the different categories of tourist service providers you are going to addresses and the target you want to reach for each of them. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - hotels serving breakfast (can be clustered according to the different categories or the position): 20 in the historical centre + 10 in the new shopping district, and/or 25 three star hotels + 5 four/five star hotels etc etc. - hotels serving breakfast and meals: - restaurants: - bars: - camping sites: - <p>In case it is required the support of other private or public actors, please specify who do you want to involve.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - <p>For some measures, it is also important to consider what kind of tourist your measure is targeting, in order to arrange the appropriate communication approach</p>

	<p>and materials. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - foreign/local - young people/families/elderly -
<p>The category we are going to address the measure will be foreign tourists but also italian tourists.</p> <p>Take in account that touristic facilities (i.e., hotels, B&B and apartments) in Syracuse could support the measure (total number is about: 808 and about 40/45 only in Ortigia) (Fonts: infocamere, a public announcement has been done for involving and select these facilities.</p> <p>We estimate to interview at least 1500tourists (the 10% of received tourists during the implementation period) before October 2018 and to share these feedback with IGM and tourist related associations and service providers for meeting the advice and the needs of the tourists in order to reach the best separation of waste and show the city in a sustainable and clean way.</p>	
<p>Involvement of the actors</p>	<p>Once defined the target audience, please specify how do you plan to get the operative involvement of the different actors identified as target audience: for example, organization of informative initiatives, collection of expressions of interest through personal contacts, specific commitments/agreements with trade associations or single chains etc.</p>
<p>Being the tourists our target, the main means for reaching them and make useful and winning the implementation of the measure are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To Integrate the information about this measure in the regular info addressed to tourists by means of promo card of the project, into the maps of the city distributed to the tourists and into the waste APP - To inform people working as guide and in the touristic info points to communicate this measure showing the promocard and answering to possible questions <p>So the actors to involve are: IGM (the enterprise in charge of the waste management in Syracuse), tourism associations (Sicilia Turismo per tutti, Proloco and Noi Albergatori), tourist guide associations will sign the PPP for underline their role following this scheme, participate to operative meetings and informative initiatives, contributing to the contents, distributing the promocards and involving apartments' owners and tourist related facilities.</p>	
<p>Target setting</p>	<p>When setting the targets you want to achieve during the implementation phase of the measure, it is important to discuss and agree them with all the stakeholders and actors involved in the process. The targets can be related to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the management process (e.g. number of waste prevention actions applied by hotels/restaurants, number of reuse initiative organised, etc.); - the quantification of items/equipment (e.g. number of flasks/carafes or doggy bag distributed; number of waste sorting street bins installed; number of compost bins distributed); - the evaluation of the tourist (citizens) reached by communication initiative - the evaluation of the avoided production of waste (kg of organic waste, kg of plastic, kg of unsorted waste etc...)

Taking in account that Syracuse counts 1000 tourists per day (more than 2000 during spring/summer) (normally from north of Europe) the 10% at least will be reached by the measure,

Thanks to the touristic guided visits and the info points, Syracuse Municipality will try to reach all tourists visiting Syracuse and collect also the feedback of tourists: in case they are visiting or visited the pilot places, if they see the bins, if they used them and if they believe it can be useful or not.

We estimate to interview at least 1500 tourists (the 10% of received tourists during the implementation period) before October 2018 and to share these feedback with IGM and tourist related associations and service providers for meeting the advice and the needs of the tourists in order to reach the best separation of waste and show the city in a sustainable and clean way.

We plan to involve tourists (citizens) during specific communication initiatives and distributing communication materials or gadgets.

Setting up the measures

Please specify what are the operative steps foreseen to set up the measure. An approximate list of actions (to be tailored according to the different kind of measures) can include:

- organization of training activities,
- setting up of help-desk activities,
- design and customization of communication materials,
- distribution of communication materials,
- purchase/distribution of equipment (when needed),
- logistic management,
- organization of preliminary audits

- *operational meeting with actors and stakeholders for identifying the main tourist nationalities to define the languages in which the instructions will be translated*
- *study the contents of the promocard to distribute together with the separate collection instructions of the city*
- *obtaining the contact of the owners and renters of tourist accommodations*
- *Launching an initial communication campaign to raise awareness on waste sorting and to inform on the new system being implemented, during the public signature of the PPP (during the 4th COP event, 26th of April 2018)*
- *informing the guide, the people working on the info points and the owners of touristic facilities to communicate the measure (together with the measure 12 and 4) to the tourists, and collect their feedback (foreseen 1/2 questions and a place where noting down the answers)*
- *Distributing communication materials (promocard measure 12+14+4)*
- *creating a multi-languages communication campaign on sorting waste within the touristic areas, the train stations, etc.*
- *Organize informative events with apartments' owners and info points' workers*
- *Organize info corner during the main cultural events involving tourists for promoting the measure and distribute the promocards.*
- *Organization of preliminary audits (where unsorted bins are present, they will be monitored daily before installing the other bins).*

Resources available and needed

It is important to evaluate the financial and logistic resources needed, underlying:

- *the budget available, according to the different financial sources: project's budget, public funding, private contribution etc.*
- *the other resources available: voluntary work, free spaces, etc.*
- *the further financial or logistic resources which have to be acquired (public*

	<p><i>funding, private sponsorships etc.)</i></p> <p><i>No financial resources is needed as regard to the design of communication materials, IGM will adapt it to the communication they developed for the promotion of the new waste management service. For the promocard will be exploit the project layout.</i></p> <p><i>As for printing communication material, organize informative initiatives and info corners, municipality will use the related project resources. Public spaces will be used for organizing the informative initiatives, together with the promotion of the other measures.</i></p>
<p>Timing</p>	<p><i>When defining the timeline, please consider at least the following steps:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>organization of a public initiative/launch event (could be during or in parallel with the 4thCoP event); February-April 2018</i> - <i>start-up phase (about 2 months): final design of materials, organisation of training activities and (if needed) testing of the actions foreseen within a sample of tourist facilities; January-April 2018</i> - <i>full implementation phase involving all the selected tourist facilities and targeting the different tourist categories with dedicated communication activities which will last for, at least, 6 months; April-October 2018</i> <p><i>The municipality will try to respect the following timeline:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>organization of a public initiative/launch event (probably in parallel with the 4th CoP event); 26th April 2018</i> - <i>start-up phase (about 2 months): final design of materials, organisation of informative activities – 15th April 2018</i> - <i>first monitoring, before the implementation of the measure (last week of July)</i> - <i>full implementation phase and communication activities April-October 2018</i> - <i>monitoring April-October 2018</i> - <i>final evaluation and possible replication in other areas: September 2018</i> - <i>monthly collection of monitoring data related to the promocard distributed and eventual feedback from tourists.</i>
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p><i>In relation to the targets which have been set (e.g. number of waste prevention actions applied by hotels/restaurants; number of flasks/carafes or doggy bag distributed; tourists (citizens) reached by communication initiative; kg of organic waste avoided; kg of unsorted waste produced), a monitoring procedure collecting data and information from the different actors (waste and water management utilities, tourist service providers, etc) need to be developed.</i></p> <p><i>The monitoring period have to be referred to the 6-8 months of the implementation phase and it should be organized through dedicated monitoring procedures using qualitative and quantitative indicators.</i></p> <p><i>In each measure form you can find a set of suggested indicators that can be useful both for monitoring the implementation of the measure and for defining the targeted objectives.</i></p> <p>Qualitative indicators</p> <p><i>This kind of information is usually collected through simple questionnaires/interviews that can be done before (if needed) and at the end of the implementation phase (e.g. number of actions implemented, evaluation of the results reached using a qualitative scale, etc)</i></p>

Quantitative indicators

Quantitative information can be collected, when possible, during all the implementation phase, in relation to:

- the **items/equipment**, e.g. pieces of furniture donated to charities, number of ashtrays/flasks/doggy bag distributed to tourists, that can be collected on a weekly or monthly basis;
- the quantity of **waste generated/collected using weight scales**;
- when it is not possible to use weight scales, data about the quantity of **waste can be evaluated using an average coefficients** of waste avoided/generated related to the items (furniture, doggy bag, ashtrays) and, for some measures, collecting the number of waste bags, and the related volumes and materials contained.

When it is not possible to collect data related to the whole implementation period, the data collection phase can be focused in three different moments: a week (from Monday to Sunday) **BEFORE** the start of the implementation phase, a week **DURING** the implementation phase, a week at **THE END** of the implementation phase.

Regarding the measures involving tourist facilities like hotels and restaurants, it is important to monitor also the **number of guests/customers** in order to calculate a per capita value.

- Number of distributed waste instructions leaflets [Number]
- Mapping of touristic establishments that provide waste instructions leaflets to tourists [Name and address of the establishment]: apartments, info points, other facilities and events.
- Number of tourists potentially affected by the measure [Number]

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

FLORENCE – REGIONE TOSCANA

Protocollo d'intesa per la costituzione di una partnership pubblico-privato per lo sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure previste dal progetto URBAN-WASTE

**URBAN
WASTE**
URBAN STRATEGIES FOR
WASTE MANAGEMENT
IN TOURIST CITIES

Il progetto UrBAN-WASTE

UrBAN WASTE è un progetto finanziato dal programma di ricerca Europeo Horizon 2020 che ha l'obiettivo di supportare i decisori politici in una gestione sempre più sostenibile dei flussi di rifiuti prodotti dai turisti. La minimizzazione della produzione di rifiuti è una componente importante nella qualificazione dell'offerta turistica e nella promozione di una crescita "smart" e sostenibile delle città turistiche europee.

Flussi turistici sempre più consistenti e spesso concentrati in determinati periodi dell'anno comportano una serie di esternalità negative che rendono più complessa la sfida relativa alla riduzione e migliore gestione dei rifiuti con cui le città devono confrontarsi.

Considerato che:

A Giugno 2016 il progetto UrBAN WASTE ha avuto inizio, coinvolgendo 27 partner europei tra cui Regione Toscana (RT), Government of Canary Islands (coordinatore), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)].

Le principali attività previste dal progetto sono:

1. Sviluppare nuove strategie eco-innovative, attente anche alle differenze di genere, e buone pratiche in grado di ridurre la produzione complessiva di rifiuti urbani e incentivare la corretta gestione, la raccolta, il riuso e il riciclo dei rifiuti nelle città turistiche. Queste strategie saranno sviluppate in 11 città pilota Firenze (IT), Nizza (FR), Lisbona (PT), Siracusa (IT), Copenaghen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] e i risultati

saranno adeguatamente monitorati e disseminati in modo da facilitare il trasferimento in altre realtà.

2. Coinvolgere gli stakeholder locali in un processo partecipativo che attraverso la creazione delle Comunità di Pratica in cui partecipano, in modo bilanciato, uomini e donne operanti nel settore turistico, nel settore dei rifiuti, nel modo dell'associazionismo, ecc., prevede lo sviluppo di strategie e misure volte alla riduzione della produzione dei rifiuti e a una loro migliore gestione.
3. Assicurare che ogni misura sia realizzata grazie all'effettivo coinvolgimento di stakeholder locali pubblici e/o privati che, sottoscrivendo il presente accordo volontario, si impegnano a fornire il loro contributo per ridurre la produzione di rifiuti e promuovere il progetto UrBAN WASTE.

Il presente accordo volontario per lo sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure previste dal progetto UrBAN-WASTE, sottoscritto in data 14 maggio 2018,

Firmatario A - Regione Toscana

Firmatario B - Comune di Firenze

Firmatario C - Città Metropolitana di Firenze

Firmatario D - Agenzia Regionale Recupero Risorse

Firmatario E - ATO Toscana Centro

Firmatario F - Alia Spa

Firmatario G - Publiacqua Spa

Firmatario H - Associazioni di categoria: Confcommercio Firenze, Confesercenti Firenze, Confindustria Firenze, Federalberghi Firenze, CISPEL, etc.

Firmatario I – Enti assistenziali e/o associazioni del terzo settore che si occupano di solidarietà sociale: Associazione Banco Alimentare della Toscana onlus, Associazione di volontariato Solidarietà Caritas onlus- Firenze, etc.

Firmatario L – Consorzi di filiera: Comieco, Cial, etc.

Firmatario M – Associazioni di consumatori, ambientaliste etc.: Angeli del Bello, Legambiente, Turismo senza barriere, etc

Firmatario N - Strutture ricettive, esercizi commerciali: WTB Hotels, etc

Firmatario O – Istituti scolastici: Istituto Tecnico Turismo Marco Polo

Firmatario P – Comuni del Chianti Fiorentino

prevede nello specifico lo sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure:

- n. 1 “Doggy Bag” e n. 2 “Prevenzione dello spreco ai buffet e nei ristoranti”;
- n. 13 “Promozione dell’uso dell’acqua di rete”;
- n. 14 “Istruzioni sulla raccolta differenziata in diverse lingue”,
- n. 22 “Donazione del cibo da parte di hotel e ristoranti ad associazioni benefiche”,

attraverso l’effettivo coinvolgimento degli stakeholder locali (enti pubblici, gestori del servizio rifiuti, operatori del settore turistico, associazioni locali, ecc.) che operano a Firenze nello svolgimento di azioni volte a ridurre la produzione di rifiuti e a promuovere una gestione sostenibile degli stessi. Le azioni contribuiscono a raggiungere gli obiettivi generali stabiliti dal Programma Nazionale di prevenzione dei Rifiuti, dal Piano Nazionale di prevenzione dello spreco alimentare e dal Programma di prevenzione regionale (All.2 del Piano Regionale di gestione dei rifiuti e bonifica dei siti inquinati DCR n°94 del 18/11/2014)

Adesioni successive alla sottoscrizione

Le parti concordano sulla possibilità di accettare, previa valutazione della congruità con le finalità del presente protocollo, adesioni successive alla data di sottoscrizione dello stesso, nei limiti possibili rispetto allo stato di avanzamento dei lavori.

Impegni

Le parti quindi concordano, di supportare lo sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure sopra ricordate del progetto UrBAN-WASTE nella città di Firenze e di partecipare attivamente ai lavori della Comunità di Pratica locale che sarà responsabile dell'implementazione delle misure secondo i ruoli e le azioni che saranno dettagliati nei singoli Piani Operativi. I firmatari di questo accordo volontario si impegnano a rispettare gli impegni previsti per le organizzazioni che rappresentano in quanto coerenti con la loro mission istituzionale e commerciale.

Con la sottoscrizione del seguente accordo volontario, le parti assumono i seguenti impegni, che saranno meglio specificati nei singoli Piani Operativi che saranno sviluppati dai soggetti sottoscrittori del presente accordo.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario A - REGIONE TOSCANA
- Realizza le attività di progetto e assicura la realizzazione e lo sviluppo delle misure con il coinvolgimento degli stakeholder;
- Fornisce supporto tecnico e logistico nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure;
- Organizza e finanzia, con le risorse già stanziato per il progetto, le attività di comunicazione: la divulgazione e conoscenza del progetto sarà supportata da una campagna di comunicazione uguale per ogni misura e da strumenti specifici per rendere riconoscibili e valorizzare, da un punto di vista comunicativo, i soggetti che aderiranno alla realizzazione delle misure;
- Promuove il recupero del cibo nei catering degli eventi istituzionali e nelle proprie sedi;
- Promuove una comunicazione attenta alle differenze di genere eliminando gli stereotipi di genere;

- IMPEGNO del firmatario B - Comune di Firenze
 - Collabora alle attività finalizzate alla realizzazione delle misure;
 - Fornisce supporto tecnico e logistico nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure;
 - Promuove le misure e collabora alla diffusione dei materiali di comunicazione previsti dal progetto anche attraverso gli uffici di informazione turistica, con pubblicazione di avvisi e distribuzione dei materiali di comunicazione previsti dal progetto, in collaborazione con la Città Metropolitana di Firenze.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario C - Città Metropolitana di Firenze
 - Collabora alle attività finalizzate alla realizzazione delle misure;
 - Fornisce supporto tecnico e logistico nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure;
 - Promuove le misure e collabora alla diffusione dei materiali di comunicazione previsti dal progetto anche attraverso gli uffici di informazione turistica, con pubblicazione di avvisi e distribuzione dei materiali di comunicazione previsti dal progetto, in collaborazione con il Comune di Firenze;
 - Offre una riduzione sul biglietto di ingresso a Palazzo Medici Riccardi ai turisti che dimostrano di aver gestito i propri rifiuti attraverso l'uso della WasteApp, applicazione mobile.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario D - Agenzia Regionale Recupero Risorse (ARRR)
 - Fornisce supporto tecnico nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure;
 - Coordina le attività finalizzate alla realizzazione della misura n. 22;
 - Si impegna a cercare di ridurre gli svantaggi di genere nello sviluppo e realizzazione della misura n.22.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario E – ATO Toscana Centro
 - Fornisce supporto tecnico nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario F – ALIA spa
 - Fornisce supporto tecnico nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure;
 - Coordina le attività finalizzate alla realizzazione della misura n. 14;

- IMPEGNO del firmatario G - PUBBLIACQUA
 - Fornisce supporto tecnico nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure;

- IMPEGNO del firmatario H - Associazioni di categoria: Confcommercio Firenze, Confesercenti Firenze, Confindustria Firenze, Federalberghi Firenze, CISPEL, etc.
 - Collaborano alla diffusione dei contenuti e delle attività presso i propri associati e forniscono supporto nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario I – Enti assistenziali e/o associazioni del terzo settore che si occupano di solidarietà sociale: Associazione Banco Alimentare della Toscana onlus, Associazione di volontariato Solidarietà Caritas onlus- Firenze, etc.
 - Forniscono supporto tecnico e operativo nello sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure;

- IMPEGNO del firmatario L — Consorzi di filiera: Comieco, Cial, etc.
 - Collaborano alla diffusione dei contenuti e delle attività.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario M – Associazioni di consumatori, ambientaliste etc.: Angeli del Bello, LEGAMBIENTE, Turismo senza barriere
 - Collaborano alla diffusione dei contenuti e delle attività.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario N - Strutture ricettive, esercizi commerciali: WTB Hotels, etc
 - Collaborano alla realizzazione delle attività finalizzate all'attuazione delle misure;
 - Collaborano all'attività di coinvolgimento dei turisti attraverso l'esposizione e/o distribuzione di materiali di comunicazione.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario O - Istituto Tecnico Turismo Marco Polo:
 - Promuove l'iniziativa, attraverso le piattaforme social, e la diffusione dei materiali di comunicazione previsti dal progetto.

- IMPEGNO del firmatario P - Comuni del Chianti Fiorentino:
 - Mettono a disposizione l'esperienza maturata nel progetto Life Wasteless in Chianti, incentrato sulla prevenzione e riduzione dei rifiuti, le cui azioni sono ancora in fase di attuazione.

Termini e durata

Questo accordo è di natura volontaria e può essere modificato con il consenso delle parti. Esso diventerà effettivo una volta firmato da uno dei rappresentanti dei partner del progetto UrBAN WASTE il 14 maggio 2018 e rimarrà in essere fino ad una sua eventuale successiva modifica o termine da parte di un soggetto firmatario, con il mutuo consenso delle parti. In caso non si verifichi una di queste situazioni, la valenza dell'accordo terminerà il 31 maggio 2019.

Noi, di seguito firmatari, dichiariamo di aver letto e accettato i termini e le condizioni dell'accordo sopra descritto.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Piano Operativo per l'attuazione della misura n. 13 - Promozione dell'uso di acqua di rete

Attuazione delle misure dimostrative di prevenzione e gestione dei rifiuti

Misura n. 13	
I promotori: ruoli e responsabilità	<p><i>E' importante definire chiaramente quali siano le risorse umane di cui abbiamo bisogno per attuare le azioni, e quali siano i diversi ruoli e responsabilità.</i></p> <p><i>In particolare:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>la persona responsabile dell'attuazione delle azioni e del monitoraggio (manager);</i> - <i>la squadra che supporta il manager (se necessario);</i> - <i>i più importanti stakeholders che è necessario coinvolgere nell'attuazione delle misure per avere un supporto organizzativo e, se possibile, finanziario (per esempio associazioni di categoria, associazioni di beneficenza, attori pubblici o privati, come la società di gestione dei rifiuti o di gestione della rete idrica).</i>
<p>L'azione prevede il coinvolgimento dei seguenti soggetti, che saranno firmatari del un protocollo d'intesa:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regione Toscana: coordina e realizza i materiali di comunicazione con fondi di progetto. Promuove il censimento delle fontane pubbliche da pubblicizzare nei materiali di comunicazione e nella App di progetto. • Comune di Firenze (assessorato all'Ambiente e assessorato al Turismo): fornisce permessi e spazi per le affissioni negli stalli comunali e per la distribuzione dei materiali presso gli infopoint turistici, inoltre dà supporto e spazi per la realizzazione delle azioni e delle iniziative di promozione del progetto. • Città Metropolitana: promuove l'iniziativa in collaborazione con il Comune. • Publicacqua: effettua le analisi delle acque presso i pubblici esercizi, inoltre fornisce bottiglie di vetro riutilizzabili ai pubblici esercizi che ne fanno richiesta, si occupa di apporre gli adesivi di progetto sui fontanelli di acqua di alta qualità presenti in città; • ALIA: verifica la disponibilità di contenitori per la raccolta differenziata nelle vicinanze delle aree attrezzate; • Confcommercio imprese per l'Italia della Provincia di Firenze: contattano i propri aderenti e diffondono l'iniziativa. • Confesercenti Metropolitana di Firenze: contattano i propri aderenti e diffondono l'iniziativa. <p>L'azione è coordinata dalla Regione Toscana in collaborazione con Publicacqua Spa.</p>	
I destinatari	<p><i>Definire quali sono le diverse categorie di fornitori di servizi turistici che vogliamo raggiungere con l'attuazione dell'azione, e, se possibile, stimarne il bacino complessivo.</i></p> <p><i>Per esempio:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>hotel che servono colazioni: l'insieme può essere caratterizzato in base alla zona (a Firenze ci sono 200 hotel nel centro storico e 100 nella zona esterna) e/o in base alle stelle (a Firenze ci sono 5 hotel 5 stelle, 25 tre stelle, ecc.)</i> - <i>hotel con ristorante (che servono colazioni e pasti);</i> - <i>ristoranti;</i> - <i>bar;</i> - <i>....</i> <p><i>Se è necessario il coinvolgimento di attori pubblici o privati, specificare chi si vuole coinvolgere.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>.....</i> - <i>.....</i> <p><i>Per alcune misure, è anche importante considerare a che tipo di turista la misura è rivolta, con lo scopo di sviluppare idonei materiali di comunicazione.</i></p>

	<p><i>Per esempio:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - estera/locale; - giovani, famiglie, anziani; -
<p>L'azione si rivolge a:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bar del centro storico del comune di Firenze • Ristoratori del centro storico del comune di Firenze • Turisti e cittadini del comune di Firenze 	
Coinvolgimento degli attori	<p><i>Una volta definiti i beneficiari, specificare come si intende riuscire a coinvolgere operativamente i diversi attori identificati nella sezione precedente: per esempio, organizzazione di iniziative informative, attivazione di contatti personali, specifici accordi con associazioni di categoria, ecc.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comune di Firenze, Publiacqua e Alia organizzeranno un incontro per identificare le attrezzature necessarie per la realizzazione delle aree attrezzate (in coordinamento con misura 14) e per il censimento e la riattivazione di fontane pubbliche esistenti; • Le associazioni di categoria si occuperanno di contattare e coinvolgere ristoratori, in modo coordinato con il gruppo di lavoro sullo spreco alimentare per identificare e contattare quegli esercizi che, oltre alla riduzione degli sprechi di cibo, sono disponibili a realizzare anche azioni per la promozione dell'acqua di rubinetto (o viceversa). • Con l'aiuto delle associazioni di categoria contattare le altre strutture (in prevalenza Bar) potenzialmente disponibili a realizzare azioni di promozione dell'acqua di rubinetto, sia inviando una mail contenente le informazioni relative al progetto e alle azioni da attuare, che attraverso contatti personali. • Effettuare un incontro formativo/informativo a Aprile 2018 con un primo gruppo di aspiranti aderenti. • Una volta partita l'iniziativa, organizzare un evento/incontro a Giugno/Luglio 2018 in cui mostrare i primi risultati raggiunti con l'obiettivo di coinvolgere un maggior numero di aderenti.
Obiettivi	<p><i>Definire e concordare con tutti gli stakeholder gli obiettivi che si vogliono raggiungere con la realizzazione dell'azione.</i></p> <p><i>Gli obiettivi possono essere collegati a:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - il processo di gestione (per esempio il numero di azioni di prevenzione dei rifiuti attuate da hotel/ristoranti, numero di iniziative del riuso organizzate, ecc.); - il bacino di destinatari che si punta a raggiungere (ovvero la percentuale del bacino definito nella sezione precedente, il 5% degli hotel del centro storico, ad esempio); - la quantificazione di articoli/attrezzature (per esempio numero di borracce/caraffe o doggy bag distribuite, numero di cestini per la raccolta differenziata installati lungo le strade, numero di compostiere distribuite); - la stima dei turisti (cittadini) raggiunti dalle iniziative di comunicazione; - la valutazione della riduzione della produzione dei rifiuti (kg di rifiuto organico, kg di plastica, kg di rifiuto indifferenziato, ecc...).
<p>L'azione si pone come obiettivo principale l'incremento dell'uso di acqua di rete per ottenere una riduzione della produzione dei rifiuti. Inoltre si propone di educare i visitatori a un turismo responsabile e sostenibile, offrendo una migliore accoglienza nelle aree appositamente attrezzate.</p> <p>L'attuazione delle diverse azioni per questa misura si propone di perseguire i seguenti obiettivi:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realizzazione di due aree turisticamente attrezzate; • Valorizzazione delle nuove fontane pubbliche; • Coinvolgimento di almeno n. 10 esercenti. 	
Attuazione delle misure	<p><i>Descrivere quali sono i passi operativi per attuare le misure. Una lista approssimativa delle azioni (da adattare a seconda dei diversi tipi di azioni) può includere:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organizzazione di attività di formazione; - creazione di attività di assistenza (help-desk); - progettazione e personalizzazione dei materiali di comunicazione; - distribuzione dei materiali di comunicazione; - vendita/distribuzione delle attrezzature (se necessario); - gestione logistica;

- *organizzazione di audit preliminari.*

L'attuazione si propone di realizzare le seguenti azioni:

1. **Creazione di luoghi dell'accoglienza attrezzati:** valorizzazione e promozione di aree verdi dotate di fontanello per la distribuzione gratuita di acqua di rete, panchine per il ristoro, contenitori per la raccolta differenziata.

Per quanto riguarda questa azione:

- Il Comune di Firenze si impegna a verificare che le aree siano accessibili e in ordine;
- Il gestore del servizio rifiuti ALIA si impegna a verificare che siano disponibili contenitori per la raccolta differenziata delle principali frazioni merceologiche;
- Il gestore del servizio idrico Publiacqua si impegna a verificare il corretto funzionamento dei fontanelli.

E' in corso di verifica la possibilità di realizzare una nuova area attrezzata Urban Waste in un luogo di significativa presenza turistica.

2. **Censimento e valorizzazione delle fontane pubbliche del centro storico.**

Per quanto riguarda questa azione:

- La Regione Toscana e il Comune di Firenze si impegnano a individuare un set di fontane pubbliche localizzate nel centro storico da inserire nella mappa di progetto;

3. **Distribuzione di borracce "griffate"** con il logo della campagna "Florence Urban Water" durante eventi appositamente organizzati.

- La Regione Toscana provvede all'acquisto delle borracce e, insieme con i firmatari del progetto, organizza e promuove eventi dedicati. Le borracce faranno parte anche del kit di benvenuto (contenente sacchetto, borraccia e mappa con i luoghi e servizi Urban Waste) che i turisti potranno ricevere come premio per aver utilizzato la APP di progetto.
- Publiacqua Spa si impegna alla realizzazione di ulteriori borracce con il logo "Florence Urban Water".

4. **Locali "Urban Waste" con acqua pubblica:** individuare una rete di pubblici esercizi disponibili a fornire acqua di rete. Tali esercenti saranno promossi nella campagna informativa e saranno identificabili mediante un apposito logo.

Per quanto riguarda questa azione:

- Le associazioni di categoria si impegnano a contattare i propri aderenti e a promuovere il progetto, con lo scopo di raggiungere il target definito nei paragrafi precedenti;
- Publiacqua si impegna ad analizzare l'acqua di rete del pubblico esercizio, rilasciando idonea documentazione da esporre nel locale;
- I pubblici esercizi aderenti si impegnano a
 - promuovere l'azione nel proprio esercizio, fornendo ai clienti che consumano con servizio al tavolo, acqua di rete e non in bottiglia a perdere;
- I pubblici esercizi aderenti saranno inclusi nella campagna di comunicazione e riceveranno tutti i materiali previsti, come, ad esempio, la vetrofania e l'adesivo per le brocche.

CAMPAGNA DI COMUNICAZIONE

La campagna di Comunicazione prevede la realizzazione di:

- Una conferenza stampa, per il lancio della fase sperimentale del Progetto, che sarà organizzata a Maggio 2018;
- Organizzazione di eventi dedicati alla promozione del progetto, tra cui:
 - un primo evento di lancio della campagna di comunicazione relativa a tutte e quattro le misure

sviluppate a Firenze (Giugno-Luglio 2018);

- eventuali eventi specifici dedicati alla promozione della misura;
- un evento alla fine della campagna per promuovere i risultati raggiunti, valorizzare gli esercenti coinvolti e rilanciare nuove iniziative (Settembre-Ottobre 2018).

Si prevede la produzione e diffusione dei seguenti materiali di comunicazione:

Materiale generale relativo a tutte le misure

- Affissioni di manifesti (stalli comunali 70x100 e 6mx3m) e locandine in città, soprattutto presso infopoint turistici del comune di Firenze.
- Mappe promozionali con indicazione della localizzazione di fontanelli, fontane pubbliche, contenitori per la raccolta differenziata, distribuite presso infopoint turistici del comune di Firenze.
- Realizzazione di promocard da distribuire presso infopoint turistici, strutture ricettive, volantinaggio durante iniziative di comunicazione, ecc;
- Vetrofanie per identificare i locali aderenti al progetto Urban Waste;
- WasteApp: applicazione sviluppata nell'ambito del progetto contenente informazioni relative all'elenco dei pubblici esercizi aderenti al progetto e alle istruzioni per una corretta raccolta differenziata. L'applicazione, rivolta prevalentemente ai turisti, esorta gli utenti a utilizzare i contenitori per la raccolta differenziata e le fontanelle di acqua di rete, e tramite un meccanismo di gioco li ricompensa con premi, come ingressi al museo scontati o il kit di benvenuto (contenente sacchetto, borraccia e mappa con i luoghi e servizi Urban Waste), se effettivamente li utilizzano.

Materiale specifico per bar e ristoranti: acqua

- Stickers per brocche "Florence Urban Water";
- Bottiglie con logo Publiacqua.

Materiale specifico per bar e ristoranti: raccolta differenziata (se richiesto da alcuni aderenti)

- Contenitori di cartone forniti eventualmente da Comieco per la raccolta della carta.

Comunicazione sul web

Sito del Comune di Firenze : <http://www.firenzeturismo.it/it/>

Siti web di alcuni stakeholder (www.aliaspa.it, www.publiacqua.it)

sito di progetto <http://www.urban-waste.eu/>

sito della comunità di pratica <http://www.urban-waste.eu/florence-cop/>

<p>Risorse disponibili e necessarie</p>	<p><i>E' importante stimare le risorse finanziarie e logistiche necessarie:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>il budget disponibile, secondo le diverse fonti finanziarie: budget di progetto, fondi pubblici, contributi privati, ecc.</i> - <i>le altre risorse disponibili: lavoro volontario, spazi liberi, ecc.</i> - <i>ulteriori risorse finanziarie o logistiche che devono essere acquistate (fondi pubblici, sponsorizzazioni private, ecc.).</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget disponibile per realizzazione dei materiali di comunicazione: € 13.000 • Per lo sviluppo del piano di comunicazione il Comune mette a disposizione 10 stalli 70x100 nel centro storico (vetrine del centro storico) e 60 stalli murali 70x100 (per 3 cicli di affissioni). Inoltre saranno effettuate due affissioni negli stalli 6mx3m. In aggiunta saranno inseriti i materiali di progetti tra quelli proiettati a rotazione nei 42 display collocati in 24 luoghi diversi dell'area metropolitana. • Publiacqua effettua le analisi delle acque presso i pubblici esercizi, inoltre fornisce bottiglie di vetro riutilizzabili ai pubblici esercizi che ne fanno richiesta. Fornirà inoltre 250 borracce riutilizzabili con logo. • Alia fornisce contenitori per la raccolta differenziata nelle aree attrezzate.
<p>Tempistica</p>	<p><i>Quando si definisce il cronoprogramma, considerare le seguenti scadenze:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>organizzazione di una iniziativa pubblica di lancio (può essere in parallelo con il quarto incontro della comunità di pratica), tra Febbraio e Aprile 2018;</i> - <i>fase di start-up (circa 2 mesi): progettazione finale dei materiali, organizzazione di attività formative e (se necessario) test delle azioni con un campione di strutture turistiche, Gennaio – Aprile 2018;</i> - <i>fase di completa attuazione della misura, coinvolgendo tutte le strutture turistiche e le diverse categorie di turisti individuate tra "i destinatari", con apposite campagne di comunicazione dedicate. Questa fase deve durare almeno 6 mesi, Aprile – Ottobre 2018.</i>

Il cronoprogramma dell'azione prevede:

- Coinvolgimento dei pubblici esercizi per la realizzazione dell'azione entro Marzo/Aprile 2018
- Firma del protocollo di Intesa a Maggio 2018
- Sperimentazione dell'attuazione da Maggio 2018;
- Attuazione a regime dell'azione da Giugno a Dicembre 2018.

Monitoraggio

Tenendo conto degli obiettivi individuati è necessario sviluppare una procedura per il monitoraggio, con la raccolta di dati e informazioni dai diversi attori (gestore dei rifiuti e della rete idrica, fornitori dei servizi turistici, ecc.) coinvolti, con lo scopo di valutare il raggiungimento o meno di tali obiettivi. Il monitoraggio si riferisce al periodo di 6-8 mesi di attuazione a regime delle misure.

Indicatori qualitativi

Questo tipo di informazioni sono generalmente raccolte attraverso semplici questionari/interviste che possono essere richiesti prima dell'implementazione della misura (se necessario) e alla fine della fase di attuazione a regime (per esempio: numero di azioni attuate, valutazione dei risultati raggiunti su una scala qualitativa, ecc.)

Indicatori quantitativi

I dati relative alla quantità di rifiuti prodotti possono essere raccolti pesando i rifiuti e riempiendo una scheda di monitoraggio in tre diversi momenti: una settimana (da lunedì a domenica) PRIMA dell'inizio della fase di attuazione, un'altra settimana DURANTE la fase di attuazione e infine una settimana DOPO la fase di finale.

Per quanto riguarda le misure che coinvolgono le strutture turistiche come hotel e ristoranti, è importante monitorare anche il numero di ospiti/clienti per poter calcolare i valori procapite.

In alternativa, i dati relative alla quantità dei rifiuti prodotti possono essere stimati in base al numero di sacchi di rifiuti generati (nota la volumetria e la frazione merceologica).

Per verificare l'attuazione di questa azione saranno acquisiti i seguenti dati, necessari per calcolare i relativi indicatori di monitoraggio:

- litri di acqua erogati dai fontanelli pubblici per mese (si richiede anche il dato storico dell'anno precedente);
- n. di fontane pubbliche promosse con la campagna di comunicazione;
- n. di esercenti aderenti all'iniziativa;
- n. di bottiglie riutilizzabili distribuite;
- n. di borracce distribuite.

Saranno poi sviluppati alcuni indicatori relativi alla campagna di comunicazione:

- n. mappe realizzate e distribuite;
- n. di promocard realizzate e distribuite;
- n. di partecipanti agli eventi.

Piano Operativo per l'attuazione della misura n. 14 - Istruzioni sulla raccolta differenziata in diverse lingue

Attuazione delle misure dimostrative di prevenzione e gestione dei rifiuti

Misura n. 14	
I promotori: ruoli e responsabilità	<p><i>E' importante definire chiaramente quali siano le risorse umane di cui abbiamo bisogno per attuare le azioni, e quali siano i diversi ruoli e responsabilità.</i></p> <p><i>In particolare:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>la persona responsabile dell'attuazione delle azioni e del monitoraggio (manager);</i> - <i>la squadra che supporta il manager (se necessario);</i> - <i>i più importanti stakeholders che è necessario coinvolgere nell'attuazione delle misure per avere un supporto organizzativo e, se possibile, finanziario (per esempio associazioni di categoria, associazioni di beneficenza, attori pubblici o privati, come la società di gestione dei rifiuti o di gestione della rete idrica).</i>
<p>L'azione prevede il coinvolgimento dei seguenti soggetti, firmatari del protocollo d'intesa:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ALIA: coordina le azioni, verifica la disponibilità di contenitori per la raccolta differenziata nelle vicinanze delle aree attrezzate e prepara e stampa le brochure multilingua. • Regione Toscana: coordina e realizza i materiali di comunicazione con fondi di progetto. • Comune di Firenze (Assessorato all'Ambiente e assessorato al Turismo): fornisce permessi e spazi per le affissioni negli stalli comunali e per la distribuzione dei materiali presso gli infopoint turistici, inoltre da supporto e spazi per la realizzazione delle azioni e delle iniziative di promozione del progetto. • Città Metropolitana: promuove l'iniziativa in collaborazione con il Comune; • Ato Toscana Centro: fornisce supporto tecnico per lo sviluppo dell'azione. 	
I destinatari	<p><i>Definire quali sono le diverse categorie di fornitori di servizi turistici che vogliamo raggiungere con l'attuazione dell'azione, e, se possibile, stimarne il bacino complessivo.</i></p> <p><i>Per esempio:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>hotel che servono colazioni: l'insieme può essere caratterizzato in base alla zona (a Firenze ho 200 hotel nel centro storico e 100 nella zona esterna) e/o in base alle stelle (a Firenze ho 5 hotel 5 stelle, 25 tre stelle, ecc.)</i> - <i>hotel con ristorante (che servono colazioni e pasti);</i> - <i>ristoranti;</i> - <i>bar;</i> - <i>.....</i> <p><i>Se è necessario il coinvolgimento di attori pubblici o privati, specificare chi si vuole coinvolgere.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>.....</i> - <i>.....</i> <p><i>Per alcune misure, è anche importante considerare a che tipo di turista la misura è rivolta, con lo scopo di sviluppare idonei materiali di comunicazione.</i></p> <p><i>Per esempio:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>estera/locale;</i> - <i>giovani, famiglie, anziani;</i> - <i>.....</i>
<p>L'azione si rivolge a:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proprietari e gestori di camere e appartamenti in affitto e/o di sharing economy • Strutture alberghiere e B&B • Turisti che pernottano almeno una notte (sia in alberghi e B&B, sia in altre strutture in affitto e/o di 	

sharing economy).	
Coinvolgimento degli attori	<i>Una volta definiti i beneficiari, specificare come si intende riuscire a coinvolgere operativamente i diversi attori identificati nella sezione precedente: per esempio, organizzazione di iniziative informative, attivazione di contatti personali, specifici accordi con associazioni di categoria, ecc.</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comune di Firenze, Publiacqua e Alia organizzeranno un incontro per identificare le attrezzature necessarie per la realizzazione delle aree attrezzate (in coordinamento con misura 13) • Gli enti coinvolti si impegnano a diffondere il progetto in generale e le istruzioni per una corretta raccolta differenziata in particolare ciascuno sui propri canali informativi, ad esempio, per quanto riguarda il comune di Firenze, mediante tutti gli infopoint turistici. • Iniziative specifiche saranno mirate al coinvolgimento Proprietari e gestori di camere e appartamenti in affitto e/o di sharing economy. 	
Obiettivi	<p><i>Definire e concordare con tutti gli stakeholders gli obiettivi che si vogliono raggiungere con la realizzazione dell'azione.</i></p> <p><i>Gli obiettivi possono essere collegati a:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>il processo di gestione (per esempio il numero di azioni di prevenzione dei rifiuti attuate da hotel/ristoranti, numero di iniziative del riuso organizzate, ecc.);</i> - <i>il bacino di destinatari che si punta a raggiungere (ovvero la percentuale del bacino definito nella sezione precedente, il 5% degli hotel del centro storico, ad esempio);</i> - <i>la quantificazione di articoli/attrezzature (per esempio numero di borracce/caraffe o doggy bag distribuite, numero di cestini per la raccolta differenziata installati lungo le strade, numero di compostiere distribuite);</i> - <i>la stima dei turisti (cittadini) raggiunti dalle iniziative di comunicazione;</i> - <i>la valutazione della riduzione della produzione dei rifiuti (kg di rifiuto organico, kg di plastica, kg di rifiuto indifferenziato, ecc...).</i>
<p>Gli obiettivi quantificabili della misura sono i seguenti:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - distribuzione di n. 20.000 brochure multilingue e altri strumenti di comunicazione (italiano/inglese) contenenti istruzioni semplici, intuitive, usando immagini evocative, in modo da rendere semplice la raccolta differenziata per i turisti. La distribuzione è prevista nel corso del mese di maggio. - Realizzazione di due aree turisticamente attrezzate. 	
Attuazione delle misure	<p><i>Descrivere quali sono i passi operativi per attuare le misure. Una lista approssimativa delle azioni (da adattare a seconda dei diversi tipi di azioni) può includere:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>organizzazione di attività di formazione;</i> - <i>creazione di attività di assistenza (help-desk);</i> - <i>progettazione e personalizzazione dei materiali di comunicazione;</i> - <i>distribuzione dei materiali di comunicazione;</i> - <i>vendita/distribuzione delle attrezzature (se necessario);</i> - <i>gestione logistica;</i> - <i>organizzazione di audit preliminari.</i>
<p>L'attuazione si propone di realizzare le seguenti azioni:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creazione di luoghi dell'accoglienza attrezzati: valorizzazione e promozione di aree verdi dotate di fontanello per la distribuzione gratuita di acqua di rete, panchine per il ristoro, contenitori per la raccolta differenziata. <p>Per quanto riguarda questa azione:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Il Comune di Firenze si impegna a verificare che le aree siano accessibili e in ordine; • Il gestore del servizio rifiuti ALIA si impegna a verificare che siano disponibili contenitori per la raccolta differenziata delle principali frazioni merceologiche; <p>Questa azione è comune con la misura 13 – promozione dell'acqua di rete.</p>	

1. **Diffusione delle istruzioni sulla raccolta differenziata.** Tutti gli attori devono essere coinvolti con una apposita campagna informativa che prevederà la diffusione di messaggi contenenti istruzioni per una corretta raccolta differenziata attraverso il sito del gestore e attraverso la WasteApp realizzata nell'ambito del progetto Urban Waste che conterrà il link alla descrizione in più lingue sulle corrette modalità di conferimento dei rifiuti da parte di cittadini e turisti.

Per quanto riguarda questa azione:

- Il gestore dei rifiuti ALIA prepara e stampa la brochure multilingua contenente le informazioni relative alle modalità di raccolta differenziata ed eventuali altri strumenti a supporto;
- Organizzazione di iniziative specifiche al fine di rendere disponibili le brochure in case e appartamenti in affitto o gestiti da piattaforme di sharing economy
- Gli enti coinvolti si impegnano a promuovere accordi con le piattaforme di sharing economy per la diffusione delle istruzioni nelle seconde case.
- Il Comune si impegna a diffondere le brochure nei propri canali informativi, come i punti di informazione turistica, presenti nei luoghi strategici della città;
- Tutti i promotori della misura si impegnano a diffondere la App di progetto che conterrà il link alle istruzioni multilingue sulle modalità di raccolta differenziata;

CAMPAGNA DI COMUNICAZIONE

La campagna di Comunicazione prevede la realizzazione di:

- Una conferenza stampa, per il lancio della fase sperimentale del Progetto, che sarà organizzata a Maggio 2018;
- Organizzazione di eventi dedicati alla promozione del progetto, tra cui:
 - un primo evento di lancio della campagna di comunicazione relativa a tutte e quattro le misure sviluppate a Firenze (Giugno-Luglio 2018);
 - eventuali eventi specifici dedicati alla promozione della misura;
 - un evento alla fine della campagna per promuovere i risultati raggiunti, valorizzare gli esercenti coinvolti e rilanciare nuove iniziative (Settembre-Ottobre 2018).

Si prevede la produzione e diffusione dei seguenti materiali di comunicazione:

Materiale generale relativo a tutte le misure

- Affissioni di manifesti (stalli comunali 70x100 e 6mx3m) e locandine in città, soprattutto presso infopoint turistici del comune di Firenze.
- Mappe promozionali con indicazione della localizzazione di fontanelli, fontane pubbliche, contenitori per la raccolta differenziata, distribuite presso infopoint turistici del comune di Firenze.
- Realizzazione di promocard da distribuire presso infopoint turistici, strutture ricettive, volantinaggio durante iniziative di comunicazione, ecc;
- Vetrofanie per identificare i locali aderenti al progetto Urban Waste;
- WasteApp: applicazione sviluppata nell'ambito del progetto le istruzioni per una corretta raccolta differenziata. L'applicazione, rivolta prevalentemente ai turisti, esorta gli utenti a utilizzare i contenitori per la raccolta differenziata e le fontanelle di acqua di rete, e tramite un meccanismo di gioco li ricompensa con premi, come ingressi al museo scontati o il kit di benvenuto (contenente sacchetto, borraccia e mappa con i luoghi e servizi Urban Waste), se effettivamente li utilizzano.

Materiale specifico per bar e ristoranti: raccolta differenziata (se richiesto da alcuni aderenti)

- Contenitori di cartone forniti eventualmente da Comieco per la raccolta della carta.

Comunicazione sul web

Sito del Comune di Firenze : <http://www.firenzeturismo.it/it/>

Siti web di alcuni stakeholder (www.aliaspa.it, ...)

sito di progetto <http://www.urban-waste.eu/>

sito della comunità di pratica <http://www.urban-waste.eu/florence-cop/>

Risorse

E' importante stimare le risorse finanziarie e logistiche necessarie:

- il budget disponibile, secondo le diverse fonti finanziarie: budget di progetto, fondi pubblici, contributi

disponibili e necessarie	<p><i>privati, ecc.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>le altre risorse disponibili: lavoro volontario, spazi liberi, ecc.</i> - <i>ulteriori risorse finanziarie o logistiche che devono essere acquistate (fondi pubblici, sponsorizzazioni private, ecc.).</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget disponibile per realizzazione dei materiali di comunicazione generale di progetto: € 13.000 • Per lo sviluppo del piano di comunicazione il Comune mette a disposizione 10 stalli 70x100 nel centro storico (vetrine del centro storico) e 60 stalli murali 70x100 (per 3 cicli di affissioni). Inoltre saranno effettuate due affissioni negli stalli 6mx3m. In aggiunta saranno inseriti i materiali di progetti tra quelli proiettati a rotazione nei 42 display collocati in 24 luoghi diversi dell'area metropolitana. • Alia fornisce contenitori per la raccolta differenziata nelle aree attrezzate e prepara e stampa le brochure multilingua.
Tempistica	<p><i>Quando si definisce il cronoprogramma, considerare le seguenti scadenze:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>organizzazione di una iniziativa pubblica di lancio (può essere in parallelo con il quarto incontro della comunità di pratica), tra Febbraio e Aprile 2018;</i> - <i>fase di start-up (circa 2 mesi): progettazione finale dei materiali, organizzazione di attività formative e (se necessario) test delle azioni con un campione di strutture turistiche, Gennaio – Aprile 2018;</i> - <i>fase di completa attuazione della misura, coinvolgendo tutte le strutture turistiche e le diverse categorie di turisti individuate tra "i destinatari", con apposite campagne di comunicazione dedicate. Questa fase deve durare almeno 6 mesi, Aprile – Ottobre 2018.</i>
	<p>Il cronoprogramma dell'azione prevede:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coinvolgimento dei soggetti interessati entro Marzo/Aprile 2018 • Firma del protocollo di Intesa a Maggio 2018 • Sperimentazione dell'attuazione da Maggio 2018; • Attuazione a regime dell'azione da Giugno a Ottobre 2018.
Monitoraggio	<p><i>Tenendo conto degli obiettivi individuati è necessario sviluppare una procedura per il monitoraggio, con la raccolta di dati e informazioni dai diversi attori (gestore dei rifiuti e della rete idrica, fornitori dei servizi turistici, ecc.) coinvolti, con lo scopo di valutare il raggiungimento o meno di tali obiettivi. Il monitoraggio si riferisce al periodo di 6-8 mesi di attuazione a regime delle misure.</i></p> <p>Indicatori qualitativi <i>Questo tipo di informazioni sono generalmente raccolte attraverso semplici questionari/interviste che possono essere richiesti prima dell'implementazione della misura (se necessario) e alla fine della fase di attuazione a regime (per esempio: numero di azioni attuate, valutazione dei risultati raggiunti su una scala qualitativa, ecc.)</i></p> <p>Indicatori quantitativi <i>I dati relative alla quantità di rifiuti prodotti possono essere raccolti pesando i rifiuti e riempiendo una scheda di monitoraggio in tre diversi momenti: una settimana (da lunedì a domenica) PRIMA dell'inizio della fase di attuazione, un'altra settimana DURANTE la fase di attuazione e infine una settimana DOPO la fase di finale.</i> <i>Per quanto riguarda le misure che coinvolgono le strutture turistiche come hotel e ristoranti, è importante monitorare anche il numero di ospiti/clienti per poter calcolare i valori procapite.</i> <i>In alternativa, i dati relative alla quantità dei rifiuti prodotti possono essere stimati in base al numero di sacchi di rifiuti generati (nota la volumetria e la frazione merceologica).</i></p>
	<p>Per verificare l'attuazione di questa azione saranno acquisiti i seguenti dati, necessari per calcolare i relativi indicatori di monitoraggio:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numero di brochure multilingua distribuite; • Numero di appartamenti coinvolti; • Numero di punti informativi coinvolti. <p>Saranno poi sviluppati alcuni indicatori relativi alla campagna di comunicazione:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • n. mappe realizzate e distribuite • n. di promocard realizzate e distribuite • n. di partecipanti agli eventi

Piano Operativo per l'attuazione delle misure n. 1 – Doggy Bag e n.2 - Prevenzione dello spreco ai buffet e nei ristoranti

Attuazione delle misure dimostrative di prevenzione e gestione dei rifiuti

Misura n. 1-2	
I promotori: ruoli e responsabilità	<p><i>E' importante definire chiaramente quali siano le risorse umane di cui abbiamo bisogno per attuare le azioni, e quali siano i diversi ruoli e responsabilità.</i></p> <p><i>In particolare:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>la persona responsabile dell'attuazione delle azioni e del monitoraggio (manager);</i> - <i>la squadra che supporta il manager (se necessario);</i> - <i>i più importanti stakeholders che è necessario coinvolgere nell'attuazione delle misure per avere un supporto organizzativo e, se possibile, finanziario (per esempio associazioni di categoria, associazioni di beneficenza, attori pubblici o privati, come la società di gestione dei rifiuti o di gestione della rete idrica).</i>
<p>Si prevede il coinvolgimento dei seguenti soggetti, firmatari del protocollo d'intesa:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regione Toscana: coordina e realizza i materiali di comunicazione con fondi di progetto. • Comune di Firenze (assessorato all'Ambiente): fornisce permessi e spazi per le affissioni negli stalli comunali e per la distribuzione dei materiali presso gli infopoint turistici, inoltre dà supporto e spazi per la realizzazione delle azioni e delle iniziative di promozione del progetto. • Città Metropolitana: promuove l'iniziativa; • Confcommercio: contattano i propri aderenti e diffondono l'iniziativa; • Confesercenti: contattano i propri aderenti e diffondono l'iniziativa. <p>Azione coordinata direttamente dalla Regione Toscana in collaborazione con il Comune di Firenze</p>	
I destinatari	<p><i>Definire quali sono le diverse categorie di fornitori di servizi turistici che vogliamo raggiungere con l'attuazione dell'azione, e, se possibile, stimarne il bacino complessivo.</i></p> <p><i>Per esempio:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>hotel che servono colazioni: l'insieme può essere caratterizzato in base alla zona (a Firenze ci sono 200 hotel nel centro storico e 100 nella zona esterna) e/o in base alle stelle (a Firenze ci sono 5 hotel 5 stelle, 25 tre stelle, ecc.)</i> - <i>hotel con ristorante (che servono colazioni e pasti);</i> - <i>ristoranti;</i> - <i>bar;</i> - <i>.....</i> <p><i>Se è necessario il coinvolgimento di attori pubblici o privati, specificare chi si vuole coinvolgere.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>.....</i> - <i>.....</i> <p><i>Per alcune misure, è anche importante considerare a che tipo di turista la misura è rivolta, con lo scopo di sviluppare idonei materiali di comunicazione.</i></p> <p><i>Per esempio:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>estera/locale;</i> - <i>giovani, famiglie, anziani;</i> - <i>.....</i>
<p>La misura si rivolge a:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ristoranti del centro storico di di Firenze. • Turisti che alloggiano in alberghi con servizio buffet e/o ristorante; • Turisti e cittadini clienti di ristoranti. 	

Coinvolgimento degli attori	<i>Una volta definiti i beneficiari, specificare come si intende riuscire a coinvolgere operativamente i diversi attori identificati nella sezione precedente: per esempio, organizzazione di iniziative informative, attivazione di contatti personali, specifici accordi con associazioni di categoria, ecc.</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Le associazioni di categoria si occupano di contattare e coinvolgere ristoratori, in modo coordinato con il gruppo di lavoro sulla promozione dell'acqua di rete, per identificare e contattare quegli esercizi che, siano disponibili a realizzare anche azioni per la riduzione degli sprechi di cibo. • Effettuare un incontro formativo/informativo a Maggio 2018 con un primo gruppo di aspiranti aderenti. • Una volta partita l'iniziativa, organizzare un evento/incontro a Giugno/Luglio 2018 in cui mostrare i primi risultati raggiunti con l'obiettivo di coinvolgere un maggior numero di aderenti.
Obiettivi	<p><i>Definire e concordare con tutti gli stakeholders gli obiettivi che si vogliono raggiungere con la realizzazione dell'azione.</i></p> <p><i>Gli obiettivi possono essere collegati a:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - il processo di gestione (per esempio il numero di azioni di prevenzione dei rifiuti attuate da hotel/ristoranti, numero di iniziative del riuso organizzate, ecc.); - il bacino di destinatari che si punta a raggiungere (ovvero la percentuale del bacino definito nella sezione precedente, il 5% degli hotel del centro storico, ad esempio); - la quantificazione di articoli/attrezzature (per esempio numero di borracce/caraffe o doggy bag distribuite, numero di cestini per la raccolta differenziata installati lungo le strade, numero di compostiere distribuite); - la stima dei turisti (cittadini) raggiunti dalle iniziative di comunicazione; - la valutazione della riduzione della produzione dei rifiuti (kg di rifiuto organico, kg di plastica, kg di rifiuto indifferenziato, ecc...).
<p>L'attuazione di questa misura si propone di coinvolgere almeno 20 pubblici esercizi dislocati nel centro storico che svilupperanno inizialmente la misura.</p>	
Attuazione delle misure	<p><i>Descrivere quali sono i passi operativi per attuare le misure. Una lista approssimativa delle azioni (da adattare a seconda dei diversi tipi di azioni) può includere:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organizzazione di attività di formazione; - creazione di attività di assistenza (help-desk); - progettazione e personalizzazione dei materiali di comunicazione; - distribuzione dei materiali di comunicazione; - vendita/distribuzione delle attrezzature (se necessario); - gestione logistica; - organizzazione di audit preliminari.
<p>I pubblici esercizi aderenti si impegnano a realizzare le seguenti azioni:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promuovere il menu "Urban Waste": all'interno del listino menu devono prevedere la possibilità di ordinare un menu bambino e/o le mezze porzioni di tutti (o alcuni) i piatti presenti nel menu esteso, oppure mettere in evidenza quei piatti della tradizione che utilizzano pane raffermo, "scarti" della cucina, ecc. 2. Promozione dell'uso di doggy bag: il cliente deve essere informato, specificandolo anche nel menu, che può richiedere la propria doggy bag per portare a casa i propri avanzi da poter consumare successivamente. Ciascun pubblico esercizio potrà utilizzare il contenitore che preferisce per consegnare il proprio cibo non consumato al cliente, mentre con i fondi di progetto sarà prodotta una prima fornitura di sacchetti di carta con il logo di progetto in cui riporli. 	
<p>CAMPAGNA DI COMUNICAZIONE</p> <p>La campagna di Comunicazione prevede la realizzazione di:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Una conferenza stampa, per il lancio della fase sperimentale del Progetto, che sarà organizzata a Maggio 2018; • Organizzazione di eventi dedicati alla promozione del progetto, tra cui: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - un primo evento di lancio della campagna di comunicazione relativa a tutte e quattro le misure sviluppate a Firenze (Giugno-Luglio 2018); - eventuali eventi specifici dedicati alla promozione della misura; - un evento alla fine della campagna per promuovere i risultati raggiunti, valorizzare gli esercenti 	

coinvolti e rilanciare nuove iniziative (Settembre-Ottobre 2018).

Si prevede la produzione e diffusione dei seguenti materiali di comunicazione:

Materiale generale relativo a tutte le misure

- Affissioni di manifesti (stalli comunali 70x100 e 6mx3m) e locandine in città, soprattutto presso infopoint turistici del comune di Firenze.
- Mappe promozionali con indicazione della localizzazione di fontanelli, fontane pubbliche, contenitori per la raccolta differenziata, distribuite presso infopoint turistici del comune di Firenze.
- Realizzazione di promocard da distribuire presso infopoint turistici, strutture ricettive, volantinaggio durante iniziative di comunicazione, ecc;
- Vetrofanie per identificare i locali aderenti al progetto Urban Waste;
- WasteApp: applicazione sviluppata nell'ambito del progetto contenente istruzioni per una corretta raccolta differenziata. L'applicazione, rivolta prevalentemente ai turisti, esorta gli utenti a utilizzare i contenitori per la raccolta differenziata e le fontanelle di acqua di rete, e tramite un meccanismo di gioco li ricompensa con premi, come ingressi al museo scontati o il kit di benvenuto (contenente sacchetto, borraccia e mappa con i luoghi e servizi Urban Waste), se effettivamente li utilizzano.

Materiale specifico per ristoranti e buffet: cibo

- Layout per "menu del giorno" personalizzabile e stampabile direttamente dai ristoratori;
- Cartonato centrotavola con descrizione del progetto e delle principali azioni sviluppate;
- Sacchetti di carta per trasporto doggy bags.

Materiale specifico per bar e ristoranti: acqua

- Stickers per brocche "Florence Urban Water";
- Bottiglie con logo Publiacqua.

Materiale specifico per bar e ristoranti: raccolta differenziata (se richiesto da alcuni aderenti)

- Contenitori di cartone forniti eventualmente da Comieco per la raccolta della carta.

Comunicazione sul web

Sito del Comune di Firenze : <http://www.firenzeturismo.it/it/>

Siti web di alcuni stakeholder (www.aliaspa.it, ...)

sito di progetto <http://www.urban-waste.eu/>

sito della comunità di pratica <http://www.urban-waste.eu/florence-cop/>

Risorse disponibili e necessarie

E' importante stimare le risorse finanziarie e logistiche necessarie:

- *il budget disponibile, secondo le diverse fonti finanziarie: budget di progetto, fondi pubblici, contributi privati, ecc.*
- *le altre risorse disponibili: lavoro volontario, spazi liberi, ecc.*
- *ulteriori risorse finanziarie o logistiche che devono essere acquistate (fondi pubblici, sponsorizzazioni private, ecc.).*

- Budget disponibile per realizzazione dei materiali: € 13.000
- Per lo sviluppo del piano di comunicazione il Comune mette a disposizione 20 stalli 70x100 nel centro storico (vetrine del centro storico) e 60 stalli murali 70x100 (per 3 cicli di affissioni). Inoltre saranno effettuate due affissioni negli stalli 6mx3m. In aggiunta saranno inseriti i materiali di progetti tra quelli proiettati a rotazione nei 42 display collocati in 24 luoghi diversi dell'area metropolitana.

Tempistica

Quando si definisce il cronoprogramma, considerare le seguenti scadenze:

- *organizzazione di una iniziativa pubblica di lancio (può essere in parallelo con il quarto incontro della comunità di pratica), tra **Febbraio e Aprile 2018**;*
- *fase di start-up (circa 2 mesi): progettazione finale dei materiali, organizzazione di attività formative e (se necessario) test delle azioni con un campione di strutture turistiche, **Gennaio – Aprile 2018**;*
- *fase di completa attuazione della misura, coinvolgendo tutte le strutture turistiche e le diverse categorie di turisti individuate tra "i destinatari", con apposite campagne di comunicazione dedicate.*

Questa fase deve durare almeno 6 mesi, Aprile – Ottobre 2018.

Il cronoprogramma dell'azione prevede:

- Coinvolgimento dei pubblici esercizi per la realizzazione dell'azione entro Marzo/Aprile 2018
- Firma del protocollo di Intesa a Maggio 2018
- Sperimentazione dell'attuazione da Maggio 2018;
- Attuazione a regime dell'azione da Giugno a Ottobre 2018.

Monitoraggio

Tenendo conto degli obiettivi individuati è necessario sviluppare una procedura per il monitoraggio, con la raccolta di dati e informazioni dai diversi attori (gestore dei rifiuti e della rete idrica, fornitori dei servizi turistici, ecc.) coinvolti, con lo scopo di valutare il raggiungimento o meno di tali obiettivi. Il monitoraggio si riferisce al periodo di 6-8 mesi di attuazione a regime delle misure.

Indicatori qualitativi

Questo tipo di informazioni sono generalmente raccolte attraverso semplici questionari/interviste che possono essere richiesti prima dell'implementazione della misura (se necessario) e alla fine della fase di attuazione a regime (per esempio: numero di azioni attuate, valutazione dei risultati raggiunti su una scala qualitativa, ecc.)

Indicatori quantitativi

I dati relative alla quantità di rifiuti prodotti possono essere raccolti pesando i rifiuti e riempiendo una scheda di monitoraggio in tre diversi momenti: una settimana (da lunedì a domenica) PRIMA dell'inizio della fase di attuazione, un'altra settimana DURANTE la fase di attuazione e infine una settimana DOPO la fase di finale.

Per quanto riguarda le misure che coinvolgono le strutture turistiche come hotel e ristoranti, è importante monitorare anche il numero di ospiti/clienti per poter calcolare i valori procapite.

In alternativa, i dati relative alla quantità dei rifiuti prodotti possono essere stimati in base al numero di sacchi di rifiuti generati (nota la volumetria e la frazione merceologica).

Per verificare l'attuazione di questa azione saranno acquisiti i seguenti dati, necessari per calcolare i relativi indicatori di monitoraggio:

- n. di esercizi coinvolti
- n. di doggy bag distribuite
- n. di centrotavola realizzati e distribuiti

Saranno poi sviluppati alcuni indicatori relativi alla campagna di comunicazione:

- n. di promocard realizzate e distribuite
- n. di partecipanti agli eventi

Piano Operativo per l'attuazione della misura n. 22 - Donazione del cibo da parte di hotel e ristoranti ad associazioni benefiche

Attuazione delle misure dimostrative di prevenzione e gestione dei rifiuti

	Misura n. 22
I promotori: ruoli e responsabilità	<p><i>E' importante definire chiaramente quali siano le risorse umane di cui abbiamo bisogno per attuare le azioni, e quali siano i diversi ruoli e responsabilità.</i></p> <p><i>In particolare:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>la persona responsabile dell'attuazione delle azioni e del monitoraggio (manager);</i> - <i>la squadra che supporta il manager (se necessario);</i> - <i>i più importanti stakeholders che è necessario coinvolgere nell'attuazione delle misure per avere un supporto organizzativo e, se possibile, finanziario (per esempio associazioni di categoria, associazioni di beneficenza, attori pubblici o privati, come la società di gestione dei rifiuti o di gestione della rete idrica).</i>
<p>L'azione numero "22 - Donazione del cibo da parte di hotel e ristoranti ad associazioni benefiche prevede il coinvolgimento dei seguenti soggetti, firmatari del protocollo d'intesa "Partnership pubblico-privato per lo sviluppo e realizzazione delle misure previste dal progetto URBAN-WASTE":</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regione Toscana; • Agenzia Regionale Recupero Risorse ARRR; • Città Metropolitana di Firenze; • Associazione di volontariato solidarietà Caritas onlus • Associazione Banco Alimentare della Toscana onlus: • Federalberghi Firenze; • Confindustria Firenze; • Confesercenti Metropolitana di Firenze; • WTB Hotels - Garibaldi BLU <p>I criteri e le modalità di realizzazione dell'azione sono stati definiti con il supporto di:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambiente Italia s.r.l. <p>In particolare si definiscono i seguenti ruoli:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinatore: Marisa Valtancoli - ARRR - Supporto operativo: Associazione di volontariato solidarietà Caritas onlus e Associazione Banco Alimentare della Toscana onlus <p>Inoltre, i donatori (siano essi hotel o società di catering), per aderire al progetto, devono procedere con la nomina del responsabile che diventa il referente col quale tutti gli attori coinvolti nell'attuazione</p>	

dell'azione possono comunicare. Tale nominativo dovrà essere comunicato al coordinatore.
 Il donatori e i beneficiari, ciascuno per la propria parte hanno il compito di verificare che l'attuazione dell'azione sia realizzata secondo le modalità e indicazioni operative concordate e sottoscritte fra le parti nel **PROTOCOLLO DI INTESA PER IL RECUPERO DELLE ECCEденZE ALIMENTARI A SCOPO DI SOLIDARIETA' SOCIALE**

I destinatari

Definire quali sono le diverse categorie di fornitori di servizi turistici che vogliamo raggiungere con l'attuazione dell'azione, e, se possibile, stimarne il bacino complessivo.

Per esempio:

- *hotel che servono colazioni: l'insieme può essere caratterizzato in base alla zona (a Firenze ha 200 hotel nel centro storico e 100 nella zona esterna) e/o in base alle stelle (a Firenze ho 5 hotel 5 stelle, 25 tre stelle, ecc.)*
- *hotel con ristorante (che servono colazioni e pasti);*
- *ristoranti;*
- *bar;*
- *....*

*Se è necessario il coinvolgimento di **attori pubblici o privati**, specificare chi si vuole coinvolgere.*

- *.....*
- *.....*

*Per alcune misure, è anche importante considerare a **che tipo di turista** la misura è rivolta, con lo scopo di sviluppare idonei materiali di comunicazione.*

Per esempio:

- *estera/locale;*
- *giovani, famiglie,anziani;*
- *.....*

L'azione numero "22 - Donazione del cibo da parte di hotel e ristoranti ad associazioni benefiche" si rivolge a:

- Hotel o società di catering con sede nel comune di Firenze, denominati di seguito come "donatori"
- Enti assistenziali e/o associazioni del terzo settore che si occupano di solidarietà sociale (ONLUS, strutture caritative, Banco Alimentare, Caritas), denominati di seguito come donatori "beneficiari".

Dal confronto con i partecipanti si opta per effettuare inizialmente una selezione a monte degli Hotel in relazione alla localizzazione delle strutture ONLUS ai fini di realizzare una rete molto corta di donazione.

Coinvolgimento degli attori

Una volta definiti i beneficiari, specificare come si intende riuscire a coinvolgere operativamente i diversi attori identificati nella sezione precedente: per esempio, organizzazione di iniziative informative, attivazione di contatti personali, specifici accordi con associazioni di categoria, ecc.

Lo sviluppo del Piano operativo dell'azione si concentrerà sul recupero delle eccedenze delle colazioni e dei resti non porzionati dei catering presso le strutture alberghiere (4 / 5 stelle) da destinare a mense e strutture che operano a fini di solidarietà sociale, fermo restando lo scopo principale di ridurre al minimo i rifiuti alimentari.

Gli operatori delle cucine e i volontari saranno informati/formati sulle modalità di gestione e di conservazione del cibo secondo quanto previsto dalla legge 166/2016 relativa allo spreco alimentare: per fare ciò, sia i beneficiari, sia i donatori aderenti all'azione si impegnano a organizzare insieme al coordinatore della misura appositi incontri formativi rivolti ai soggetti operativamente coinvolti.

La diffusione di questa azione deve coinvolgere anche i cittadini e i turisti di Firenze, mediante apposite campagne informative, in particolare, nell'ambito del progetto Urban Waste è prevista la realizzazione di una campagna per sensibilizzare sul tema dello spreco alimentare, comune anche alle azioni 1 Doggy Bag e 2 - Prevenzione dello spreco di cibo al buffet e nei ristoranti.

Obiettivi	<p><i>Definire e concordare con tutti gli stakeholders gli obiettivi che si vogliono raggiungere con la realizzazione dell'azione.</i></p> <p><i>Gli obiettivi possono essere collegati a:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>il processo di gestione (per esempio il numero di azioni di prevenzione dei rifiuti attuate da hotel/ristoranti, numero di iniziative del riuso organizzate, ecc.);</i> - <i>il bacino di destinatari che si punta a raggiungere (ovvero la percentuale del bacino definito nella sezione precedente, il 5% degli hotel del centro storico, ad esempio);</i> - <i>la quantificazione di articoli/attrezzature (per esempio numero di borracce/caraffe o doggy bag distribuite, numero di cestini per la raccolta differenziata installati lungo le strade, numero di compostiere distribuite);</i> - <i>la stima dei turisti (cittadini) raggiunti dalle iniziative di comunicazione;</i> - <i>la valutazione della riduzione della produzione dei rifiuti (kg di rifiuto organico, kg di plastica, kg di rifiuto indifferenziato, ecc...).</i>
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L'azione numero "22 - Donazione del cibo da parte di hotel e ristoranti ad associazioni benefiche" si pone come obiettivo principale la creazione di una rete "solidale" in grado di mettere in contatto donatori e beneficiari, nel modo più diretto possibile, evitando l'utilizzo di depositi intermedi. Ovvero, lo scopo principale è di creare una filiera corta, nella quale il cibo donato viene raccolto dalle associazioni sul territorio che lo smistano direttamente ai beneficiari finali.

Obiettivi quantificabili

Soggetti da coinvolgere:

5 Hotel di categoria 4/5 stelle

1 società di catering

2 Enti assistenziali e/o associazioni del terzo settore che si occupano di solidarietà sociale

Quantità cibo recuperato:

Per quanto riguarda gli obiettivi relativi alla quantità, non esistono ad oggi dati di letteratura sulle eccedenze delle colazioni e catering. La realizzazione del progetto consentirà di avere una prima base dati. Il monitoraggio viene effettuato per ciascun soggetto donatore che vorrà aderire.

Attuazione delle misure	<p><i>Descrivere quali sono i passi operativi per attuare le misure. Una lista approssimativa delle azioni (da adattare a seconda dei diversi tipi di azioni) può includere:</i></p>
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- *organizzazione di attività di formazione;*
- *creazione di attività di assistenza (help-desk);*
- *progettazione e personalizzazione dei materiali di comunicazione;*
- *distribuzione dei materiali di comunicazione;*
- *vendita/distribuzione delle attrezzature (se necessario);*
- *gestione logistica;*
- *organizzazione di audit preliminari.*

L'adesione all'azione da parte dei potenziali destinatari avviene attraverso la sottoscrizione di uno specifico protocollo di intesa, attraverso il quale:

- I promotori dell'azione si impegnano a garantire la gestione dell'azione e a fornire supporto agli aderenti, secondo le modalità specificate nel successivo paragrafo "benefici per chi aderisce";
- I partecipanti (beneficiari e donatori) si impegnano a realizzare azioni di recupero e distribuzione di alimenti recuperati da hotel (avanzi non porzionati delle colazioni) e da catering (avanzi non porzionati dei pasti), secondo le modalità specificate nel successivo paragrafo "obblighi per chi aderisce".

OBBLIGHI PER CHI ADERISCE

NOMINA DEL RESPONSABILE

Per poter aderire al progetto innanzi tutto, i destinatari (siano essi hotel e associazioni) individuano il responsabile che diventa il referente col quale tutti gli attori coinvolti nell'attuazione dell'azione possono comunicare.

Il responsabile si assume inoltre il compito di verificare l'attuazione dell'azione secondo le linee guida concordate e di provvedere alla compilazione delle schede di monitoraggio ex ante e dei risultati, secondo le modalità e le frequenze definite nel relativo paragrafo.

ANALISI PRELIMINARE

L'analisi preliminare è necessaria per poter determinare e definire l'incontro tra domanda e offerta, ovvero:

- i donatori (hotel) con il monitoraggio individueranno le tipologie di cibo da donare, e in quali quantità, compilando il relativo questionario descritto nella sezione "monitoraggio" (il questionario può essere compilabile anche online in un google form);
- i beneficiari (enti e associazioni benefiche) dovranno dichiarare la frequenza della disponibilità per il ritiro e i mezzi a disposizione, compilando il relativo questionario descritto nella sezione "monitoraggio" (il questionario può essere compilabile anche online in un google form).

MODALITA' OPERATIVE

L'azione "22 - Donazione del cibo da parte di hotel e ristoranti ad associazioni benefiche" prevede la donazione di alimenti:

- provenienti dalle colazione degli hotel, comprendendo sia gli alimenti come pane e derivati delle farine - pane, dolci, torte – sia gli alimenti cotti come uova, salumi, ecc.
- provenienti da buffet e catering: si ritirano i vassoi non porzionati.

Tali alimenti devono essere ritirati dalle associazioni benefiche e consegnati agli utenti finali entro poche ore, secondo modalità che ne garantiscono la qualità dal punto di vista igienico-sanitario.

Per questo motivo è ovvio che le maggiori difficoltà siano di tipo logistico, pertanto:

1. l'analisi preliminare consente di conoscere quali siano i potenziali donatori, le quantità medie di cibo che possono donare e le frequenze delle potenziali donazioni;
2. l'analisi preliminare consente inoltre di conoscere quali siano le associazioni attive sul territorio, quale dotazione di mezzi e volontari abbiano e con quale frequenza siano disponibili a ritirare e distribuire.
3. Le informazioni ottenute al punto 1 e 2 devono essere inviate al coordinatore che definirà la relazione tra donatori e beneficiari, ovvero quale associazione dovrà ritirare eccedenze alimentari prodotte da

un determinato donatore, con quale tipologia di mezzo e con quale frequenza.

BENEFICI PER CHI ADERISCE

ASSISTENZA TECNICA

I promotori dell'azione offrono supporto ai soggetti aderenti nelle seguenti forme:

- ciclo di incontri informativi e formativi, rivolti alle diverse tipologie di destinatari, finalizzati anche a mettere a punto le corrette prassi operative previste per l'adesione all'attività;
- supporto nella fase di start-up per l'applicazione delle procedure previste dal presente Piano d'Azione;

MATERIALI INFORMATIVI E DI SUPPORTO

Tutti i destinatari dell'azione riceveranno la vetrofaneria con il logo dell'azione relativa alla minimizzazione dello spreco alimentare prevista nel progetto Urban Waste, da esporre presso l'hotel aderente, nonché presso la sede e sui mezzi usati dalle associazioni benefiche per il ritiro delle eccedenze alimentari.

Tutti gli hotel riceveranno una "cavaliera" da esporre al buffet dove viene specificato "Partecipiamo al progetto Urban Waste donando il cibo non consumato presso questo buffet ad associazioni della città di Firenze che operano ai fini di solidarietà sociale"

CAMPAGNA DI COMUNICAZIONE

I soggetti aderenti fruiscono inoltre di una campagna di comunicazione sia di livello locale sia di livello nazionale ed europeo.

Sono strumenti generali di comunicazione del progetto:

- Sito internet <http://www.urban-waste.eu/> florence-cop
- campagna di affissione con manifesti 70x100 e 6x3 metri

SCONTO DELLA TARI

Sarà aperto un confronto con il Comune di Firenze per valutare la possibilità di uno sconto sulla parte variabile della tassa sui rifiuti per gli aderenti (hotels).

RECUPERO DELL'IVA

Le attività che aderiscono e attuano nella loro completezza l'azione hanno diritto al recupero dell'IVA pagata per l'acquisto del cibo donato.

Risorse disponibili e necessarie

E' importante stimare le risorse finanziarie e logistiche necessarie:

- *il budget disponibile, secondo le diverse fonti finanziarie: budget di progetto, fondi pubblici, contributi privati, ecc.*
- *le altre risorse disponibili: lavoro volontario, spazi liberi, ecc.*
- *ulteriori risorse finanziarie o logistiche che devono essere acquistate (fondi pubblici, sponsorizzazioni private, ecc.).*

Per l'attuazione dell'azione numero "22 - Donazione del cibo da parte di hotel e ristoranti ad associazioni benefiche" è necessario trovare risorse:

- umane: è prioritario coinvolgere i volontari delle associazioni benefiche, ma anche trovare il supporto nelle istituzioni, come Comune di Firenze e Regione Toscana, e le associazioni di categoria.

Inoltre il progetto Urban Waste provvederà alla realizzazione dei materiali per promuovere una apposita campagna di comunicazione sullo spreco alimentare e la sua riduzione sul territorio comunale.

Tempistica

Quando si definisce il cronoprogramma, considerare le seguenti

	<p>scadenze:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organizzazione di una iniziativa pubblica di lancio (può essere in parallelo con il quarto incontro della comunità di pratica), tra Febbraio e Aprile 2018; - fase di start-up (circa 2 mesi): progettazione finale dei materiali, organizzazione di attività formative e (se necessario) test delle azioni con un campione di strutture turistiche, Gennaio – Aprile 2018; - fase di completa attuazione della misura, coinvolgendo tutte le strutture turistiche e le diverse categorie di turisti individuate tra “i destinatari”, con apposite campagne di comunicazione dedicate. Questa fase deve durare almeno 6 mesi, Aprile – Ottobre 2018.
<p>Il cronoprogramma dell’azione prevede:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analisi preliminare a partire da febbraio 2018; • sottoscrizione P.I. a partire da marzo 2018; • Sperimentazione dell’attuazione dell’azione a partire da marzo 2018; • Attuazione a regime dell’azione da maggio a 30 novembre 2018. 	
<p>monitoraggio</p>	<p>Tenendo conto degli obiettivi individuati è necessario sviluppare una procedura per il monitoraggio, con la raccolta di dati e informazioni dai diversi attori (gestore dei rifiuti e della rete idrica, fornitori dei servizi turistici, ecc.) coinvolti, con lo scopo di valutare il raggiungimento o meno di tali obiettivi.</p> <p>Il monitoraggio si riferisce al periodo di 6-8 mesi di attuazione a regime delle misure.</p> <p>Indicatori qualitativi</p> <p>Questo tipo di informazioni sono generalmente raccolte attraverso semplici questionari/interviste che possono essere richiesti prima dell’implementazione della misura (se necessario) e alla fine della fase di attuazione a regime (per esempio: numero di azioni attuate, valutazione dei risultati raggiunti su una scala qualitativa, ecc.)</p> <p>Indicatori quantitativi</p> <p>I dati relative alla quantità di rifiuti prodotti possono essere raccolti pesando i rifiuti e riempiendo una scheda di monitoraggio in tre diversi momenti: una settimana (da lunedì a domenica) PRIMA dell’inizio della fase di attuazione, un’altra settimana DURANTE la fase di attuazione e infine una settimana DOPO la fase di finale.</p> <p>Per quanto riguarda le misure che coinvolgono le strutture turistiche come hotel e ristoranti, è importante monitorare anche il numero di ospiti/clienti per poter calcolare i valori procapite.</p> <p>In alternativa, i dati relative alla quantità dei rifiuti prodotti possono essere stimati in base al numero di sacchi di rifiuti generati (nota la volumetria e la frazione merceologica).</p>

Il monitoraggio dell'azione numero "22 - Donazione del cibo da parte di hotel e ristoranti ad associazioni benefiche" è di fondamentale importanza in quanto in via preliminare serve per capire le quantità di cibo che sono potenzialmente donabili, ed in via consuntiva per determinare e giustificare eventuali sconti nella tassazione rifiuti spettanti ai donatori.

Per questo motivo è necessario che sia donatori, sia beneficiari compilino il questionario di analisi preliminare, e di monitoraggio

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

COPENHAGEN

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

City of Copenhagen and the hotel 66 Guldsmiden hereby agree on a voluntary partnership about using the Food tracking device in order to minimize the food waste.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Why partnership?

Waste management from tourism is increasingly important as Europe's cities are some of the world's greatest tourism destinations. The City of Copenhagen has the past 7 years seen an increase in tourism, which now has passed 10 mio. overnights stay per year. This corresponds to waste production from 27,000 inhabitants.

How can we get a cleaner city? Every day, waste is generated from the activities in the city. Especially in summertime, where the whole city is filled with life and activities from Copenhageners, local tourists and tourists from abroad. The City of Copenhagen participates with 10 other European cities and regions in an URBAN-WASTE project www.urban-waste.eu in order to focus on waste from tourism. How can we prevent waste or treat it better?

The City of Copenhagen has great focus on sustainable living including waste minimizing, reuse and recycling. It is essential to make the transformation from waste disposal to exploitation of resources. Materials must no longer be discarded and wasted; they must circulate in the cycle for as long as possible. The city cannot assume this task by itself. We need your contribution and inspiration to create a more sustainable city.

By signing the Diploma for this voluntary Public-Private Partnership you declare your voluntary contribution as described on the Diploma and specified in the Operative Plan.

URBAN-WASTE background

URBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative environmental impacts and tourist cities have to face a number of challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

The main actions in the URBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop new good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and to support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities.
2. To organize the local stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies.

Project partners in URBAN-WASTE

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure no. 20: Food tracking device
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Contact information of the relevant kitchen staff</i> - <i>Samuel.Lindgren@slu.se is the contact person from Sveriges Lantbruksuniversite, who is providing a food tracking device for interested kitchens at hotels and restaurants which has an interest of reducing their food waste.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will ensure the installation and system support of the food tracking device which includes a weight and a touchpad with software connected to the weight to track the food waste.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will tailor the system to fit the conditions and needs for your kitchen.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will report the results to your kitchen and your data will be anonymised if requested.</i> - <i>Birte Busch Thomsen bibusc@tmf.kk.dk from Copenhagen Municipality will present the opportunities of the food tracking device for your kitchen and establish the contacts between your kitchen and Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet.</i>
Target audience	<p><i>The City of Copenhagen is targeting 26 restaurants located in Nyhavn. Nyhavn is the most famous tourist dining area in Copenhagen and a place where Copenhageners and visitors are enjoying the relaxed atmosphere by the canal. All kind of national and foreign tourists are coming here either to eat or just to have a drink.</i></p> <p><i>https://www.nyhavn.com/restaurants</i></p> <p><i>The City of Copenhagen has also contacted Copenhagen Hospitality College who is educating future staff for hotels and restaurants. The school has room for approximately 2,000 pupils, students and course participants. Among other things they have focus on organic food and food waste. Using the food tracking device in will give the students the opportunity to work with food waste in theory and practice.</i></p> <p><i>Finely the City of Copenhagen has contacted 8 different Hotels who either previously has been contacted in the Urban Waste project because of their interest in organic food, food waste reduction etc., green key hotels and hotels in the GoGeeen network with focus on waste and energy reduction etc.</i></p> <p><i>(The food tracking device has been generally introduced at the Network for Foodservice organized by Groconsults on 15th March 2018 for 31 participants from different kitchens, hotels and restaurants.</i></p>

	<i>In May 2018 the City of Copenhagen contacted the 26 restaurants in Nyhavn, the 8 hotels and the Copenhagen Hospitality College personally, by phones and emails to hear if they were interested in using the food tracking device).</i>
Involvement of the actors	<i>Dialog with either the kitchen manager or the restaurant owner by paying them a visit and present the opportunities they get by using the food tracking device.</i>
Target setting	<p><i>By using the food tracking device your restaurant will be able to get an insight of the amount of surplus food from each day or served meal if chosen divided over different weekdays.</i></p> <p><i>When your restaurants starts using the food tracking device you will be able to map where and how much you can save in the purchase of raw materials and cost savings.</i></p> <p><i>The food tracking device will be tailored to fit the conditions and needs for your kitchen.</i></p>
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Your restaurant is contacted by personal visits from The City of Copenhagen in order to inform you about the opportunities of using the food tracking device</i> - <i>If your restaurant is interested the City of Copenhagen will send your contact information to Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet, who will install the system in your kitchen and they will also educate your staff.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will send reports to your kitchen so you can get feedback on your own food waste to be able to reduce it.</i>
Resources available and needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>The food tracking device consisting a weight and a touchpad can be installed from spring 2018 and the equipment is free of charge until May 1st 2019.</i> - <i>After May 1st 2019 your kitchen can choose if you want to continue to use the system for a price of 25 €/month.</i> - <i>The installation and service of the food tracking device, training of staff and reports of food waste is also free of charge.</i>
Timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>The food tracking device consisting a weight and a touchpad can be installed from spring 2018 and the equipment is free of charge until May 1st 2019.</i> - <i>The minimization of food waste will be an ongoing process during that period.</i>
Monitoring	<p><i>The food waste tracking device will collect data continually.</i></p> <p><i>The results will be published in reports and scientific journals and your kitchen can choose to be anonymized if requested.</i></p> <p><i>If possible, it will be good if your restaurant can monitor the number of guests/customers in order to calculate a per capita value for your restaurant.</i></p>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

City of Copenhagen and the hotel Axel Guldsmeden hereby agree on a voluntary partnership about using the Food tracking device in order to minimize the food waste.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Why partnership?

Waste management from tourism is increasingly important as Europe's cities are some of the world's greatest tourism destinations. The City of Copenhagen has the past 7 years seen an increase in tourism, which now has passed 10 mio. overnights stay per year. This corresponds to waste production from 27,000 inhabitants.

How can we get a cleaner city? Every day, waste is generated from the activities in the city. Especially in summertime, where the whole city is filled with life and activities from Copenhagengers, local tourists and tourists from abroad. The City of Copenhagen participates with 10 other European cities and regions in an URBAN-WASTE project www.urban-waste.eu in order to focus on waste from tourism. How can we prevent waste or treat it better?

The City of Copenhagen has great focus on sustainable living including waste minimizing, reuse and recycling. It is essential to make the transformation from waste disposal to exploitation of resources. Materials must no longer be discarded and wasted; they must circulate in the cycle for as long as possible. The city cannot assume this task by itself. We need your contribution and inspiration to create a more sustainable city.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure no. 20: Food tracking device
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Contact information of the relevant kitchen staff</i> - <i>Samuel.Lindgren@slu.se is the contact person from Sveriges Lantbruksuniversite, who is providing a food tracking device for interested kitchens at hotels and restaurants which has an interest of reducing their food waste.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will ensure the installation and system support of the food tracking device which includes a weight and a touchpad with software connected to the weight to track the food waste.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will tailor the system to fit the conditions and needs for your kitchen.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will report the results to your kitchen and your data will be anonymised if requested.</i> - <i>Birte Busch Thomsen bibusc@tmf.kk.dk from Copenhagen Municipality will present the opportunities of the food tracking device for your kitchen and establish the contacts between your kitchen and Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet.</i>
Target audience	<p><i>The City of Copenhagen is targeting 26 restaurants located in Nyhavn. Nyhavn is the most famous tourist dining area in Copenhagen and a place where Copenhageners and visitors are enjoying the relaxed atmosphere by the canal. All kind of national and foreign tourists are coming here either to eat or just to have a drink.</i></p> <p><i>https://www.nyhavn.com/restaurants</i></p> <p><i>The City of Copenhagen has also contacted Copenhagen Hospitality College who is educating future staff for hotels and restaurants. The school has room for approximately 2,000 pupils, students and course participants. Among other things they have focus on organic food and food waste. Using the food tracking device in will give the students the opportunity to work with food waste in theory and practice.</i></p> <p><i>Finely the City of Copenhagen has contacted 8 different Hotels who either previously has been contacted in the Urban Waste project because of their interest in organic food, food waste reduction etc., green key hotels and hotels in the GoGreen network with focus on waste and energy reduction etc.</i></p> <p><i>(The food tracking device has been generally introduced at the Network for Foodservice organized by Groconsults on 15th March 2018 for 31 participants from different kitchens, hotels and restaurants.</i></p>

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Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

City of Copenhagen and the hotel Babette Guldsmeden hereby agree on a voluntary partnership about using the Food tracking device in order to minimize the food waste.

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Develop it.

Why partnership?

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Project partners in URBAN-WASTE

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Measure no. 20: Food tracking device	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Contact information of the relevant kitchen staff</i> - <i>Samuel.Lindgren@slu.se is the contact person from Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet, who is providing a food tracking device for interested kitchens at hotels and restaurants which has an interest of reducing their food waste.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will ensure the installation and system support of the food tracking device which includes a weight and a touchpad with software connected to the weight to track the food waste.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will tailor the system to fit the conditions and needs for your kitchen.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will report the results to your kitchen and your data will be anonymised if requested.</i> - <i>Birte Busch Thomsen bibusc@tmf.kk.dk from Copenhagen Municipality will present the opportunities of the food tracking device for your kitchen and establish the contacts between your kitchen and Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet.</i>
Target audience	<p><i>The City of Copenhagen is targeting 26 restaurants located in Nyhavn. Nyhavn is the most famous tourist dining area in Copenhagen and a place where Copenhageners and visitors are enjoying the relaxed atmosphere by the canal. All kind of national and foreign tourists are coming here either to eat or just to have a drink.</i></p> <p><i>https://www.nyhavn.com/restaurants</i></p> <p><i>The City of Copenhagen has also contacted Copenhagen Hospitality College who is educating future staff for hotels and restaurants. The school has room for approximately 2,000 pupils, students and course participants. Among other things they have focus on organic food and food waste. Using the food tracking device in will give the students the opportunity to work with food waste in theory and practice.</i></p> <p><i>Finely the City of Copenhagen has contacted 8 different Hotels who either previously has been contacted in the Urban Waste project because of their interest in organic food, food waste reduction etc., green key hotels and hotels in the GoGreen network with focus on waste and energy reduction etc.</i></p> <p><i>(The food tracking device has been generally introduced at the Network for Foodservice organized by Groconsults on 15th March 2018 for 31 participants from different kitchens, hotels and restaurants.</i></p>

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Target setting	<i>By using the food tracking device your restaurant will be able to get an insight of the amount of surplus food from each day or served meal if chosen divided over different weekdays.</i> <i>When your restaurants starts using the food tracking device you will be able to map where and how much you can save in the purchase of raw materials and cost savings.</i> <i>The food tracking device will be tailored to fit the conditions and needs for your kitchen.</i>
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Your restaurant is contacted by personal visits from The City of Copenhagen in order to inform you about the opportunities of using the food tracking device</i> - <i>If your restaurant is interested the City of Copenhagen will send your contact information to Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet, who will install the system in your kitchen and they will also educate your staff.</i> - <i>Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet will send reports to your kitchen so you can get feedback on your own food waste to be able to reduce it.</i>
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Monitoring	<i>The food waste tracking device will collect data continually.</i> <i>The results will be published in reports and scientific journals and your kitchen can choose to be anonymized if requested.</i> <i>If possible, it will be good if your restaurant can monitor the number of guests/customers in order to calculate a per capita value for your restaurant.</i>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

City of Copenhagen and Hostel Steel House Copenhagen hereby agree on a voluntary partnership about using the Food tracking device in order to minimize the food waste.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Why partnership?

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How can we get a cleaner city? Every day, waste is generated from the activities in the city. Especially in summertime, where the whole city is filled with life and activities from Copenhageners, local tourists and tourists from abroad. The City of Copenhagen participates with 10 other European cities and regions in an URBAN-WASTE project www.urban-waste.eu in order to focus on waste from tourism. How can we prevent waste or treat it better?

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Reduce your food waste

YOU GET

- A scale to quantify food waste
- A touchpad with software connected to the scale to track the food waste
- Introduction on how to use the system
- Feedback on your own food waste to be able to reduce it.
- Cost savings when you act on preventing food waste.
- The opportunity to contribute to sustainability

THE PROJECT GETS

- Access to your recorded data (data will be anonymised if requested)
- The possibility to study food waste reduction from your data.
- Possibility to share and discuss results on waste reduction.

Details

Your kitchen will get

- The possibility to track food waste to be able to assess the produced quantity by category and reduce it
- A system that will be tailored to fit the conditions and needs for your kitchen
- Cost savings related to the amount of food waste avoided
- Installation and system support
- Delivery of the system is expected during spring 2018

What is required to participate ?

- Engagement to reduce food waste
- A place with power-access for the scale and touchpad
- A bin (maximum 60 liters) to put on the scale
- Daily measurements of food waste throughout 2018. This applies for every meal or at least, the 'plate waste' and 'buffet waste' categories, including info about the number of served meals
- The will to participate in a research project where quantified results will be published in scientific journals (anonymized if requested)

Costs and terms of use

The equipment is provided for free until May 1st 2019 via the EU-project Urban Waste through The Swedish University of Agricultural Science (SLU), who is participating in the project and will provide equipment, installation and support. This is done free of charge, but if something breaks due to uncareful handling or theft, the project will not replace it. If there is a manufacturing error it can be replaced.

After May 1st 2019 a contract for the license and support can be agreed with the company Matomatic AB. The company will provide the service and system for the price of 25 EUR/month. If no contract is written, the equipment must be returned to SLU.

Urban Waste

11 cities, 16 research institutions and other partners participate in an EU funded project focusing on minimising waste from tourism. The food waste tracking tool is developed in this project and the goal is that 40 kitchens will use the tool to reduce their amount of food waste. For more information about the project, please go the website: <http://www.urban-waste.eu/>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

City of Copenhagen and Haven Festival hereby agree on a voluntary partnership about initiatives to minimize/improve sorting of waste from events.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Why partnership?

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The main actions in the URBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop new good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and to support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities.
2. To organize the local stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies.

Project partners in URBAN-WASTE

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

Measure no. 18: Eco-event guidelines	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Jacob Baungaard, Environment Manager at Down the Drain Production which organizes concerts and festivals such as Haven.</i> - <i>Sofie Randel, Event Consultant, will be responsible for organizing the waste recycling activities at Haven.</i> - <i>Business waste supervisors from Copenhagen Municipality, who inspires and guides event organizers to sort and minimize the amount of waste from events Katherine.Mary.Poneta@tmf.kk.dk</i> - <i>Birte.Busch.Thomsen@tmf.kk.dk and Katherine.Mary.Poneta@tmf.kk.dk from Copenhagen Municipality will in dialog with Haven Festival monitor the effect of waste prevention initiatives.</i>
Target audience	<p><i>Haven Festival is a music festival for all senses combining experiments within art, music, food and beer. It is a two days festival taking place in Copenhagen on the 10th and 11th August 2018.</i></p> <p><i>Haven Festival is primarily aiming at adults (Copenhagengers, and tourist from Denmark and abroad). They serve drinks and food at the festivals.</i></p> <p><i>The City of Copenhagen is targeting the event organizer, staff and volunteers</i></p>
Involvement of the actors	<p><i>Contact and dialog with the event organizer before the event to discuss options for waste minimization and take back-system on different materials.</i></p> <p><i>The City waste supervisors from Copenhagen Municipality will have an introductory dialog meeting with Haven where the partners agreed on the recycling initiatives and supervisors will also visit the event in August and guide the staff/volunteers on waste handling and verify that it is done correctly.</i></p> <p><i>Johannes Sørensen & Sønner who rents and transport waste containers and the waste collecting company M. Larsen</i></p>

<p>Target setting</p>	<p><i>The event organisers and the city supervisors will guide personal and volunteers about sorting and recycling in prioritized areas such as back stage of soft plastic, metal, wood, glass, cooking oil, food and cardboard. They will also inform about the Danish recycling system for drinking bottles and tins to improve the amount of recycling. (Danish water bottles have a deposit system to ensure long life for bottles) and inform about the recycling system in general at the Haven festival.</i></p> <p><i>Personal at the stalls will be responsible for signing/telling about waste handling in smaller surrounding areas to minimize the numbers of volunteers.</i></p> <p><i>A deposit on drinking cups, cup carriers, cigarette package, wine bottles, pitcher, Haven rain poncho etc. to ensure correct waste sorting. Festival guests their money back when they handle over a certain amount of deposit waste.</i></p> <p><i>Testing recyclable cups and jugs that can be washed and reused.</i></p> <p><i>Make the waste collecting containers very visible with waste sorting signs, different colours for different fraction and light on the containers to make them visible in the evening. The light is produced by solar cells on the containers.</i></p> <p><i>Dialog about using recyclable plates which can be eaten or plastic plates which can be reproduced as plates or degradable plates.</i></p> <p><i>Dialog about getting access to drinking water from fire hydrants or tub of water</i></p> <p><i>Dialog about having pocket ash trays to minimize cigarette butts.</i></p> <p><i>Having Trash talkers at the event to guide the festival guests in waste sorting.</i></p> <p><i>During and after the event the city supervisors will evaluate the recycling work done by the staff.</i></p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>The City of Copenhagen will set up 2-3 initial meetings with the event organizer to discuss options for waste recycling</i> - <i>The event organizers must get a permission to host an event in Copenhagen</i> - <i>The event organizer will communicate and train the staff and volunteers about waste sorting and dialog with people attending the event.</i> - <i>The event organizers will be in contact with waste collecting companies to ensure enough waste containers for efficient waste sorting</i> - <i>The City of Copenhagen will be in dialog with catering companies before the event to improve waste sorting backstage to get better materials for recycling.</i> - <i>The City of Copenhagen will visit the event to guide and answer questions from the staff and volunteers</i> - <i>The City of Copenhagen will help designing the sorting signs for each recyclable material</i> - <i>The City of Copenhagen/the city supervisors will have 2-4 internal meetings to exchange experiences of the initiatives to improve the initiatives next year and in order to improve the dialog with other event organizers in the future.</i>

<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p><i>Time for meetings and training of staff and volunteers and collecting data and feedback on experiences</i></p>
<p>Timing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>The City of Copenhagen had gathered different event organizers at the 4th CoP on 17th April 2018 to help large events in the city to become more clean and sustainable by letting the organizers share experiences of best practice from previous events.</i> - <i>Haven Festival gets a permission from Copenhagen Municipality, the Environmental Protection Department allowing them to host the event when they fulfil the Danish and EU legislation on e.g. commercial waste (waste back stage)</i> - <i>Host the initial meeting with the event organizer on the 31st of May 2018 about rules and demands for waste sorting and recycling and guiding on good practice.</i> - <i>Organize training of staff and volunteers before the event</i> - <i>Planning and implementing the waste collection at the sight</i> - <i>The Haven Festival takes place in Copenhagen on the 10th and 11th August 2018</i> - <i>The event organizer arranges pickup of the different waste fraction</i> - <i>The event organizer and the City of Copenhagen follow up on the experiences of sorting and minimizing waste.</i>
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p><i>Where it is possible we will collect data on sorted waste based on the information given on the invoice from the waste collection companies.</i></p> <p><i>We will estimate the waste amount and the number of participants based on sold tickets, sold drinks and foods at different stores.</i></p> <p><i>The event organizer and the City of Copenhagen follow up on the experiences of sorting and minimizing waste at the event.</i></p>

Relevant monitoring parameters

Monitoring of actions, items, stakeholders and people involved etc.	
Guidelines distributed	number
People attending the event	number
Measures implemented:	number
measures enhancing separated collection of paper	number
measures enhancing separated collection of glass	number
measures enhancing separated collection of plastic	number
measures enhancing separated collection of organic waste	number
measures enhancing tap water and drinks with dispenser	number
measures enhancing reusable glass bottle	number
measures enhancing minimization of single dose food	number
measures enhancing food donation to charities	number
other: specify.....	number
Waste production monitoring	
plastic waste collected (weighted)	kg
paper waste collected (weighted)	kg
organic waste collected (weighted)	kg
glass waste collected (weighted)	kg
unsorted waste collected (weighted)	kg
Second option in case it is not possible to weight waste produced:	
bin (collecting plastic waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting paper waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting organic waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting glass waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting unsorted waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting plastic waste) capacity	litre
bin (collecting paper waste) capacity	litre
bin (collecting glass waste) capacity	litre
bin (collecting unsorted waste) capacity	litre
Gender considerations	
Who takes ultimate responsibility for event?	male-female
Who organises and conducts the rubbish collection?	% female
Approximately how many people take part in the event?	% female

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

City of Copenhagen and Copenhagen Malmø Port hereby agree in partnership on communication about waste management from cruise ships.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Why partnership?

Waste management from tourism is increasingly important as Europe's cities are some of the world's greatest tourism destinations. The City of Copenhagen has the past 7 years seen an increase in tourism, which now has passed 10 mio. overnights stay per year. This corresponds to waste production from 27,000 inhabitants.

How can we get a cleaner city? Every day, waste is generated from the activities in the city. Especially in summertime, where the whole city is filled with life and activities from Copenhageners, local tourists and tourists from abroad. The City of Copenhagen participates with 10 other European cities and regions in an URBAN-WASTE project www.urban-waste.eu in order to focus on waste from tourism. How can we prevent waste or treat it better?

The City of Copenhagen has great focus on sustainable living including waste minimizing, reuse and recycling. It is essential to make the transformation from waste disposal to exploitation of resources. Materials must no longer be discarded and wasted; they must circulate in the

cycle for as long as possible. The city cannot assume this task by itself. We need your contribution and inspiration to create a more sustainable city.

By signing the partnership agreement, you declare your voluntary contribution to minimise and increase the recycling of waste.

URBAN-WASTE background

URBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative environmental impacts and tourist cities have to face a number of challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

The main actions in the URBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop new good practices that aim at reducing the amount of waste and to support the re-use, recycling, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities.
2. To organize the local stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies.

Project partners in URBAN-WASTE

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure no. 16: Information on waste sorting for cruise ships
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p><i>The maritime waste coordinator at Copenhagen Malmoe Port (CMP) and the project manager in the City of Copenhagen are responsible for the partnership.</i></p> <p><i>The harbour uses own resources already allocated to the handling of waste from cruise ships, and the staff in the City of Copenhagen is financed through the Urban Waste project.</i></p> <p><i>Expenses to waste handling at the harbour is financed through the ordinary harbour fee paid by the cruise ships to the harbour, due to the principle of "no special fee" for the handling of waste. The principle of "no special fee" is related to the aim of avoiding marine litter.</i></p>
Target audience	<p><i>Copenhagen Malmoe Port cruise ship terminal, waste management handling.</i></p> <p><i>The communication from the port authority is targeted the cruise ships/staff and not the tourists directly.</i></p>
Involvement of the actors	<p><i>Contact made between Copenhagen/Malmoe Port authority staff and The City of Copenhagen (CPH) through personal meeting in beginning of 2017.</i></p> <p><i>Tasks are carried out via:</i></p> <p><i>Meetings between port authority and the City regarding handling of the waste from cruise ships entering the harbour.</i></p> <p><i>Discussions about best practice of waste sorting. Recycling possibilities aso.</i></p> <p><i>Discussions between CPH and CMP to improve communication about waste sorting to cruise ships.</i></p> <p><i>Meetings and e-mail-contact to follow up on effect.</i></p>

Target setting and setting up the measures

Improve the handling of waste from cruise ships at the harbour. The target should support the aim of avoiding marine littering, and amounts of waste should therefore not decline! Focus on hazardous waste should ensure, that the amounts of hazardous waste should rise.

Specific targets:

- *Ensuring recycling of plastic waste via Support from experts in City administration and contract between CMP and the waste-handling company*
- *Ensuring handling of hazardous waste via contract with local company with hazardous waste-specialists*
- *Amounts of hazardous waste should rise*
- *Improving communication between harbour and cruise ships (through evaluation of communication material)*
- *Use of communication material by sending it to all cruise ships docking in the harbour during the season 2018 and years to come*
- *Help from the City with the waste management plan in CMP.*
- *Improve the overall recycling from 21 % in 2016 to 30 % in 2018.*

Resources available and needed

- *Resources already allocated at harbour authority, no extra resources needed*
- *Communication between harbour and cruise ships is via e-mail, hence no printing costs.*
- *Budget for waste-handling at the harbour (not available)*

Timing

- *start-up phase: initial contact, dialogue about waste handling, final design of communication materials,, new waste-plan for CMP, organisation of waste management at the cruise-terminal, start up of monitoring: **June 2017-April 2018 (all these tasks are carried out as planned)***
- *Discussions with CMP and the Danish Harbour organisation about possibilities of better waste handling in other ports: **May 2018 (carried out)***
- *full implementation phase: the cruise season: **May-October 2018***
- *Evaluation phase: Monitoring of effects: **December 2018/January 2019***

Monitoring

Registrations for the season 2016:

Number of cruise-ships: 308

Number of cruise guests/staff: 560.000/150-185.000

Waste-amounts: from app. 80 % of the cruise-ships

Waste at cruise-terminal	2016
	Tonnes
Landfill/special treatment	39,74
Hazardous waste	0,02
Plastic	9,38
Wood	119,73
Metals	4,46
Cardboard	93,04
Glass	81,48
Incineration/mixed	1.125,73
C/D	12,08
Total	1.485,66

Recycling rate: 21,5

Incineration: 75,5

Landfill/special treatment: 3

Make a new registration on waste amount after cruise season May-October 2018

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

City of Copenhagen and DHL Stafetten hereby agree on a voluntary partnership about initiatives to minimize/improve sorting of waste from events.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Why partnership?

Waste management from tourism is increasingly important as Europe's cities are some of the world's greatest tourism destinations. The City of Copenhagen has the past 7 years seen an increase in tourism, which now has passed 10 mio. overnights stay per year. This corresponds to waste production from 27,000 inhabitants.

How can we get a cleaner city? Every day, waste is generated from the activities in the city. Especially in summertime, where the whole city is filled with life and activities from Copenhageners, local tourists and tourists from abroad. The City of Copenhagen participates with 10 other European cities and regions in an URBAN-WASTE project www.urban-waste.eu in order to focus on waste from tourism. How can we prevent waste or treat it better?

The City of Copenhagen has great focus on sustainable living including waste minimizing, reuse and recycling. It is essential to make the transformation from waste disposal to exploitation of resources. Materials must no longer be discarded and wasted; they must circulate in the cycle for as long as possible. The city cannot assume this task by itself. We need your contribution and inspiration to create a more sustainable city.

By signing the Diploma for this voluntary Public-Private Partnership you declare your voluntary contribution as described on the Diploma and specified in the Operative Plan.

URBAN-WASTE background

URBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative environmental impacts and tourist cities have to face a number of challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

The main actions in the URBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop new good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and to support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities.
2. To organize the local stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies.

Project partners in URBAN-WASTE

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure no. 18: Eco-event guidelines
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Lars Nissen, Race Coordinator at DHL Stafetten who is also responsible for waste handling at the race.</i> - <i>Business waste supervisors from Copenhagen Municipality, who inspires and guides event organizers to sort and minimize the amount of waste from events Katherine.Mary.Poneta@tmf.kk.dk</i> - <i>Birte.Busch.Thomsen@tmf.kk.dk and Katherine.Mary.Poneta@tmf.kk.dk from Copenhagen Municipality will in dialog with DHL Stafetten monitor the effect of waste prevention initiatives.</i>
Target audience	<p><i>DHL Stafetten is big yearly relay race taking place in Copenhagen and 4 other Danish cities. It started back in 1981. You can choose between joining in a group of 5, where each person is running 5 km or you can chose to walk 5 km in a joint group.</i></p> <p><i>The relay race in Copenhagen is split over 5 days due to the many participants (125.000 people from 3.500 companies). It is the largest relay race in the world for armatures and it takes place in Copenhagen from the 27th August – 31st August 2018.</i></p> <p><i>DHL Stafetten is primarily aiming Danish Companies but foreign companies can also participate. Tourists are able to watch the race in green surroundings and park area.</i></p> <p><i>The participants can get a lunch box or a smaller snack box, but they can also bring their own food and drink. Some companies bring their own catering companies to prepare the food on a grill.</i></p> <p><i>The City of Copenhagen is targeting the event organizer, staff and volunteers and the catering companies.</i></p>
Involvement of the actors	<p><i>Personal contact and dialog with the event organizer before the event to discuss options for waste minimization and recycling.</i></p> <p><i>Business waste supervisors from Copenhagen Municipality will have some introductive dialog meetings with DHL where the partners agreed on the recycling initiatives and supervisors will also visit the event in August and guide the staff/volunteers on waste handling and verify that it is done correctly.</i></p> <p><i>Waste collecting company HCS who rents and collect waste containers.</i></p> <p><i>Before the event the City Waste Supervisors from Copenhagen will contact up to 50 of the biggest catering companies booked by companies joining the relay race. The</i></p>

purpose is having a dialog about waste sorting and opportunity for minimizing of food waste.

Target setting

The city supervisors will guide personal and volunteers in sorting and recycling in prioritized areas such as back stage of plastic, soft plastic, biowaste and cardboard, and in front stage of cardboard and glass sorting.

During and after the event the city supervisors will evaluate the recycling work done by the staff and participants in the relay race.

Minimizing food waste by having 2 sizes of lunch boxes. A lunch box and a snack box.

Lunch boxes which are not handed over to the participants goes to "fødevarebanken" who distribute it to charity (homeless shelters).

Dialog about handling surplus food from catering companies (more difficult to handle as the food has been outside / in open air too long to be allowed for charity).

Dialog with up to 50 catering companies about waste sorting and minimizing of food waste.

Dialog about getting access to drinking water from fire hydrants.

(Previous problems with recyclable water bottles, as the area is open for collectors and potential thefts)

(Previous used environmental friendly water cardboards have been found to be dissolvable).

Setting up the measures

- *The City of Copenhagen will set up 2-3 initial meetings with the event organizer to discuss options for waste recycling*
- *The event organizers must get a permission to host an event in Copenhagen*
- *The event organizer will communicate and train the staff and volunteers about waste sorting and dialog with people attending the event.*
- *The event organizers will be in contact with waste collecting companies to ensure enough waste containers for efficient waste sorting*
- *The City of Copenhagen will be in dialog with catering companies before the event in order to improve waste sorting backstage to get better materials for recycling.*
- *The City of Copenhagen will visit the event to guide and answer questions from the staff and volunteers*
- *The City of Copenhagen will help designing the sorting signs for each recyclable material*
- *The City of Copenhagen/the city supervisors will have 2-4 internal meetings to exchange experiences of the initiatives in order to improve the initiatives next year and in order to improve the dialog with other event organizers in the future.*

Resources available and needed

- *Time for meetings and training of staff and volunteers and collecting data and feedback on experiences.*

Timing

- *The City of Copenhagen had gathered different event organizers at the 4th CoP on 17th April 2018 in order to help large events in the city to become more clean and sustainable by letting the organizers share experiences of best practice from previous events.*
- *DHL Stafetten gets a permission from Copenhagen Municipality, the Environmental Protection Department allowing them to host the event when they fulfil the Danish and EU legislation on e.g. commercial waste (waste back stage)*
- *Host the initial meetings with the event organizer in May and June 2018 about rules and demands for waste sorting and recycling and guiding on good practice.*
- *Organize training of staff and volunteers before the event*
- *Planning and implementing the waste collection at the sight*
- *The race takes place in Copenhagen from the 27th August – 31st August 2018.*
- *The event organizer arrange pickup of the different waste fraction*
- *The event organizer and the City of Copenhagen follow up on the experiences of sorting and minimizing waste.*

Monitoring

Where it is possible we will collect data on sorted waste based on the information given on the invoice from the waste collection companies.

We will estimate the waste amount and the number of participants based on sold tickets.

The event organizer and the City of Copenhagen follow up on the experiences of sorting and minimizing waste at the event.

Relevant monitoring parameters

Monitoring of actions, items, stakeholders and people involved etc.	
Guidelines distributed	number
People attending the event	number
Measures implemented:	number
measures enhancing separated collection of paper	number
measures enhancing separated collection of glass	number
measures enhancing separated collection of plastic	number
measures enhancing separated collection of organic waste	number
measures enhancing tap water and drinks with dispenser	number
measures enhancing reusable glass bottle	number
measures enhancing minimization of single dose food	number
measures enhancing food donation to charities	number
other: specify.....	number

Waste production monitoring	
plastic waste collected (weighted)	kg
paper waste collected (weighted)	kg
organic waste collected (weighted)	kg
glass waste collected (weighted)	kg
unsorted waste collected (weighted)	kg
Second option in case it is not possible to weight waste produced:	
bin (collecting plastic waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting paper waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting organic waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting glass waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting unsorted waste) filled in	number
bin (collecting plastic waste) capacity	litre
bin (collecting paper waste) capacity	litre
bin (collecting glass waste) capacity	litre
bin (collecting unsorted waste) capacity	litre

Gender considerations	
Who takes ultimate responsibility for event?	male-female
Who organises and conducts the rubbish collection?	% female
Approximately how many people take part in the event?	% female

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

LISBON

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

Contents

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Hotel 3K Europa

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measures 2- Food Waste Prevention+20- Food Tracking System Device (App), aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure ;
 - To endorse the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Banner";
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- COMMITMENTS OF HOTEL 3K EUROPA
 - to implement Measure number 2 - Food Waste Prevention + 20- Food Tracking System Device (App);
 - to reduce in 15% food waste in the Hotel;
 - to reduce in 5% the unsorted waste production of the Hotel;
 - To be aware and promote gender equity.

If the Entity be unsuccessful in achieving the goals here defined, there would be no consequences or fines.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measures n. 2 Food waste prevention + 20 Food tracking device
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Altis Avenida Hotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.2)</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa - Implementation and Monitoring of measures (nº.2+nº.20)</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa – Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The employees and customers of the Altis Avenida Hotel - The customers of the Hotel 3K Europa - Students, Teachers and Staff of the Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa -The employees and customers of ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Dissemination of information both to employees, customers and/or students on the the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and implementation of Measures; - Communication materials; - Promotion and Dissemination in social media.
Target setting	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel is going to implement Measure number 2 - Food prevention at Employees Cafeteria(All meals) and Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the Hotel. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Zero Waste Association</i>.</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa is going to implement Measures number 2 - Food prevention + 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), at Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) and Kitchen (when we have lunch and/or dinner) aiming to reduce in 15% food waste in the Hotel.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the School. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Refood</i>.</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the hotel. Bar - waste production Restaurant - customers waste Kitchen -Preparation Waste +</p>

	<p>Expired Product and Overproduction Cafeteria -Employees Waste.</p> <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy; -Information and awareness: What is the required amount of food for children What is the required amount of food for adults (F / M) → Right Dose <u>Design of materials</u> 20 Labels for tables Monitoring Assessment</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel. (*) -Information and awareness <u>Monitoring</u> -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; Monitoring -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; -Definition of communication Strategy; <u>Monitoring</u></p>

	<p>-Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) - Monthly evaluation and process adjustment Assessment</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Team from the Department of Waste Management + Department of Health, Hygiene and Safety</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 140 (*) and website/social media.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 6 Poster; Promocard on social media. Banner on digital email signature</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> Posters (10) + promocards (60)</p> <p><u>Financial Resources:</u> NA There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality. Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotels.</p>
Timing	<p>4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018</p> <p>Star up phase: March - May 2018</p> <p>Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018</p> <p>* <i>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa</i>, due to school year calendar it will have a different monitoring phase. They will do it from October to January.</p>
Monitoring	<p>Percentage of organic waste reduction or Kgs of organic waste reduction Estimate of tourist who receive information on site Hotel occupancy rate communication/signs in the buffet reuse of edible leftovers in the kitchen Survey delivered to the customer at checkout Number of students.</p>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Hotel 3K Europa

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measures 10 -Waste sorting in 140 hotel rooms, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Avenida da República, 93 - Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure ;
 - To endorse the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Banner";
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- COMMITMENTS OF HOTEL 3K EUROPA
 - To implement Measure number 10 - Waste sorting in hotel rooms – 140 rooms;
 - To reduce in 15% waste produce in the Hotel rooms;
 - Positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability;
 - To be aware and promote gender equity.

If the Entity be unsuccessful in achieving the goals here defined, there would be no consequences or fines.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

Measure n. 10 – Waste sorting in hotel (rooms)	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>HOTEL 3K EUROPA - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL 3K EUROPA Measure implementation in all hotel Rooms (140)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE Measure implementation in all hotel (88 Rooms)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE Measure implementation in all hotel (83 Rooms).</p>
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to implement selective collection in 140 rooms. - The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to implement selective collection. - The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to implement selective collection at the hotel.
Target setting	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in 140 rooms: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 15% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in the hotel: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability

	<p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA: Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (*) and website/social media. Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE : Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (<i>Book</i>) and website (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE: Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available at hotel social media (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p>
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p><u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + the Lisbon Municipality Team <u>Financial Resources:</u> NA</p> <p>There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality.</p> <p>Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotel. (*)</p>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690452

Timing	4th CoP Public launch event: 10/09/2018 Star up phase: March - May 2018 Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June -November 2018
Monitoring	Percentage or Number of rooms with selective collection Hotel occupancy rate Percentage of selective deposition

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Associação da Hotelaria de Portugal

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measures 2; 2+20; 7; 10 and 20, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure
 - Promote the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Seal"
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage.

- COMMITMENTS OF THE ASSOCIAÇÃO DA HOTELARIA DE PORTUGAL:
 - Disseminate UrBAN WASTE goals in Lisbon on social media (newsletter, workshops, other);
 - Disseminate UrBAN WASTE Measures that will be implemented in Lisbon by Hotels, according to the provided reports;
 - Disseminate WasteApp;
 - Disseminate Project results.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measures n. 2 Food waste prevention + 20 Food tracking device
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Altis Avenida Hotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.2)</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa - Implementation and Monitoring of measures (nº.2+nº.20)</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa – Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The employees and customers of the Altis Avenida Hotel - The customers of the Hotel 3K Europa - Students, Teachers and Staff of the Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa -The employees and customers of ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Dissemination of information both to employees, customers and/or students on the the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and implementation of Measures; - Communication materials; - Promotion and Dissemination in social media.
Target setting	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel is going to implement Measure number 2 - Food prevention at Employees Cafeteria(All meals) and Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the Hotel. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Zero Waste Association</i>.</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa is going to implement Measures number 2 - Food prevention + 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), at Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) and Kitchen (when we have lunch and/or dinner) aiming to reduce in 15% food waste in the Hotel.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the School. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Refood</i>.</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the hotel. Bar - waste production Restaurant - customers waste Kitchen -Preparation Waste + Expired Product and Overproduction Cafeteria -Employees Waste.</p>

	<p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy; -Information and awareness: What is the required amount of food for children What is the required amount of food for adults (F / M) → Right Dose <u>Design of materials</u> 20 Labels for tables Monitoring Assessment</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel. (*) -Information and awareness <u>Monitoring</u> -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; Monitoring -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; -Definition of communication Strategy; <u>Monitoring</u> -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App)</p>

	<p>- Monthly evaluation and process adjustment Assessment</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Team from the Department of Waste Management + Department of Health, Hygiene and Safety</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 140 (*) and website/social media.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 6 Poster; Promocard on social media. Banner on digital email signature</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> Posters (10) + promocards (60)</p> <p><u>Financial Resources:</u> NA There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality. Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotels.</p>
Timing	<p>4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018</p> <p>Star up phase: March - May 2018</p> <p>Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018</p> <p>* <i>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa</i>, due to school year calendar it will have a different monitoring phase. They will do it from October to January.</p>
Monitoring	<p>Percentage of organic waste reduction or Kgs of organic waste reduction Estimate of tourist who receive information on site Hotel occupancy rate communication/signs in the buffet reuse of edible leftovers in the kitchen Survey delivered to the customer at checkout Number of students.</p>

Measure n. 7 - Substitution of disposable products in hotels			
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Holiday Inn Lisboa - Implementation of measures and Monitoring</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>		
Target audience	<p>The target are the costumers of the Holiday Inn Lisboa Hotel</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>HOLIDAY INN LISBOA</td> <td>All the rooms</td> </tr> </table>	HOLIDAY INN LISBOA	All the rooms
HOLIDAY INN LISBOA	All the rooms		
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Implementation of measure number 7 in 169 rooms of the Holiday Inn Lisboa Hotel. 		
Target setting	<p>The Holiday Inn Lisboa is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informe the Customer of the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and substitution of amenities by dispensers in all rooms in order to achieve good environmental pratices, through the adaptation of sustainable choices. - Reduce in 2% the amount of waste result from disposable products. <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>		
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Replacement of disposable products in room by dispensers; -Customer communication strategy regarding the advantage of using rechargeable products letting him know that the amenities items are in the Reception and that they are still entitled to them; -Dissemination on social media networks and our Business Partners; -Monitoring the process. 		
Resources available and needed	<p><u>Human Resources</u>: Hotel Staff and the Lisbon Municipality Team</p> <p><u>Financial Resources</u>: NA</p> <p>There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality.</p> <p>Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotel.</p>		
Timing	<p>4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018</p> <p>Star up phase: March - May 2018</p> <p>Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018</p>		
Monitoring	<p>Nr and % of rooms involved</p> <p>Percentage of organic waste reduction</p>		

	<p>Nrº of information distributed to customers by the Hotel.</p> <p>Nº or % of amenities kit requested by customers.</p> <p>Hotel occupation rate during monitoring phase.</p>
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Measure n. 10 – Waste sorting in hotel (rooms)	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>HOTEL 3K EUROPA - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL 3K EUROPA Measure implementation in all hotel Rooms (140)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE Measure implementation in all hotel (88 Rooms)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE Measure implementation in all hotel (83 Rooms).</p>
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to implement selective collection in 140 rooms. - The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to implement selective collection. - The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to implement selective collection at the hotel.
Target setting	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in 140 rooms: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 15% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in the hotel: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA:</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (*) and website/social media. Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE :</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (<i>Book</i>) and website (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE:</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available at hotel social media (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p>
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p><u>Human Resources</u>: Hotel Staff + the Lisbon Municipality Team <u>Financial Resources</u>: NA</p> <p>There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality.</p>

	Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotels. (*)
Timing	4th CoP Public launch event: 10/09/2018 Star up phase: March - May 2018 Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June -November 2018
Monitoring	Percentage or Number of rooms with selective collection Hotel occupancy rate Percentage of selective deposition

UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrmaton Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Altis – Sociedade de Empreendimentos Turísticos e Hoteleiros, SA

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measures 2-Food waste prevention, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure ;
 - To endorse the creation of the “UrBAN-WASTE Project Banner”;
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- COMMITMENTS OF ALTIS – SOCIEDADE DE EMPREENDIMENTOS TURÍSTICOS E HOTELEIROS, SA
 - to implement Measure number 2 - Food prevention at buffets and restaurants;
 - to reduce food waste in the Hotel;
 - to reduce in 10% the food waste production of the Hotel
 - to be aware and promote the gender equality.

If the Entity be unsuccessful in achieving the goals here defined, there would be no consequences or fines.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measures n. 2 Food waste prevention + 20 Food tracking device
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Altis Avenida Hotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.2)</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa - Implementation and Monitoring of measures (nº.2+nº.20)</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa – Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The employees and customers of the Altis Avenida Hotel - The customers of the Hotel 3K Europa - Students, Teachers and Staff of the Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa -The employees and customers of ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Dissemination of information both to employees, customers and/or students on the the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and implementation of Measures; - Communication materials; - Promotion and Dissemination in social media.
Target setting	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel is going to implement Measure number 2 - Food prevention at Employees Cafeteria(All meals) and Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the Hotel. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Zero Waste Association</i>.</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa is going to implement Measures number 2 - Food prevention + 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), at Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) and Kitchen (when we have lunch and/or dinner) aiming to reduce in 15% food waste in the Hotel.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the School. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Refood</i>.</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the hotel. Bar - waste production Restaurant - customers waste Kitchen -Preparation Waste +</p>

	<p>Expired Product and Overproduction Cafeteria -Employees Waste.</p> <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy; -Information and awareness: What is the required amount of food for children What is the required amount of food for adults (F / M) → Right Dose <u>Design of materials</u> 20 Labels for tables Monitoring Assessment</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel. (*) -Information and awareness <u>Monitoring</u> -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; Monitoring -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; -Definition of communication Strategy; <u>Monitoring</u></p>

	<p>-Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) - Monthly evaluation and process adjustment Assessment</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Team from the Department of Waste Management + Department of Health, Hygiene and Safety</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 140 (*) and website/social media.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 6 Poster; Promocard on social media. Banner on digital email signature</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> Posters (10) + promocards (60)</p> <p><u>Financial Resources:</u> NA There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality. Communication materials will be replicated by the EHT de Lisboa.</p>
Timing	<p>4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018</p> <p>Star up phase: March - May 2018</p> <p>Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - October 2018</p> <p>* <i>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa</i>, due to school year calendar it will have a different monitoring phase. They will do it from October to January.</p>
Monitoring	<p>Percentage of organic waste reduction or Kgs of organic waste reduction Estimate of tourist who receive information on site Hotel occupancy rate communication/signs in the buffet reuse of edible leftovers in the kitchen Survey delivered to the customer at checkout Number of students.</p>

UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Turismo de Lisboa - Visitors and Convention Bureau

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measures 2+20; 7; and 10, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
- Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure ;
- To endorse the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Banner";
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage.

- COMMITMENTS OF THE TURISMO DE LISBOA - VISITORS AND CONVENTION BUREAU

- Disseminate UrBAN WASTE goals in Lisbon on social media (newsletter, workshops, other);
- Disseminate UrBAN WASTE Measures being implemented in Lisbon by Hotels;
- Disseminate WasteApp;
- Disseminate Project results.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measures n. 2 Food waste prevention + 20 Food tracking device
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Altis Avenida Hotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.2)</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa - Implementation and Monitoring of measures (nº.2+nº.20)</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa – Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The employees and customers of the Altis Avenida Hotel - The customers of the Hotel 3K Europa - Students, Teachers and Staff of the Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa -The employees and customers of ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Dissemination of information both to employees, customers and/or students on the the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and implementation of Measures; - Communication materials; - Promotion and Dissemination in social media.
Target setting	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel is going to implement Measure number 2 - Food prevention at Employees Cafeteria(All meals) and Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the Hotel. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Zero Waste Association</i>.</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa is going to implement Measures number 2 - Food prevention + 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), at Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) and Kitchen (when we have lunch and/or dinner) aiming to reduce in 15% food waste in the Hotel.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the School. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Refood</i>.</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the hotel. Bar - waste production Restaurant - customers waste Kitchen -Preparation Waste +</p>

	<p>Expired Product and Overproduction Cafeteria - Employees Waste.</p> <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy; -Information and awareness: What is the required amount of food for children What is the required amount of food for adults (F / M) → Right Dose <u>Design of materials</u> 20 Labels for tables Monitoring Assessment</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel. (*) -Information and awareness <u>Monitoring</u> -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; Monitoring -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; -Definition of communication Strategy; <u>Monitoring</u></p>

	<p>-Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) - Monthly evaluation and process adjustment Assessment</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Team from the Department of Waste Management + Department of Health, Hygiene and Safety</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 140 (*) and website/social media.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 6 Poster; Promocard on social media. Banner on digital email signature</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> Posters (10) + promocards (60)</p> <p><u>Financial Resources:</u> NA There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality. Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotels.</p>
Timing	<p>4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018</p> <p>Star up phase: March - May 2018</p> <p>Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018</p> <p>* <i>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa</i>, due to school year calendar it will have a different monitoring phase. They will do it from October to January.</p>
Monitoring	<p>Percentage of organic waste reduction or Kgs of organic waste reduction Estimate of tourist who receive information on site Hotel occupancy rate communication/signs in the buffet reuse of edible leftovers in the kitchen Survey delivered to the customer at checkout Number of students.</p>

Measure n. 7 - Substitution of disposable products in hotels			
Managing team; roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Holiday Inn Lisboa - Implementation of measures and Monitoring</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>		
Target audience	<p>The target are the costumers of the Holiday Inn Lisboa Hotel</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>HOLIDAY INN LISBOA</td> <td>All the rooms</td> </tr> </table>	HOLIDAY INN LISBOA	All the rooms
HOLIDAY INN LISBOA	All the rooms		
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Implementation of measure number 7 in 169 rooms of the Holiday Inn Lisboa Hotel. 		
Target setting	<p>The Holiday Inn Lisboa is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informe the Customer of the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and substitution of amenities by dispensers in all rooms in order to achieve good environmental practices, through the adaptation of sustainable choices. - Reduce in 2% the amount of waste result from disposable products. <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>		
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Replacement of disposable products in room by dispensers; -Customer communication strategy regarding the advantage of using rechargeable products letting him know that the amenities items are in the Reception and that they are still entitled to them; -Dissemination on social media networks and our Business Partners; -Monitoring the process. 		
Resources available and needed	<p><u>Human Resources</u>: Hotel Staff and the Lisbon Municipality Team</p> <p><u>Financial Resources</u>: NA</p> <p>There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality.</p> <p>Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotel.</p>		
Timing	<p>4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018</p> <p>Star up phase: March - May 2018</p> <p>Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018</p>		
Monitoring	<p>Nr and % of rooms involved</p> <p>Percentage of organic waste reduction</p>		

	<p>Nr^o of information distributed to customers by the Hotel.</p> <p>Nr^o or % of amenities kit requested by customers.</p> <p>Hotel occupation rate during monitoring phase.</p>
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Measure n. 10 – Waste sorting in hotel (rooms)	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>HOTEL 3K EUROPA - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL 3K EUROPA Measure implementation in all hotel Rooms (140)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE Measure implementation in all hotel (88 Rooms)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE Measure implementation in all hotel (83 Rooms).</p>
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to implement selective collection in 140 rooms. - The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to implement selective collection. - The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to implement selective collection at the hotel.
Target setting	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in 140 rooms: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 15% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in the hotel: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability

	<p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA:</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (*) and website/social media. Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE :</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (<i>Book</i>) and website (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE:</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available at hotel social media (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p>
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p><u>Human Resources</u>: Hotel Staff + the Lisbon Municipality Team <u>Financial Resources</u>: NA</p> <p>There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality.</p> <p>Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotel. (*)</p>

Timing	4th CoP Public launch event: 10/09/2018 Star up phase: March - May 2018 Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June -November 2018
Monitoring	Percentage or Number of rooms with selective collection Hotel occupancy rate Percentage of selective deposition

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosa Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Escola de Turismo e Hotelaria de Lisboa

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure 20- Food Tracking System Device (App), aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions
 - Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure
 - Promote the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Seal"
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- COMMITMENTS OF ESCOLA DE TURISMO E HOTELARIA DE LISBOA
 - to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App);
 - to reduce in 10% food waste in the School;
 - to be aware and promote the gender equality;
 - Positive external image of the School associated with sustainability.

If the Entity be unsuccessful in achieving the goals here defined, there would be no consequences or fines.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measures n. 2 Food waste prevention + 20 Food tracking device
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Altis Avenida Hotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.2)</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa - Implementation and Monitoring of measures (nº.2+nº.20)</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa – Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The employees and customers of the Altis Avenida Hotel - The customers of the Hotel 3K Europa - Students, Teachers and Staff of the Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa -The employees and customers of ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Dissemination of information both to employees, customers and/or students on the the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and implementation of Measures; - Communication materials; - Promotion and Dissemination in social media.
Target setting	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel is going to implement Measure number 2 - Food prevention at Employees Cafeteria(All meals) and Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the Hotel. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Zero Waste Association</i>.</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa is going to implement Measures number 2 - Food prevention + 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), at Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) and Kitchen (when we have lunch and/or dinner) aiming to reduce in 15% food waste in the Hotel.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the School. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Refood</i>.</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the hotel. Bar - waste production Restaurant - customers waste Kitchen -Preparation Waste +</p>

	<p>Expired Product and Overproduction Cafeteria -Employees Waste.</p> <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy; -Information and awareness: What is the required amount of food for children What is the required amount of food for adults (F / M) → Right Dose <u>Design of materials</u> 20 Labels for tables Monitoring Assessment</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel. (*) -Information and awareness <u>Monitoring</u> -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; Monitoring -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; -Definition of communication Strategy; <u>Monitoring</u></p>

	<p>-Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) - Monthly evaluation and process adjustment Assessment</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Team from the Department of Waste Management + Department of Health, Hygiene and Safety</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 140 (*) and website/social media.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 6 Poster; Promocard on social media. Banner on digital email signature</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> Posters (10) + promocards (60)</p> <p><u>Financial Resources:</u> NA There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality. Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotels.</p>
Timing	<p>4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018</p> <p>Star up phase: March - May 2018</p> <p>Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018</p> <p>* <i>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa</i>, due to school year calendar it will have a different monitoring phase. They will do it from October to January.</p>
Monitoring	<p>Percentage of organic waste reduction or Kgs of organic waste reduction Estimate of tourist who receive information on site Hotel occupancy rate communication/signs in the buffet reuse of edible leftovers in the kitchen Survey delivered to the customer at checkout Number of students.</p>

UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Holiday Inn Lisboa Hotel

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measures 7-Substitution of disposable products in hotels, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
- Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure ;
- To endorse the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Banner";
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- COMMITMENTS OF HOLIDAY INN LISBOA HOTEL

- to implement Measure number 7 - Substitution of disposable products in hotels;
- Reduce in 2% the amount of waste result from disposable products through the adaptation of sustainable choices;
- inform the Customer of the commitments to the Urban Waste project;
- Positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability;
- To be aware and promote gender equity.

If the Entity be unsuccessful in achieving the goals here defined, there would be no consequences or fines.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

Measure n. 7 - Substitution of disposable products in hotels			
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Holiday Inn Lisboa - Implementation of measures and Monitoring</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>		
Target audience	<p>The target are the costumers of the Holiday Inn Lisboa Hotel</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>HOLIDAY INN LISBOA</td> <td>All the rooms</td> </tr> </table>	HOLIDAY INN LISBOA	All the rooms
HOLIDAY INN LISBOA	All the rooms		
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Implementation of measure number 7 in 169 rooms of the Holiday Inn Lisboa Hotel. 		
Target setting	<p>The Holiday Inn Lisboa is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informe the Customer of the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and substitution of amenities by dispensers in all rooms in order to achieve good environmental practices, through the adaptation of sustainable choices. - Reduce in 2% the amount of waste result from disposable products. <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>		
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Replacement of disposable products in room by dispensers; -Customer communication strategy regarding the advantage of using rechargeable products letting him know that the amenities items are in the Reception and that they are still entitled to them; -Dissemination on social media networks and our Business Partners; -Monitoring the process. 		
Resources available and needed	<p><u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff and the Lisbon Municipality Team</p> <p><u>Financial Resources:</u> NA</p> <p>There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality.</p> <p>Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotel.</p>		

Timing	4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018 Star up phase: March - May 2018 Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018
Monitoring	Nr and % of rooms involved Percentage of organic waste reduction Nrº of information distributed to customers by the Hotel. Nº or % of amenities kit requested by customers. Hotel occupation rate during monitoring phase.

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

HOTEL NH Lisboa Campo Grande

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measures nº.10 - Waste sorting in hotel, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure ;
 - To endorse the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Banner";
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- COMMITMENTS OF HOTEL (NOME HOTEL)
 - To implement Measure number 10 - Waste sorting in hotel;
 - To reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel;
 - Positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability;
 - To be aware and promote gender equity.

If the Entity be unsuccessful in achieving the goals here defined, there would be no consequences or fines.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure n. 10 – Waste sorting in hotel (rooms)
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>HOTEL 3K EUROPA - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL 3K EUROPA Measure implementation in all hotel Rooms (140)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE Measure implementation in all hotel (88 Rooms)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE Measure implementation in all hotel (83 Rooms).</p>
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to implement selective collection in 140 rooms. - The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to implement selective collection. - The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to implement selective collection at the hotel.
Target setting	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in 140 rooms: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 15% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in the hotel: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability

	<p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA: Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (*) and website/social media. Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE : Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (<i>Book</i>) and website (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE: Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available at hotel social media (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p>
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p><u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + the Lisbon Municipality Team <u>Financial Resources:</u> NA</p> <p>There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality.</p> <p>Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotel. (*)</p>

Timing	4th CoP Public launch event: 10/09/2018 Star up phase: March - May 2018 Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018
Monitoring	Percentage or Number of rooms with selective collection Hotel occupancy rate Percentage of selective deposition

UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosa Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Onj São Lázaro Aparthotel

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure 20- Food Tracking System Device (App), aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions
- Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure
- Promote the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Seal"
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- COMMITMENTS OF Onj São Lázaro Aparthotel

- to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App);
- to reduce in 10% food waste at the Hotel;
- inform the Customer of the commitments to the Urban Waste project ;
- Positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability.
- To be aware and promote gender equity.

If the Entity be unsuccessful in achieving the goals here defined, there would be no consequences or fines.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measures n. 2 Food waste prevention + 20 Food tracking device
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>Altis Avenida Hotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.2)</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa - Implementation and Monitoring of measures (nº.2+nº.20)</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa – Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel - Implementation and Monitoring of measure (nº.20)</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The employees and customers of the Altis Avenida Hotel - The customers of the Hotel 3K Europa - Students, Teachers and Staff of the Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa -The employees and customers of ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - Dissemination of information both to employees, customers and/or students on the the commitment to the UrBAN-WASTE Project and implementation of Measures; - Communication materials; - Promotion and Dissemination in social media.
Target setting	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel is going to implement Measure number 2 - Food prevention at Employees Cafeteria(All meals) and Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the Hotel. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Zero Waste Association</i>.</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa is going to implement Measures number 2 - Food prevention + 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), at Customers Breakfast buffet (Buffet PA) and Kitchen (when we have lunch and/or dinner) aiming to reduce in 15% food waste in the Hotel.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the School. Reuse of edible leftovers to <i>Refood</i>.</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel is going to implement Measure number 20 - Food Tracking System Device (App), aiming to reduce in 10% food waste in the hotel. Bar - waste production Restaurant - customers waste Kitchen -Preparation Waste +</p>

	<p>Expired Product and Overproduction Cafeteria -Employees Waste.</p> <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy; -Information and awareness: What is the required amount of food for children What is the required amount of food for adults (F / M) → Right Dose <u>Design of materials</u> 20 Labels for tables Monitoring Assessment</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the food waste measures and ensure the client communications strategy; -Definition of the communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel. (*) -Information and awareness <u>Monitoring</u> -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; Monitoring -Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) Assessment</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Food waste reduction implementation</u> -Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring measures; -Definition of communication Strategy; <u>Monitoring</u></p>

	<p>-Training about the Food Tracking System Device (App) -Monitoring of food waste with the Food Tracking System Device (App) - Monthly evaluation and process adjustment Assessment</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Altis Avenida Hotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Team from the Department of Waste Management + Department of Health, Hygiene and Safety</p> <p>Hotel 3K Europa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 140 (*) and website/social media.</p> <p>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> 6 Poster; Promocard on social media. Banner on digital email signature</p> <p>ONJ São Lázaro Aparthotel <u>Human Resources:</u> Hotel Staff + Lisbon Municipality Urban Waste Team + Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Food Tracking System Device Team) <u>Others:</u> Food Tracking System Device (App) <u>Communication Materials:</u> Posters (10) + promocards (60)</p> <p><u>Financial Resources:</u> NA There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality. Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotels.</p>
Timing	<p>4th CoP Public event: 10/09/2018</p> <p>Star up phase: March - May 2018</p> <p>Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June - November 2018</p> <p>* <i>Escola de Hotelaria e Turismo de Lisboa</i>, due to school year calendar it will have a different monitoring phase. They will do it from October to January.</p>
Monitoring	<p>Percentage of organic waste reduction or Kgs of organic waste reduction Estimate of tourist who receive information on site Hotel occupancy rate communication/signs in the buffet reuse of edible leftovers in the kitchen Survey delivered to the customer at checkout Number of students.</p>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Lisbon Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Lisbon and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated September, 2018,

between

Lisbon Municipality and

Hotel Vincci Liberdade

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measures nº.10 - Waste sorting in hotel, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Lisbon to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measures and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE LISBON MUNICIPALITY:
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - Monitoring and reports on the implementation of the measure ;
 - To endorse the creation of the "UrBAN-WASTE Project Banner";
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- COMMITMENTS OF HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE
 - To implement Measure number 10 - Waste sorting in hotel;
 - To reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel;
 - Positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability;
 - To be aware and promote gender equity.

If the Entity be unsuccessful in achieving the goals here defined, there would be no consequences or fines.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 10/09/2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on May 2019.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure n. 10 – Waste sorting in hotel (rooms)
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Lisbon Municipality - Coordination, Technical support and Monitoring the implementation of measures</p> <p>HOTEL 3K EUROPA - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE - Implementation and Monitoring of measures</p> <p>AHP – Dissemination</p> <p>Green Dot Company (SPV) - Dissemination</p> <p>Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau - Dissemination</p>
Target audience	<p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL 3K EUROPA Measure implementation in all hotel Rooms (140)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE Measure implementation in all hotel (88 Rooms)</p> <p>The target are the staff of the HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE Measure implementation in all hotel (83 Rooms).</p>
Involvement of the actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signature of UrBAN WASTE PPP; - The Municipality Team will continue to have meetings with the stakeholder all through the implementation phase; - The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to implement selective collection in 140 rooms. - The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to implement selective collection. - The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to implement selective collection at the hotel.
Target setting	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in 140 rooms: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 15% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection in the hotel: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability

	<p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE is going to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ implement selective waste collection: done by the housekeeping team ▪ separate plastic, paper and glass ▪ reduce in 12% waste produce in the Hotel rooms ▪ work in a positive external image of the Hotel associated with sustainability <p><u>AHP, Green Dot Company (SPV) and Turismo de Lisboa Visitors & Conversion Bureau</u>, will be promoting the Project and the Stakeholders by publishing/posting on their social media networks news and information concerning the implementation/monitoring phase and results.</p> <p><u>Lisbon Municipality</u> expects to reach more hotels in Lisbon. For that purpose the team will hold presentations and meetings with potential stakeholders.</p>
<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>The HOTEL 3K EUROPA:</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (*) and website/social media. Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL NH LISBOA CAMPO GRANDE :</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available in all rooms of the hotel (<i>Book</i>) and website (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p> <p>The HOTEL VINCCI LIBERDADE:</p> <p>Identification of the person(s) that will be responsible for the implementation and monitoring of implementation of the measure and ensure the client communications strategy; Information and awareness Definition of internal communication strategy: Information about the project available at hotel social media (<i>TBC</i>). Monitoring the results Assessment</p>
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p><u>Human Resources</u>: Hotel Staff + the Lisbon Municipality Team <u>Financial Resources</u>: NA</p> <p>There is no budget dedicated to the awareness sessions, activities will be done by the Municipality.</p> <p>Communication materials will be replicated by the Hotel. (*)</p>

Timing	4th CoP Public launch event: 10/09/2018 Star up phase: March - May 2018 Full Implementation and Monitoring phase: June – November 2018
Monitoring	Percentage or Number of rooms with selective collection Hotel occupancy rate Percentage of selective deposition

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

PONTA DELGADA

Acordo de Parceria Público-Privada para a implementação das medidas do URBAN-WASTE

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Descrição do UrBAN-WASTE

UrBAN-WASTE é um projeto Europeu financiado pelo Programa Horizonte 2020 que visa apresentar propostas aos decisores políticos para a elaboração de políticas eco-inovadoras e desenvolvimento de estratégias para fazer face aos desafios apresentados pelo turismo, no que diz respeito à gestão e produção de resíduos urbanos.

A redução da produção de resíduos é um importante componente para a qualificação da oferta turística e promoção do crescimento sustentável e inteligente, em cidades turísticas europeias. No entanto, o aumento do fluxo turístico acarreta uma variedade de externalidades negativas e as cidades turísticas têm de enfrentar desafios adicionais, relacionados com a produção e gestão de resíduos, devido às suas características geográficas e climáticas e à sazonalidade e especificidade do fluxo de turistas.

Considerando que:

No mês de junho de 2016, o signatário [FRCT, Fundo Regional para a Ciência e Tecnologia], em cooperação com 27 parceiros [Governo das Ilhas Canárias (coordenador do projeto), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa-Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Periferieia Ipeiroy (EPI), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Câmara Municipal de Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] iniciaram a implementação do projeto URBAN WASTE.

Considerando que:

Os objetivos e ações do projeto URBAN-WASTE são:

1. Desenvolver estratégias originais, eco-inovadoras e sensíveis ao género, bem como boas práticas que visem a redução da produção de resíduos e que apoiem a reutilização, reciclagem, recolha e eliminação de resíduos em cidades turísticas. Estas estratégias serão implementadas em 11 cidades piloto [Florença (IT), Nice (FR), Lisboa (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] e os resultados do projeto serão monitorizados e divulgados, facilitando a transferência e adaptação destas boas práticas noutras cidades.
2. Organizar Comunidades de Práticas (CoP), envolvendo diferentes colaboradores, incluindo de forma equilibrada homens e mulheres da indústria do turismo, autoridades de gestão de resíduos, ONG's, turistas, etc.. Através de um processo participativo as CoP discutem e selecionam as medidas a implementar em Ponta Delgada e definem o Plano Operacional para cada uma dessas medidas.

3. Garantir que cada medida é implementada pelas partes interessadas locais, privadas e/ou públicas, que, ao assinar o seguinte compromisso, concordam com a implementação de ações voluntárias, com o objetivo de reduzir a produção de resíduos e de promover o projeto UrBAN-WASTE através da organização de atividades de comunicação.

Assina-se, em 16 de março 2018, este acordo voluntário para a promoção da implementação das medidas estratégicas selecionadas, através de um processo participativo, para o Município de Ponta Delgada, no âmbito do projeto UrBAN-WASTE.

entre:

[o signatário A, Fundo Regional para a Ciência e Tecnologia] e;

[o signatário B, Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada];

[o signatário C, Direção Regional do Turismo];

[o signatário D, ARHESP - Associação da Hotelaria, Restauração e Similares de Portugal];

[o signatário E, ANA - Aeroportos de Portugal];

[o signatário F, AAFTH - Associação Açoriana de Formação Turística e Hoteleira];

[o signatário G, ERSARA, Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos dos Açores];

[o signatário H, Azoris Royal Garden];

[o signatário I, Hotel Marina Atlântico];

[o signatário J, Hotel Talisman];

[o signatário K, MUSAMI - Operações Municipais do Ambiente EIM];

[o signatário L, Portos dos Açores];

[o signatário M, Quinta Bom Despacho];

[o signatário N, SATA Air Açores].

Na data mencionada, é assinado o presente acordo voluntário para promoção da implementação de 3 Medidas Estratégicas do Projeto UrBAN-WASTE, visando em particular o envolvimento dos colaboradores locais [entidades públicas, entidades de gestão de resíduos, prestadores de serviços turísticos e ONG's locais], localizadas no concelho de Ponta Delgada, para aplicar ações específicas para reduzir a produção de resíduos e aperfeiçoar as práticas de gestão de resíduos.

Compromisso

As partes, concordam, portanto, em:

- Apoiar a implementação das 3 Medidas Estratégicas do Projeto do UrBAN-WASTE, em Ponta Delgada, que são:

Medida nº7: Substituição de produtos descartáveis em Hotéis;

Medida nº11: Cursos de formação e consultadoria de reciclagem para estabelecimentos turísticos;

Medida nº14: Tradução e disseminação das instruções de separação dos resíduos noutras línguas;

e fazer parte da Comunidade de Prática Local (CoP) que promoverá a sua implementação;

- Reconhecer as ações e o seu papel na implementação das Medidas descritas nos Planos Operacionais (*Anexo I*), comprometendo-se em respeitar e implementar os compromissos descritos, encontrando-os coerentes com a sua respectiva missão institucional ou comercial.

Ao assinar o presente acordo voluntário, as partes assumem os compromissos descritos e especificados nos Planos Operacionais (*Anexo I*).

Vigência do Acordo

Este acordo voluntário pode ser modificado por vontade das partes.

O acordo entra em vigor após a assinatura das autoridades oficiais dos signatários do projeto UrBAN-WASTE, em 16 de março de 2018, e será mantido efetivo até modificação ou término por qualquer um dos signatários, através de consenso mútuo. Caso contrário, este acordo termina em novembro 2018.

Nós, os abaixo-assinados, declaramos que lemos e aceitamos os termos e condições deste contrato, como acima descrito.

Ponta Delgada, 16 de março de 2018.

ANEXO I. Planos Operacionais

Implementação das medidas demonstrativas de prevenção e gestão de resíduos

Medida 7 - Substituição de produtos descartáveis em Hotéis	
Equipe de gestão: Ações e responsabilidades	<p>FRCT : Coordenação, Implementação e monitorização; Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada : Promoção e disseminação Direção Regional do Turismo: Promoção e disseminação; MUSAMI: Promoção e disseminação; AHRESP: Promoção e disseminação; Azoris Royal Garden: Implementação e monitorização; Hotel Talisman: Implementação e monitorização; Quinta do Bom Despacho: Promoção e disseminação, troca de boas práticas</p>
Público-alvo	<p>O público-alvo da medida são os clientes dos seguintes hotéis: - Hotel Marina Atlântico - Azoris Royal Garden - Hotel Talisman</p>
Envolvimento dos atores	<p>Assinatura do Acordo de Parceria UrBAN-WASTE;</p> <p>Estratégias de comunicação da medida para os clientes dos hotéis: - Uso de autocolantes informativos nos WCs explicando a substituição dos kits por recipientes reutilizáveis de champô e sabonete como uma boa prática ambiental.</p>
Definição de metas	<p>Implementação em 3 grandes hotéis até 31 de Maio (14 % dos hotéis de Ponta Delgada), com o objetivo de ter 5 hotéis em 1 de junho (aproximadamente 25 % dos hotéis em Ponta Delgada)</p>
Etapas para a execução das medidas	<p>Fase de planeamento:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reunião para discutir indicadores de monitorização da medida (FRCT e hotéis) - Escolha de produtos mais ecológicos para substituição dos kits (Hotéis) - Revisão dos contratos com os fornecedores dos kits (Hotéis) - Produção de materiais de comunicação e disseminação (FRCT) <p>Fase de implementação:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Troca dos kits pelos dispensadores nos quartos de hotel - Disseminação e comunicação da medida para encorajar hotéis da mesma rede a implementar a mesma medida(FRCT e hotéis) - Organização de visitas de acompanhamento na fase de implementação (FRCT e hotéis)

	<p>Fase de monitorização:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitas semanais ou mensais para recolha dos indicadores <p>Fase de avaliação:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Análise dos indicadores e da eficiência da medida.</i>
Recursos disponíveis e necessários	<p>Recursos humanos (RH):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - equipa dos hotéis para substituição do kits e manutenção dos dispensadores; - recolha dos indicadores (Hotéis e FRCT) <p>Recursos financeiros (RF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Material de comunicação e disseminação (FRCT) - Recursos financeiros para substituição dos kits pelos recipientes reutilizáveis. (Hóteis)
Agenda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assinatura do Acordo de Parceria UrBAN-WASTE –16 de março; - Fase de implementação: Março a abril/2018; - Monitorização da medida: Maio a outubro/2018.
Monitorização	<p><i>Indicadores a utilizar:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comparação da produção de resíduos originados pelos kits entre quartos com a medida e quartos sem a medida; - Número de contratos revistos/novos contratos com fornecedores dos kits e dos dispensadores e produtos. - Quantidade de consumo de descartáveis durante a implementação de a ação / medida [Kg] - Estimativa em Kg de itens que foram evitados com a implementação da medida (kg de amenities que seriam fornecidos por quarto). - Custos com a ação. Diferença entre o dinheiro gasto em descartáveis e com os dispensadores e produtos.

	<p><i>Medida 11 - Cursos de formação e consultadoria de reciclagem para estabelecimentos turísticos</i></p>
Equipe de gestão: Ações e responsabilidades	<p>FRCT : Coordenação, Implementação e monitorização; Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada: Coordenação operacional, Implementação, gestão de meios de apoio, monitorização, promoção e disseminação; MUSAMI: Implementação, promoção, disseminação e monitorização; AHRESP: Promoção e disseminação; Angariação de restaurantes.</p>
Público-alvo	Restaurantes da cidade de Ponta Delgada
Envolvimento dos atores	Assinatura do Acordo de Parceria UrBAN-WASTE; Assinatura do protocolo do "Programa Parceiros" Atribuição de selo do "Programa Parceiros"

	<p>Atribuição de selo de participação “We join UrBAN-WASTE Project”; Publicidade institucional nas páginas da internet do UrBAN-WASTE, MUSAMI e Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada; Publicidade gratuita na WASTE APP.</p>
Definição de metas	<p>Implementar a medida em 20 restaurantes até 15 de junho; Implementar a medida em mais 20 restaurantes até 31 de outubro; Medida abranger 15% do total de restaurantes de Ponta Delgada.</p>
Etapas para a execução das medidas	<p>Fase de planeamento: a) definição dos meios humanos e recursos necessários, da metodologia do projeto e do cronograma temporal; b) formação aos recursos humanos; c) aquisição de recursos de apoio para a comunicação e a fase de execução; d) Elaboração do selo de boas práticas para os estabelecimentos aderentes.</p> <p>Fase de Implementação:</p> <p>Fase de monitorização: -Visitas regulares aos estabelecimentos onde a medida foi implementada para acompanhamento e recolha dos indicadores.</p> <p>Fase de avaliação da medida: -Análise dos indicadores.</p>
Recursos disponíveis e necessários	<p>Recursos humanos (RH) e financeiros (RF): RH – 2 equipas de consultoria; RF – aquisição de sacos para deposição de resíduos urbanos e execução de material de comunicação; Os recursos já disponíveis incluem 1 equipa de consultoria e material promocional do “Programa Parceiros”.</p>
Agenda	<p>Assinatura do Acordo de Parceria UrBAN-WASTE –16 de março; Planeamento – até 30 de abril; Execução – de 1 maio a 31 de maio (20 restaurantes) e de 1 de junho a 31 de agosto (20 restaurantes); Monitorização – de 15 de maio a 31 de outubro.</p>
Monitorização	<p><u>Indicadores:</u> n.º de restaurantes abrangidos; n.º total de restaurantes total em PDL; % de restaurantes envolvidos; n.º de sacos de embalagem de P/M produzidos/dia; n.º de sacos de embalagem de P/C produzidos/dia; n.º de sacos de embalagem de V produzidos/dia; n.º de sacos de embalagem de RU produzidos/dia; n.º de clientes/dia.</p>

Medida 14 - Tradução e disseminação das instruções de separação dos resíduos noutras línguas	
Equipe de gestão: Ações e responsabilidades	<p>FRCT: Coordenação, Implementação e monitorização;</p> <p>Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada: Implementação, promoção e disseminação</p> <p>Direção Regional do Turismo: Promoção e disseminação;</p> <p>MUSAMI: Promoção e disseminação;</p> <p>AHRESP: Promoção e disseminação;</p> <p>Hotel Marina Atlântico: Implementação; Promoção e disseminação</p> <p>Azoris Royal Garden: Implementação; Promoção e disseminação</p> <p>Hotel Talisman: Implementação; Promoção e disseminação</p> <p>Quinta do Bom Despacho: Promoção e disseminação;</p> <p>ANA - Aeroportos: Implementação; Promoção e disseminação</p> <p>AAFTH: Implementação; Promoção e disseminação</p> <p>ERSARA: Promoção e disseminação;</p> <p>Portos dos Açores: Implementação; Promoção e disseminação</p> <p>SATA Air açores: Implementação; Promoção e disseminação</p>
Público-alvo	Turistas estrangeiros
Envolvimento dos atores	<p>Assinatura do Acordo de Parceria UrBAN-WASTE;</p> <p>- Disseminação de materiais de comunicação com instruções de separação de lixo traduzidos em diferentes línguas em estabelecimentos e áreas turísticas;</p> <p>- Utilização de contentores de separação nos espaços comuns, com <i>instruções em português, inglês e pictogramas.</i></p>
Definição de metas	<p>Disseminação de materiais de comunicação com instruções de separação de lixo :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 estabelecimentos aderentes até final de Maio; +20 estabelecimentos a partir de 1 de junho <p>Utilização de contentores de separação nos espaços comuns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 estabelecimentos até final de Maio, mais 3 estabelecimentos a partir de 1 de junho
Etapas para a execução das medidas	<p>Fase de planeamento:</p> <p>- Escolha do tipo de material, produção do layout e do texto em diferentes línguas.</p> <p>- Produção de material de comunicação;</p> <p>- Compra dos contentores de separação ou recurso a autocolantes informativos;</p>

	<p>Fase implementação:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Distribuição pelos estabelecimentos dos materiais com as instruções de separação; -Entrega dos materiais aos turistas pelos estabelecimentos; <p>Fase de monitorização</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visitas semanais ou mensais para recolha dos indicadores <p>Fase de avaliação:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Análise dos indicadores e da eficiência da medida.
Recursos disponíveis e necessários	<p>Recurso financeiros (RF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Materiais de comunicação com instruções de separação de lixo traduzido em diferentes línguas, Autocolantes (FRCT, Câmara Municipal); -Contentores de resíduos com as instruções (entidades aderentes)
Agenda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assinatura do Acordo de Parceria UrBAN-WASTE –16 de março; - Fase de implementação: Março a abril/2018; - Monitorização da medida: Maio a outubro/2018.
Monitorização	<p>Indicadores:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Percentagem de estabelecimentos que utilizam os materiais de comunicação; - Número de materiais com instruções distribuídos pelos estabelecimentos aos clientes; - Aferir o número de turistas que receberam a informação nos alojamentos.

Operative Plans

Measure nº7: Substitution of disposable products in hotels	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>FRCT : Coordination, Implementation and e monitoring; Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada: Promotion and dissemination Direção Regional do Turismo: Promotion and dissemination; MUSAMI: Promotion and dissemination; AHRESP: Promotion and dissemination; Hotel Marina Atlântico: Implementation and e monitoring; Azoris Royal Garden: Implementation and e monitoring; Hotel Talisman: Implementation and e monitoring; Quinta do Bom Despacho: Promotion and dissemination, good practices exchanging.</p>
Target audience	<p>The target audience are the customers of the following hotels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hotel Marina Atlântico - Azoris Royal Garden - Hotel Talisman
Involvement of the actors	<p>UrBAN-WASTE PPP's signatures;</p> <p>Strategic Communication plan for hotel's customers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informative stickers in the WC's explaining the measure (substitution of the amenities kit by dispensers of shampoo and soap) following a good environmental practices.
Target setting	<p>Measure implementation in three of the majors hotels from Ponta Delgada until 31th May, (14% of the hotels from the Municipality), aiming to reach 5 hotels until 1st June (approximately 25% of the hotels from Ponta Delgada).</p>
Setting up the measures	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meetings monitoring indicator discussing (FRCT and hotels) - Selection of the most ecological products for kits substitutions (hotels) - Contracts review with products suppliers (hotels) - Dissemination and communication materials production (FRCT) <p>Implementation phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kits substitution by dispensers in the hotel's rooms - Measures dissemination aiming to increase the number of adherent hotels (FRCT and hotels) - Visits organizing for implementation phase follow up (FRCT and hotels) <p>Monitoring phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly or monthly visits for indicators collection

	<p>Assessment phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of the indicators and the measure efficiency
Resources available and needed	<p>Human resources (HR):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hotel's staff for kits substitution and dispensers maintenance; - indicators collection (hotels and FRCT) <p>Financial Resources (FR):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication and dissemination materials (FRCT) - Financial resources for kits substitution by dispensers (hotels)
Timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UrBAN-WASTE PPP's signing – 16th March; - Implementation phase: March to April 2018; - Measure monitoring: May to October 2018.
Monitoring	<p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of reviewed contracts/new contracts with products suppliers - Disposable consumption during the measure implementation (kg) - Weight estimation of avoided waste from measure implementation (kg of amenities that would be provided per room) - Actions budget: Balance between the costs of the disposables and the dispensers and products

Measure nº11: Recycling advisors for tourist establishments	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>FRCT : Coordination, Implementation and monitoring;</p> <p>Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada: Operational Coordination, Implementation, management supporting resources, monitoring, promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>MUSAMI: Implementation, promotion, dissemination and monitoring;</p> <p>AHRESP: Promotion and dissemination; restaurant collection.</p>
Target audience	Restaurants from Ponta Delgada Municipality
Involvement of the actors	<p>UrBAN-WASTE PPP's signatures</p> <p>Signature of the protocol from "Programa Parceiros"</p> <p>Seal attribution from "Programa Parceiros"</p> <p>Seal "We join UrBAN-WASTE Project";</p> <p>Institutional publicity in the UrBAN-WASTE, MUSAMI and Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada websites;</p> <p>Free publicity in the WASTEAPP application.</p>
Target setting	<p>Measure implementation in 20 restaurants until 15th June;</p> <p>Measure implementation in more 20 restaurants until 31th October;</p> <p>To reach 15% from all Ponta Delgada restaurants.</p>
Setting up the measures	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Definition of human resources, budgets and methodology needed; Schedule definition; Recycling advisors training (May); Acquisition of support resources for communication and execution phase; Good practices seal production for adherent establishments. <p>Implementation phase:</p> <p>Monitoring phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regular visits to adherent establishments for indicators collection and to follow up the measure implementation. <p>Assessment phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Indicator analysis.
Resources available and needed	<p>Human (HR) and financial resources (FR):</p> <p>HR – 2 recycling advisors teams;</p> <p>FR – Budget for waste bags and communication materials production;</p> <p>The available resources include 1 recycling advisors team and promotional materials from "Programa Parceiros".</p>

<p>Timing</p>	<p>- UrBAN-WASTE PPP's signing – 16th March; Planning – until 30th April; Implementation – from 1st to 31th May (20 restaurants) and 1st June to 31th August (more 20 restaurants); Monitoring – from 15th May to 31 de October.</p>
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p><u>Indicators:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) n.º of adherent restaurants; b) Total n.º of restaurants from Ponta Delgada; c) % of adherent restaurants; d) n.º clients/day; e) n.º of bags (50L) with plastic and metals packages produced/day; f) n.º of bags (50L) with papers produced/day; g) n.º of bags (50L) with glass packages produced/day; h) n.º of bags (50L) with organic waste produced/day. <p>Obs: The e, f ,g ,h indicators will be compared between the first week (without training) and the next weeks (after training).</p>

Measure nº14: Translation and dissemination of waste sorting instructions in other languages	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>FRCT: Coordination, Implementation and e monitoring;</p> <p>Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada: Implementation, promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>Direção Regional do Turismo: Promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>MUSAMI: Promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>AHRESP: Promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>Hotel Marina Atlântico: Implementation, promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>Azoris Royal Garden: Implementation, promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>Hotel Talisman: Implementation, promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>Quinta do Bom Despacho: Promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>ANA - Aeroportos: Implementation, promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>AAFTH: Implementation, promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>ERSARA: Promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>Portos dos Açores: Implementation, promotion and dissemination;</p> <p>SATA Air Açores: Implementation, promotion and dissemination.</p>
Target audience	Foreign tourists
Involvement of the actors	<p>UrBAN-WASTE PPP's signatures;</p> <p>- Dissemination of communication materials with translated instructions in foreign languages of waste sorting in tourist establishments and areas;</p> <p>- Use of containers for waste sorting with translated instructions in Portuguese, English and pictograms.</p>
Target setting	<p>Communication materials disseminations with waste sorting instructions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 adherent establishments until end of May; more 20 adherent establishments from 1st June; <p>Use of Containers for waste sorting in shared areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 adherent establishments until end of May; more 3 20 adherent establishments from 1st June.
Setting up the measures	<p>Planning phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection of the material type, layout production and text in different languages production; - Communication materials production; - Containers for waste sorting purchase or use of informative stickers; <p>Implementation phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distribution of the materials with translated instructions of waste sorting in the establishments; - Materials delivery to tourists by the establishments;

	<p>Monitoring phase: - Weekly or monthly visits in the establishments for indicators collection</p> <p>Assessment phase: - Analysis of the indicators and the measure efficiency</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Financial Resources (FR): - communication materials with translated instructions, stickers (FRCT, Câmara Municipal de Ponta Delgada); - Containers with instructions (adherent establishments).</p>
Timing	<p>- UrBAN-WASTE PPP's signing – 16th March; - Implementation phase: March to April 2018; - Measure monitoring: May to October 2018.</p>
Monitoring	<p>Indicators:</p> <p>- % of establishments using the communication materials; - n^o of materials with translated instructions distributed for customers by the establishments; - Estimation of the number of tourist that received information in the accommodations.</p>

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

DUBROVNIK – NERETVA COUNTY

Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 **DUBROVNIK NERETVA REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT AGENCY DUNE** in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et l'gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNE), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These

strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in **DUBROVNIK NERETVA COUNTY** and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated **MARCH 27TH2018**.

between

DUBROVNIK NERETVA REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT AGENCY DUNEA and ČISTOĆA I ZELENILLO KONA VLE d.o.o.

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's **Measure n. 16 INFORMATION ON WASTE SORTING FOR SHIPS** aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc....] located in **DUBROVNIK NERETVA COUNTY** to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE **Measure n. 16 INFORMATION ON WASTE SORTING FOR SHIPS** in DUBROVNIK NERETVA COUNTY and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

COMMITMENTS OF ČISTOĆA I ZELENILO KONAVLE d.o.o.:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to prepare textual part of flyer in 4 languages (English, Italian, Spanish, German) as information for ships entering Cavtat port, as part of URBAN-WASTE measure campaign in order to achieve clear communication about the waste handling which can increase the amount of waste being recycled from the ships;
- to print out information flyer for ships entering Cavtat port in 8000 copies;
- to distribute information flyer for ships entering Cavtat port in their own capacities (employees of Čistoća i zelenilo Konavle d.o.o. who will within their daily activities and obligations carry out aforementioned)
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on MARCH 27TH 2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on DECEMBER 27TH 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure n. 16 INFORMATION ON WASTE SORTING FOR SHIPS
Purpose, Objectives and Justification	<i>This measure is aimed at raising awareness of visitors on the rules of waste disposal in the given PA. Promotion of waste sorting among the sailing community by providing to the tourists sailing instructions on waste sorting. Ships, yachts arriving in Cavtat port deliver the waste generated on board. Because of lack of space on the ships a lot of effort is put into sorting and compressing the waste on board. When in port the waste is unloaded - and if the waste is sorted in fractions fitting the waste management system of the receiving city - the waste can easily be recycled. Clear communication about the waste handling can increase the amount of waste being recycled from the ships. If the waste is not sorted, but delivered as mixed compressed waste it is most likely that it will be incinerated or landfilled. Communication from the port authority to the ships, about which fractions can be received, is therefore crucial for the waste handling before docking at port.</i>
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<i>Regional Development Agency DUNEA with its project team is in charge for the coordination of the measure implementation and monitoring. All activities will be implemented through collaboration with Konavle Municipality i.e. their company Čistoća i zelenilo Konavle d.o.o. that will print out and distribute project flyers.</i>
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Konavle Municipality local community,</i> - <i>nautical tourists in Konavle, entering Cavtat port.</i>
Involvement of the actors	<i>Flyers will be distributed to nautical tourists upon their arrival in Cavtat port by official employees of Čistoća i zelenilo Konavle d.o.o. which are official waste management company of the area.</i>
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>distribution of 8 000 flyers</i> - <i>n. of nautical tourist reached – depends on the number of boats arrived.</i>
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Layout and print of flyers with instructions for handling waste from ships and yachts.</i> - <i>Distribution of flyers by Čistoća i zelenilo Konavle d.o.o. employees in Cavtat upon connection or entry into Cavtat port.</i>
Resources available and	<i>Konavle Municipality will print out flyers prepared by WP6 coordinator and DUNEA, on their own budget. DUNEA has not any budget foreseen for this activity, all expenditures will be covered by Konavle Municipality.</i>

needed	
Timing	<i>06/2018 – 10/2018 - for one season because nautical tourists arrive in the summer period and will return on June 2019 when project finishes.</i> <i>Layout and print: May 2018</i> <i>First distribution round: June 2018</i> <i>Second distribution round: August 2018</i> <i>Third distribution round: September 2018</i>
Monitoring	<i>n. flyers distributed</i> <i>n of nautical tourist reached</i> <i>is it possible to measure sorted waste collected – No.</i>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 **DUBROVNIK NERETVA REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT AGENCY DUNEA** in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies

will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in **DUBROVNIK NERETVA COUNTY** and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated **MARCH 27TH 2018**.

between

**DUBROVNIK NERETVA REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT AGENCY DUNEA and
ECOLOGICAL ASSOCIATION MALA SIRENA**

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's **Measure n. 19 AWARENESS CAMPAIGN ON MARINE LITTER** aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc....] located in **DUBROVNIK NERETVA COUNTY** to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure Measure n. 19 AWARENESS CAMPAIGN ON MARINE LITTER in DUBROVNIK NERETVA COUNTY and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

COMMITMENTS OF THE ECOLOGICAL ASSOCIATION MALA SIRENA:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide expert support for the implementation of the action;
- to prepare textual part of flyer on marine litter problem awareness raising as part of URBAN-WASTE measure campaign;
- to organize and implement 3 workshops (45 minutes each) on the subject of marine litter (two of them for high school children - maritime high school and tourism oriented high school, and the third one in cooperation with FLAG JUŽNI JADRAN for fishermen);
- to prepare text for short notes for high school students that will be distributed during 2 educational workshops on marine litter problematics in high schools;
- to prepare in total 12 text pages (12 x 1500 characters including space) on marine litter problematics – this includes flyers and short notes for students;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on MARCH 27TH 2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on MAY 27TH 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

Measure n. 19 AWARENESS CAMPAIGN ON MARINE LITTER	
Purpose, Objectives and Justification	<p><i>The worrying amount of marine litter in the marine environment today is one of the fastest growing problems. Waste in the marine environment only comes due to human activity, i.e. disadvantages in the waste management system. Due to significant environmental, economic, safety, health and cultural implications, there is a need to take appropriate measures and find efficient, long-term solutions. The problem of marine litter has been recognized as one of the major threats to marine ecosystems and intensified research. Marine waste is defined as any permanent, manufactured or processed solid material that has no natural origin and has been postponed or abandoned by the marine environment and the coastal area by man. Plastic waste as the most common in nature (as much as 90% of waste that floats in seas is plastic) especially loads the sea because it is highly resistant and degrades extremely slowly. Due to the numerous processes over time, fragmentation of plastic waste into micro particles of small microorganisms, which, by ingestion by marine organisms, are permanently and irreversibly becoming part of the nutritional chain, which ultimately reaches the very man. The largest amount of marine waste in our aquarium is brought by currents from neighbouring countries. The geographic spread of waste at sea bottom strongly influences hydrodynamics, geomorphology and human factor. In shallow coastal areas the amount of marine waste is much higher than on the continental shelf. In coastal areas, activities related to tourism and fisheries contribute significantly to pollution with pronounced weather, especially seasonal fluctuations.</i></p>
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Regional Development Agency DUNEA with its project team is in charge for the coordination of the measure implementation and monitoring.</p> <p>All activities will be implemented through collaboration with environmental NGO Mala Sirena and fisheries local action group FLAG Južni Jadran.</p> <p>As important addition to this measure will be collaboration with another EU project ML-REPAIR (REducing and Preventing, an integrated Approach to Marine Litter Management in the Adriatic Sea) financed from INTERREG Italy – Croatia CBC Programme 2014-2020.</p>
Target audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – high school children (maritime high school and tourism oriented high school) – fishermen – local community – tourists
Involvement of the actors	<p>Dubrovnik Neretva Regional Development Agency DUNEA will coordinate the measure implementation and monitor the results.</p> <p>NGO Mala Sirena will be in charge of organising and implementing 3 workshops on the subject of marine litter. Two of them will be prepared for high school children (maritime high school and tourism oriented high school) and the third one will be</p>

	<p>prepared for fishermen which almost on a daily basis face the problem with marine litter which has become part of their by – catch. FLAG Južni Jadran will be in charge of coordination with fishermen who are interested in collaboration (for now 3 are interested).</p> <p>The main idea developed through ML-REPAIR project is collecting large waste from the sea bottom found in hunting catchments during fishing and its subsequent disposal on the forested areas on the shore is a very simple and also very effective way of involving the fishing sector in seabed cleansing action. Activities are very simple – fishermen expressing the desire for voluntary participation will be required to collect such waste that is found in their nets during normal fishing activities. The waste is then stored on board in the garbage bags purchased by the project and, after joining in the appropriate places on the shore (fishing ports and disembarkation sites) is stored in communal containers (bought by the project) and later disposed of in an environmentally friendly manner. The plan is to collaborate with ML-REPAIR in the following way: ML-REPAIR will set up the containers on 1 location in DNC pilot area – needs to be defined. Through URBAN-WASTE, DUNEA in collaboration with NGO Mala Sirena will implement educational workshop for fishermen on the subject of marine litter and FLAG Južni Jadran will motivate fishermen for their voluntary participation.</p>
Target setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 3 educational workshops on the subject of marine litter; – 2000 flyers distributed on educational workshops and in the cleaning action.
Setting up the measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – educational workshops organized and held; – 3 reports on implemented workshops; – Container in function and set up on the foreseen spot. – Flyers print and distribution through county tourist boards – Flyers distributed on a public event (stand).
Resources available and needed	<p>Resources foreseen will be part of public-private partnership between DUNEA and NGO Mala Sirena. For activities (organization of workshops from Mala Sirena and educational material) DUNEA will pay 6.264,00 HRK (841, 61 EUR).</p>
Timing	<p>03 – 08 /2018 the measures are supposed be scheduled for at least 5-6 months</p> <p>Layout and print of flyers: April 2018 First workshop: April 2018 Second workshop: April 2018 Third workshop: May 2018 Flyers distribution 1st round: June 2018 Flyers distribution 2nd round: July 2018</p>
Monitoring	<p>Quantitative indicators.</p> <p>n. of workshops – 3 n. of workshop participants – 170</p>

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

NICOSIA

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Nicosia Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrmaton Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These

strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva country (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Nicosia Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 3rd May 2018.

between

Nicosia Municipality and

- A. C.A. China Spice Restaurants Ltd, Bamboo restaurant Ledras and Chopsticks Chinese restaurant Galaxias Centre
- B. CK Restaurant System Franchisers Ltd, KFC Ledras
- C. Cyprus Marine Environment Protection Association (CYMEPA)
- D. Cyprus Sustainable Tourism Initiative (CSTI)
- E. Cyprus Tourism Organisation (CTO)
- F. Department of Environment (of the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment)

- G. Family Restaurants Andreou Co Ltd, Mc Donalds Ledras
- H. GGMI LTD, Artisan's Burgerbar Restaurant
- I. Giannakis Aristodemou mourtzis Ltd, Centrum Hotel
- J. Green Dot (Cyprus) Public CO LTD, Collective Compliance System for Packaging and Packaging Waste
- K. ISOTECH LTD
- L. Ocean Basket (Nicosia) Ltd, Ocean Basket restaurant Onasagorou
- M. PHC Franchised Restaurants Public LTD (mother company), Taco Bell restaurant
Avantage B&P Café Restaurants Ltd, Paul restaurant
Hetafre Trading Ltd, Nero Cafe
Catercom Ltd, Sitio restaurant
CU LTD, CU Café Ledras
WOW Burgers Ltd, Burger King restaurant Ledras

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure n. 11 Recycling advisors for tourist establishments, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, environmental consultants etc] located in Nicosia Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure n. 11 Recycling advisors for tourist establishments that are situated in (or near) the pedestrian areas of the walled city and in the commercial area of Nicosia outside the old town (Tripiotis parish) and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization. Moreover, any confidential information must be protected.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF NICOSIA MUNICIPALITY:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide financial support for the implementation of the actions;
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.
- to participate to communication activities and provide guidance to businesses for recycling issues;

- A. COMMITMENTS OF C.A. China Spice Restaurants Ltd:

- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to take part to training activities and seminars of the program that deal with recycling issues.
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

B. COMMITMENTS OF CK Restaurant System Franchisers Ltd:

- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to take part to training activities and seminars of the program that deal with recycling issues.
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

C. COMMITMENTS OF CYPRUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT PROTECTION ASSOCIATION:

- to participate to communication activities and provide guidance to businesses for recycling issues and to distribute communication materials;
- to take part to presentations during training seminars.
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

D. COMMITMENTS OF CYPRUS SUSTAINABLE TOURISM INITIATIVE:

- to take part to presentations during training seminars
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

E. COMMITMENTS OF CYPRUS TOURISM ORGANISATION:

- to participate to communication activities and provide guidance to businesses for recycling issues and to distribute communication materials;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

F. COMMITMENTS OF DEPARTMENT OF ENVIRONMENT:

- to sharing information and provide communication materials to Nicosia Municipality during events;
- to make presentations during training seminars
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

G. COMMITMENTS OF FAMILY RESTAURANTS ANDREOU CO LTD:

- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to take part to training activities and seminars of the program that deal with recycling issues.
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

H. COMMITMENTS OF GGMI LTD:

- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to take part to training activities and seminars of the program that deal with recycling issues.
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

I. COMMITMENTS OF GIANNAKIS ARISTODEMOU MOURTZIS LTD:

- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to take part to training activities and seminars of the program that deal with recycling issues.
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

J. COMMITMENTS OF GREEN DOT (CYPRUS) PUBLIC CO LTD:

- to participate to communication activities and provide guidance to businesses for recycling issues and to distribute communication materials;
- to provide communication material to municipality.
- to take part to presentations during training seminars.
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels.

K. COMMITMENTS OF ISOTECH LTD:

- to participate to communication activities and provide guidance to businesses for recycling issues and to distribute communication materials;
- to take part to presentations during training seminars
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

L. COMMITMENTS OF OCEAN BASKET (NICOSIA) LTD:

- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to take part to training activities and seminars of the program that deal with recycling issues.
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

M. COMMITMENTS OF PHC FRANCHISED RESTAURANTS PUBLIC LTD:

- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to take part to training activities and seminars of the program that deal with recycling issues.
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 3rd of May 2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on 30th of November 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure [no.11 Recycling advisors for tourist establishments]
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Coordinators: Michael Lagos and Maria Thiseos form the Public Health and Hygiene department of Nicosia Municipality. It is their responsibility the a arrangement of regular visits to establishments (hotels and restaurants) for training purposes, the creation of recycling advisors team and a schedule for each visit, the involvement of newly establishments in the training program (hotels, restaurants, any big shops) and mapping of businesses.</p> <p>Furthermore, the organisation of informative and training seminars will take place in cooperation with the European Affairs Office of the municipality (Roulla Thoma or Chryso Katsavra).</p> <p>Each business manager must arrange the implementation and monitor the staff for the application of the recommended actions. Moreover, the business manager will be in contact with a recycling advisor.</p> <p>Green Dot Cyprus as a Collective Packaging and Packaging Waste Management System will provide the existing communication material deals with recycling issues. This material describes the three main categories of recyclables (paper, Plastic Metal and Drinks (PMD) and glass) as well as the collection dates. Additionally, it will provide advice to businesses through participates in regular visits. It will take part in educational seminars in terms of recycling issues.</p> <p>The Department of Environment of the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment will provide communication materials for the training of the businesses during events. Apart from that it will make presentations during training seminars related to the legislative framework in the field of waste management in Cyprus.</p> <p>Both the company Isotech Ltd the Cyprus Marine Environment Protection Association will take part in training seminars by conduction presentations and provide advice to businesses through regular visits.</p> <p>The Cyprus Sustainable Tourism Initiative will take part in presentations during training seminars.</p> <p>Cyprus Tourism Organisation will participate in regular visits especially for hotels.</p>
Target audience	<p>Restaurants and other food businesses (Sitio, Paul, Nero, Ocean Basket, Bamboo, Burger King Ledras, Artisan's Burgerbar, Taco Bell, KFC Ledras, Mc Donalds Ledras, Chopsticks Chinese restaurant Galaxias, CU Cafe and Centrum Hotel that are situated in the pedestrian areas of the walled city and in the commercial area of Nicosia</p>

	<p>outside the old town (Tripiotis parish).</p> <p>At the beginning of the implementation phase will be involved and sign the PPP agreement 13 food businesses mostly restaurants and one Hotel. During the implementation period the number of food businesses will be constantly increased. All the establishments which are situated within the defined area and participate to measure n.20 Food tracking device will be involved in the aforementioned measure too (except Hilton Hotel because it is not in Tripiotis area but slightly further).</p>
Involvement of the actors	<p>Organisations and environmental consulting entities for the provision of advice and consultancy support to the food businesses for recycling issues (Public Health and Hygiene Department of Nicosia Municipality, Collective Compliance System for Packaging and Packaging Waste: Green Dot (Cyprus) Public Co Ltd, Cyprus Tourism Organisation, Cyprus Marine Environment Protection Association, Cyprus Sustainable Tourism Initiative, ISOTECH LTD, Department of Environment.</p> <p>Regular visits to businesses (training, flyers etc). The recycling advisors team will perform visits in the defined area once per week. Thus, four to five days in each month will be dedicated for this purpose. During the visits the team will carry out audits to control that the restaurants follow the recommendations.</p> <p>Provide and promote information material related to recycling issues and collection schedules through door to door visits.</p>
Target setting	<p>At the beginning of the implementation phase will be involved around 13 facilities. Until the end of the implementation phase the number of facilities involved (through regular visits, participate in training seminars and meetings) and received advice will be approximately 50 businesses (in total). At least, will be informed another 37 establishments and 2 among them will sign the agreement and provide quantitative data.</p>
Setting up the measures	<p>Regular visits to businesses.</p> <p>Provision of leaflets and flyers.</p> <p>Organization of training activities, conferences or seminars (two in total, in the middle of the implementation phase). During the second event the results will be communicated in order to involve more businesses.</p> <p>Identification and mapping of establishments that participate and received advices/trained from advisors.</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>The aforementioned companies and environmental consultants will provide voluntary services. However, if during the implementation phase (and based on the evaluation results) the municipality needs to fund an action or sub-action then the cost will be covered by the subcontracting part of the budget (€3000 for hiring an employee on temporary basis for monitoring the actions and represent the municipality during training visits). Moreover, €2500 for the organisation of the two events/seminars (catering etc) and to print communication material.</p>
Timing	<p>From the beginning of May until the 30th of November 2018.</p> <p>Signing the PPP on the 3rd of May.</p> <p>Training course / event in July.</p> <p>Public event in September to communicate the measure results, involve other businesses and provide training.</p> <p>One visit per week in the defined area (5 to 8 businesses each time, at least two visits in each business).</p>

Monitoring	<p>Quantitative indicators: Number of establishments received recycling advice and training (number before/in the middle/after the implementation phase).</p> <p>Number of actions implemented among the business that follow the recommendations.</p> <p>Number of people (mainly food businesses employees) attend the seminars and sign for their participation.</p> <p>Number of businesses sign the PPP at the end of the second seminar/training course as a proof that they got advice.</p> <p>Mapping of establishments received training (name and address).</p>
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Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Nicosia Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These

strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva country (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Nicosia Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 3rd May 2018.

between

Nicosia Municipality and

- A. Cyprus Marine Environment Protection Association (CYMEPA)
- B. Cyprus Sustainable Tourism Initiative (CSTI)
- C. Cyprus Tourism Organisation (CTO)
- D. Department of Environment (of the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment)
- E. Green Dot (Cyprus) Public CO LTD, Collective Compliance System for Packaging and Packaging Waste

F. ISOTECH LTD

G. Nicosia Tourism Board

H. Pancyprian Restaurants & Entertainment Establishments Owners (PASIKA)

I. Philippou Bros Energeia Ltd

J. Union of Cyprus Municipalities

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure n.14 Translation and dissemination of waste sorting instructions in foreign languages, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, environmental consultants etc] located in Nicosia Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure n.14 Translation and dissemination of waste sorting instructions in foreign languages in the old city as well as in the commercial centre of Nicosia and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF NICOSIA MUNICIPALITY:
- to involve the local stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide financial support for the implementation of the actions;

- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.
- to translate the information and design/develop new information material

A. COMMITMENTS OF CYPRUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT PROTECTION ASSOCIATION:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

B. COMMITMENTS OF CYPRUS SUSTAINABLE TOURISM INITIATIVE:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

C. COMMITMENTS OF CYPRUS TOURISM ORGANISATION:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

D. COMMITMENTS OF THE DEPARTMENT OF ENVIRONMENT:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

E. COMMITMENTS OF GREEN DOT (CYPRUS) PUBLIC CO LTD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to provide to the municipality the information material in English
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

E. COMMITMENTS OF ISOTECH LTD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

G. COMMITMENTS OF NICOSIA TOURISM BOARD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

H. COMMITMENTS OF PANCYPRIAN RESTAURANTS & ENTERTAINMENT ESTABLISHMENTS OWNERS:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

I. COMMITMENTS OF PHILIPPOU BROS ENERGEIA LTD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to disseminate/promote the communication material

J. COMMITMENTS OF UNION OF CYPRUS MUNICIPALITIES:

- to disseminate/promote the communication material

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 3rd of May 2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on 30th of November 2018.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure [no.14 Translation and dissemination of waste sorting instructions in foreign languages]
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Coordinators: Michael Lagos and Maria Thiseos from the Public Health and Hygiene department of Nicosia Municipality in cooperation with the European Affairs Office of the municipality (Roulla Thoma or Chryso Katsavra) for the development and promotion of the information material.</p> <p>The coordinators will cooperate with the Collective Packaging and Packaging Waste Management System called Green Dot Cyprus for the translation of new material in English language. Moreover, Green Dot Cyprus will provide the translated material deals with recycling issues in English.</p> <p>The public and private entities (Public Health and Hygiene Department of Nicosia Municipality, Collective System Green Dot Cyprus Ltd, Cyprus Tourism Organisation, Cyprus Marine Environment Protection Association, Cyprus Sustainable Tourism Initiative, ISOTECH LTD, Department of Environment, Union of Cyprus Municipalities, Nicosia Tourism Board, Philippou Bross Energeia, Pancyprian Restaurants & Entertainment Establishments Owners) will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website and their offices.</p>
Target audience	<p>Tourists (foreigners – from abroad especially one day visitors and locals – who live in other cities in Cyprus (internal and international tourism) and those who stay in a hotel.</p> <p>This measure will be implemented in the old city as well as in the commercial centre of Nicosia where there are only hotels. (Note that in the defined area tourists cannot find other accommodation establishments such as vacation houses or flats for rent).</p>
Involvement of the actors	<p>Translation, development and promotion of information material.</p> <p>Organisations and environmental consulting entities for the promotion of the material (Public Health and Hygiene Department of Nicosia Municipality, Collective System Green Dot Cyprus Ltd, Cyprus Tourism Organisation, CYMEPA, Cyprus Sustainable Tourism Initiative, ISOTECH LTD, Department of Environment, Nicosia Tourism Board, Union of Cyprus Municipalities, Philippou Bross Energeia, Pancyprian Restaurants & Entertainment Establishments Owners) through their website and through other relevant organisations they cooperate with.</p> <p>Through this process the distribution points will be gradually increased. For instance, one of the main aims is the involvement of the hotels by providing the aforementioned material through their website and/or the reception desk. Nicosia Municipality will arrange visits to all the hotels of the area for the achievement of this scope.</p>

Target setting	<p>Number of waste instructions disseminated (e.g. flyers, leaflets) to hotels and other entities (more than 200 per month which equals to 800 or 1200 for four or six months implementation, respectively).</p> <p>Number of hotels involved. Our goal is disseminate the information to all the licensed tourist accommodation establishments in the defined area which are eight.</p>
Setting up the measures	<p>Translate and print the communication material.</p> <p>Distribution of communication material to eight hotels, to tourism offices and to public and private organisations.</p> <p>Promoting the instructions through magazine advertising.</p> <p>Promoting the instructions through municipal buses advertising.</p> <p>Promoting the translated information through the WasteApp application.</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Green Dot Cyprus will provide the existing communication material deals with recycling issues.</p> <p>The public and private entities (stakeholders) will provide voluntary services for the promotion of information material mainly through their website.</p> <p>However, the information materials printing, any other additional actions aiming to communicate and share the information with tourists as well as the promotion of communication materials through magazines and buses advertising will be covered by the subcontracting part of the budget (€3500).</p>
Timing	<p>From the beginning of May until the 30th of November 2018.</p> <p>Signing the PPP on the 3rd of May.</p> <p>Distribution of the existent communication materials to stakeholders by 15th of May.</p> <p>Finalisation of the communication materials by 1th of June 2018.</p> <p>Distribution of the new communication materials to stakeholders by 6th of June.</p> <p>Distribution of material in hotels by 15th of June 2018.</p> <p>Promoting the instructions through magazine advertising and municipal buses by the end of July.</p>
Monitoring	<p>Qualitative indicator: Feedback collection by tourist in order to check if they have received the information.</p> <p>Quantitative indicators: Number of waste instructions distributed (number of leaflets given to hotels or to organisations (stakeholders) to promote the information).</p> <p>Number of tourists potentially informed (e.g. number of visits in municipal (or stakeholder's) website).</p> <p>Number of distribution points (points where leaflets given, number of websites that show the information, number of advertisements and press releases).</p> <p>Number/type of actions implemented (total number to be greater than 5) in terms of the promotion of waste instructions (e.g create new communication material, promoting instructions through magazines, introduce new communication channels to communicate the information to tourists etc).</p>

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Nicosia Municipality, in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrmaton Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereia Ipeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT),

Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva country (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Nicosia Municipality and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 3rd May 2018.

between

Nicosia Municipality and

- A. C.A. China Spice Restaurants Ltd, Bamboo restaurant Ledras
- B. Cyprus Tourism Development Public Company Ltd, Hilton Cyprus Hotel
- C. Cyprus Tourism Organisation (CTO)
- D. GGMI LTD, Artisan's Burgerbar Restaurant
- E. ISOTECH LTD
- F. Ocean Basket (Nicosia) Ltd, Ocean Basket restaurant Onasagorou
- G. PHC Franchised Restaurants Public LTD (mother company), Taco Bell restaurant
CU LTD, CU Café Ledras
WOW Burgers Ltd, Burger King restaurant Ledras

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure n. 20 Food tracking device, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, tourism service providers, environmental consultants etc] located in Nicosia Municipality to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure n. 20 Food tracking device in the restaurants Artisan's Burgerbar, Bamboo, Burger King, Ocean Basket, Taco Bell, CU Cafe and in Hilton Cyprus Hotel which are situated in Nicosia Municipality limits and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization. Moreover, any confidential information must be protected (e.g. some waste reduction actions that are implemented in food businesses are considered as confidential).

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF NICOSIA MUNICIPALITY:

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide consultancy support for the implementation of the actions;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

- Involved to the distribution of waste tracker and to personnel training in cooperation with SLU.
- Organization of preliminary audits.
- Determine the possible barriers and constraints in each business.

A. COMMITMENTS OF C.A. CHINA SPICE RESTAURANTS LTD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to monitor the implementation of the actions
- to adopt new food waste reduction actions for systematic improvement
- collection of guest's number data and / or served portion data during the implementation phase
- collection of food waste data (kg) during the implementation phase
- to use the waste tracker and fill in the relevant database

B. COMMITMENTS OF CYPRUS TOURISM DEVELOPMENT PUBLIC COMPANY LTD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to monitor the implementation of the actions
- to adopt new food waste reduction actions for systematic improvement
- collection of guest's number data and / or served portion data during the implementation phase
- collection of food waste data (kg) during the implementation phase
- to use the waste tracker and fill in the relevant database

C. COMMITMENTS OF CYPRUS TOURISM ORGANISATION:

- to provide consultancy support for the implementation of the actions;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

D. COMMITMENTS OF GGMI LTD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to monitor the implementation of the actions
- to adopt new food waste reduction actions for systematic improvement
- collection of guest's number data and / or served portion data during the implementation phase
- collection of food waste data (kg) during the implementation phase
- to use the waste tracker and fill in the relevant database

E. COMMITMENTS OF THE ISOTECH LTD:

- to provide consultancy support for the implementation of the actions;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;

F. COMMITMENTS OF OCEAN BASKET (NICOSIA) LTD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to monitor the implementation of the actions
- to adopt new food waste reduction actions for systematic improvement
- collection of guest's number data and / or served portion data during the implementation phase
- collection of food waste data (kg) during the implementation phase
- to use the waste tracker and fill in the relevant database

G. COMMITMENTS OF PHC FRANCHISED RESTAURANTS PUBLIC LTD:

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels;
- to monitor the implementation of the actions
- to adopt new food waste reduction actions for systematic improvement

- collection of guest's number data and / or served portion data during the implementation phase
- collection of food waste data (kg) during the implementation phase
- to use the waste tracker and fill in the relevant database

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent (between the municipality and a specific stakeholder). It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 3rd of May 2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on 30th of November 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure [no.20 Food tracking device]
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>Coordinators: Michael Lagos and Maria Theseos from the Public Health and Hygiene department of Nicosia Municipality.</p> <p>The technical consultant Mr Mattias Eriksson from SLU will introduce the food waste tracker to the food businesses as well as he will provide technical support throughout the implementation of the measure.</p> <p>Cyprus Tourism Organisation personnel will participate and contribute in this measure at working hours during the execution of their inspections. ISOTECH LTD may combine the visits to food business along with the execution of tasks relating to other entertainment establishments issues (such as noise management).</p> <p>Each business or kitchen manager must monitor the implementation of the actions and adding new waste reduction actions for systematic improvement.</p>
Target audience	<p>Target A: 1) <u>One hotel</u>: Hilton Cyprus Hotel for the reduction of food waste at buffet. 2) <u>Five restaurants</u>: Artisan's Burgerbar, Bamboo, Burger King, Ocean Basket, Taco Bell restaurant. 3) <u>One café</u>: CU Cafe to reduce kitchen food waste. These food businesses are situated in the pedestrian areas of the walled city and in the commercial area of Nicosia outside the old town.</p> <p>Target B: Obtain a commitment from another (2 to 4) facilities by the end of the implementation phase by showing them the results reached by the other facilities.</p>
Involvement of the actors	<p>Inspectors from Cyprus Tourism Organisation and environmental consultants from the firm ISOTECH LTD to provide guidance and consultancy support to the food businesses for further food waste reduction during the implementation phase.</p> <p>Organisation of training/event showing the first results achieved by the 7 facilities. The events will be taking place in conjunction with the training seminars of the measure no.11 (Recycling advisors for tourist establishments).</p>
Target setting	<p>Totally, they will be involved five restaurants, one cafe and one hotel. We will involve 2 to 4 more food businesses in this measure during the implementation period that will sign the commitment.</p> <p>The evaluation of avoided production of food waste. Each food business will be handled separately and evaluated as a unit. Quantity of food waste per day/week. Quantity of food waste per served portion (or number of customers served per day/week). It will be adjusted according to each restaurant special characteristics</p>

	and needs (food waste reduction 5 to 15% because they already adopt some relevant actions).
Setting up the measures	<p>Distribution of waste tracker (a scale to store data in a database) to food businesses to quantify food waste and interpret the collected waste data.</p> <p>Personnel training by SLU for the proper use of the device and how to use the general statistics results for further improvement to contribute to less waste generation.</p> <p>Organisation of preliminary audits.</p> <p>Determine any possible barriers and constraints in each business.</p> <p>Distribution of doggy bags and information material.</p>
Resources available and needed	<p>Doggy bags, bins, plastic bags and to print communication material stickers, window films, promo cards etc €2000.</p> <p>In case of any additional actions or needs, the cost will be covered by the subcontracting part of the project budget.</p>
Timing	<p>Upon the entire application will be installed by SLU (probably from the beginning of May until the 30th of November 2018).</p> <p>Signing the PPP on the 3rd of May.</p> <p>Installation of weighting scale by SLU by the 15th of May (maybe).</p> <p>Visits to establishments involved once per month.</p> <p>Events showing results reached in July and September.</p> <p>Involve more businesses by the end of September. During the event in September will sign the agreement.</p>
Monitoring	<p>A different monitoring procedure will be agreed for each restaurant.</p> <p>Qualitative indicators: Kind of new actions (and number) and how implemented in each business (during the implementation of the measure) to facilitate a continuous improvement (e.g. doggy bags).</p> <p>Quantitative indicators: Will be collected during all the implementation phase in relation to the quantity of food waste generated (kg) by using weight scales.</p> <p>Moreover, guest's number data will be collected or/and number of served portion or dishes (kg).</p> <p>Number of doggy bags distributed and when (if it is applicable).</p> <p>Kg of organic waste avoided to produce from a hotel buffet or restaurants kitchen based on the previous year weighted data (if it is applicable).</p> <p>Food waste reduction 5 to 15% in each establishment.</p>

Commitment

The E.I MR. COFFEE agrees,

- to participate in the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure n. 11 Recycling advisors for tourist establishments.
- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices;
- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 24 of 9 / 2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on **30th of November 2018**.

I, the undersigned, declare that I have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

E.I MR. COFFEE

Name of the legal representative

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Commitment

The ΚΕΝΤΡΟ ΕΚΦΡΑΣΗΣ ΠΑΡ. CONST/NOU LTA agrees,

- to participate in the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure n. 11 Recycling advisors for tourist establishments.
- to implement food waste/packaging reduction measures;
- to implement waste sorting actions and participate in the recycling program;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices;
- to arrange the implementation of the recommended actions;
- to be in touch with a recycling advisor;
- to complete the relevant database and send to the municipality quantitative/waste data, when it is required.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 23 of 09... 2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on **30th of November 2018**.

I, the undersigned, declare that I have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

POLYCHOROS RESTAURANT

Name of the legal representative

Omitted for GDPR compliance reasons

Public-Private Partnerships and Operative Plans

KAVALA

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the AnaptixiakiAnonimiEtairiaDiachirisisAporrimatonAnotilikisMakedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), AnaptixiakiAnonimiEtairiaDiachirisisAporrimatonAnotilikisMakedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extra hotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Periferieialpeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further

support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Kavala and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated _____ ,

between

subscriber A: AnaptixiakiAnonimiEtairiaDiachirisisAporrimatonAnotilikisMakedonias-Thrakis

AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), and

[theSubscriber B]: Port of Kavala

[the Subscriber C]: Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development

[the Subscriber D]: Municipality of Kavala

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure 12, "Sorting Bins in public and touristic places", aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located

in Kavala to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree, to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure 12, “Sorting Bins in public and touristic places”, in Kavala and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure’s implementation; to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE [subscriber A]: Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH),
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
 - to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
 - to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
 - to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber B: Port of Kavala

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
- to provide financial support for the implementation of the actions;
- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization and coastal zone of Kavala;
- to promote the implementation of the measure to other stakeholders and increase awareness;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber C: Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development

- to involve the local stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber D: Municipality of Kavala

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my city;
- to promote the implementation of the measure to other stakeholders and increase awareness;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on 31 December 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

Subscriber A

Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias - Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH)

Name of the legal representative

.....

Date and Place

Kavala.....05.2018

Signature

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

Measure n. 12 Sorting bins in public and touristic places	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>The person in charge of the measure’s implementation and monitoring (coordinator): Dr. P. Giourka, DIAAMATH S.A.,</p> <p>The most important stakeholders that need to be involved in the implementation of the measure in order to get organisational and, if possible, financial support (i.e. category associations, charity associations, public or private actors, like waste management company or water network management company):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality of Kavala <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Role of the stakeholder: Disseminate the benefits of the applied measure to citizens and support the implementation of the measure • Port of Kavala, President <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Role of the stakeholder: Key actor for financing and implementing the measure, • Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development, President of the Board of Directors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Role of the stakeholder: Disseminate the application of the measures to tourists.
Target audience	<p>The category of tourist service providers this operative plan addresses are mainly public organisations and specifically the Port of Kavala. The Port of Kavala has expressed its interest to join the URBAN WASTE project and provide sorting bins in the mainland zone managed by the Port of Kavala.</p> <p>The kind of tourist the measures are targeting, in order to arrange the appropriate communication approach and materials are:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • foreign/local • young people/families/elderly
Involvement of the actors	<p>The target audience shall be involved through the following actions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organisation of a pre-agreement meeting where the: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. operative plan will be analysed and explained to the Managing Director of the Port of Kavala b. Communication and awareness raising material will be presented c. Promotion campaign through URBAN WASTE communication channels will be explained <p>Sign a commonly agreed cooperation agreement at a public event on April 2018</p> <p>Organisation of a final event/informative initiative for involving other public stakeholders showing the reached results in order to enhance the impact of the project</p>
Target setting	<p>Targets to be achieved during the implementation phase of the measure (it is important to discuss and agree them with all the stakeholders and actors involved in the process):</p> <p>The Port of Kavaala will install 25 bins for sorting paper+plastic+metal (all together) next to the unsorted bins already installed at the mainland zone managed by the Port.</p> <p>The port is a attracting many tourists especially during summer. The average weight of the bag of the new bins will be calculated and multiplied by the number of bags collected per day to reach an estimation of how many kg of sorted waste is produced after the installation of the bins.</p>

<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>The operative steps foreseen to set up the measures and to achieve the defined targets are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of a workshop with the Port of Kavala to finalise the specific targets and monitoring metrics • Organisation of a Public Event for the signing of the Agreement on 19 April 2018 in Kavala • DIAAMATH in cooperation with the Lead Partner will provide customised communication material • DIAAMATH will distribute the material to the Port of Kavala. • Organization of preliminary audits: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st audit will take place before the start date of the implementation of the measure • 2nd audit will take place the first week of the implementation of the measure • 3rd audit will take place one the last week of the implementation of the measure • Organisation of a final event/informative initiative for involving new restaurants showing the reached results
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p>25 new bins for waste sorting collection of metal, plastic, paper and glass (blue bin) will be installed in the port area of Kavala (about 25,000 m²), supported by a massive communication campaign about waste separated collection and waste reduction (4 Big promo posters, 10 A3 posters, 40 Promocards, 60 Leaflets)</p>
<p>Timing</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organization of a public initiative/launch event - will be during the 4th CoP event: April 2018 2. Start-up phase (about 1 month): final design and print of promo materials: May 2018 3. Full implementation phase involving all the selected tourist facilities and targeting the different tourist categories with dedicated communication activities which will last for, at least, 5 months: June-October 2018 4. Organisation of a final event/informative initiative for involving

	new restaurants showing the reached results: October 2018
Monitoring	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sorting bins installed in public spaces (multiple: paper+plastic+unsorted): 50 2. Area of the city covered by the sorting bins installed:....km 3. Average number of daily emptying: Once a day 4. kg of sorted waste

Public-Private Partnership for the implementation of the URBAN-WASTE measures

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the AnaptixiakiAnonimiEtairiaDiachirisisAporrimatonAnotilikisMakedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), TechnischeUniversiteitDelft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et lagestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität FürBodenkulturWien (BOKU), KobenhavnsKommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), AnaptixiakiAnonimiEtairiaDiachirisisAporrimatonAnotilikisMakedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), KobenhavnsUniversitet (UCPH), ObservatoireRégional Des DéchetsD'île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), SverigesLantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agenced'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), AsociacionHotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Perifereialpeiroy (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo ZaRegionalniRazvoj I PoslovneUsluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further

support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Kavala and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated _____ ,

between

subscriber A: Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias -

Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), and

[theSubscriber B]: Association of Kavala Hotels

[the Subscriber C]: Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development

[the Subscriber D]: Municipality of Kavala

[the Subscriber E]: Hotel **"LUCY"**

[the Subscriber F]: Hotel **"GIANNIS"**

[the Subscriber G]: Hotel **"AIROTEL GALAXY"**

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure 2, "Food prevention at buffets and restaurants", aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Kavala to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure Measure 2, "Food prevention at buffets and restaurants", in Kavala and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure's implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE [subscriber A]: Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimation Anotilikis Makedonias - Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH),
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
 - to implement measures improving to the sorted waste collection in my activity/organization;
 - to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;

- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber B: Association of Kavala Hotels

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to implement food waste reduction measures in association members;
- to promote the implementation of the measure to other stakeholders and increase awareness;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber C: Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development

- to involve the local stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber D: Municipality of Kavala

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to promote the implementation of the measure to other stakeholders and increase awareness;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

Term

This voluntary agreement is at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on 31 December 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

Measure n. 2 Food prevention at buffets and restaurants	
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>The person in charge of the measure’s implementation and monitoring (coordinator): Dr. P. Giourka, DIAAMATH S.A.</p> <p>The most important stakeholders that need to be involved in the implementation of the measure in order to get organisational and, if possible, financial support (i.e. category associations, charity associations, public or private actors, like waste management company or water network management company):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hotel Association <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the stakeholder: Disseminate the opportunity to join URBAN WASTE to all hotels in the city of Kavala • Municipality of Kavala <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the stakeholder: Disseminate the benefits of the applied measure to citizens and support the implementation of the measure • Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development, President of the Board of Directors, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the stakeholder: Disseminate the application of the measures to tourists
Target audience	<p>The category of tourist service providers this operative plan addresses mainly hotels in the city center and in close proximity to the city center.</p> <p>The kind of tourist the measure is targeting, in order to arrange the appropriate communication approach and materials are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • foreign/local • young people/families/elderly
Involvement of	The target audience shall be involved through the following actions:

<p>the actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of an informative initiative took place the 21st February 2018 where the operative plan was explained and the collection of expression of interest from the restaurant owners was recorded • Communication and awareness raising through the association of hotels • Promotion campaign through URBAN WASTE communication materials • Sign a commonly agreed cooperation agreement at a public event on April 2018 • Engage more hotels during the public event • Hotel Association will send an invitation inviting more restaurants to take part in the initiative • Organisation of a final Event for presenting the results of measures implemented and adding new hotels to the initiative.
<p>Target setting</p>	<p>Targets to be achieved during the implementation phase of the measure (it is important to discuss and agree them with all the stakeholders and actors involved in the process):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of hotels involved: 3 • total number of hotels in Kavala: 8 • Percentage of hotels involved: 37.5 • No. of Communication /signs in the buffet • tourists (citizens) reached by communication initiative: At least 200 tourists reached in the first two months of measures application and a total of 500 tourists until the end of project implementation • kg of avoided production of waste: kg of organic waste – also if it's only an estimation, try to calculate the quantity of food waste avoided

<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>The operative steps foreseen to set up the measures and to achieve the defined targets are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of a workshop with hotel owners to finalise the specific targets and monitoring metrics • Organisation of a Public Event for the signing of the Agreement on 19 April 2018 in Kavala • Organization of a training activity to Hotels, along with signing of the agreement on the 19 April 2018 in Kavala • Setting up of help-desk activities: participants will have a contact point for any questions or issues raised. The contact point is Dr.Paraskevi Giourka, coordinator of the action. • DIAAMATH in cooperation with the Lead Partner will provide customised communication material • DIAAMATH will distribute the material to the involved hotels. • Organization of preliminary audits: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st audit will take place before the start date of the implementation of the measure • 2nd audit will take place the first week of the implementation of the measure • 3rd audit will take place one the last week of the implementation of the measure • Organisation of a final event/informative initiative for involving new restaurants showing the reached results
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p>Communication material to be distributed: 15 window films, 200 table tabs, 80 promocard, 20 posters together with a standard form for recording results. Support will be provided during the implementation phase for assisting the hotels record food waste produced from buffets.</p>
<p>Timing</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organization of a public initiative/launch event - will be during the 4th CoP event: April 2018 2. Start-up phase (about 1 month): final design of materials, organisation of training activities and (if needed) testing of the actions foreseen within a sample of tourist facilities: May 2018 3. Full implementation phase involving all the selected tourist facilities and targeting the different tourist categories with dedicated communication activities which will last for, at least,

	<p>5 months: June-October 2018</p> <p>4. Organisation of a final event/informative initiative for involving new restaurants showing the reached results: October 2018</p>
Monitoring	<p>"Sample" waste production monitoring (3 weeks: 21 days)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • kg of avoided production of waste: kg of organic waste

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UrBAN-WASTE background

UrBAN-WASTE is a European project funded under the Horizon2020 Programme that aims at supporting policy makers in answering the challenges presented by tourism in terms of waste production and management. The minimization of waste production is an important component for the qualification of the touristic offer and the promotion of smart and sustainable growth in European touristic cities. However, tourist flows bring a range of negative externalities and tourist cities have to face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flow and their specificity.

Considering that:

On June 2016 the Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), in cooperation with 27 partners [Government of Canary Islands (project coordinator), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Københavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), Københavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociación Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Περιφέρεια Ιπείρου (EPI), Fondo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Lefkosia Municipality (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] have started the implementation of the URBAN WASTE project.

The aims and actions of the UrBAN-WASTE project are:

1. To develop novel eco-innovative and gender-sensitive strategies and good practices that aim at reducing the amount of municipal waste production and at further

support the re-use, recycle, collection and disposal of waste in tourist cities. These strategies will be implemented in 11 pilot cases [Florence (IT), Nice (FR), Lisbon (PT), Syracuse (IT), Copenhagen (DK), Kavala (GR), Santander (ES), Nicosia (CY), Ponta Delgada (PT), Dubrovnik – Neretva county (HR), Tenerife (ES)] and the results will be monitored and disseminated facilitating the transfer and adaptation of the project outcomes in other cases.

2. Organize the local stakeholders in a committee, called Community of Practice (CoP), through a participatory process to involve different stakeholders, which will include a balance of women and men from the tourism industry, waste authorities, NGOs, etc., in the design of the waste prevention and management strategies. The CoP chooses the measures to be implemented in Kavala and defines the Operative Plan for each measure to implement.
3. Ensure that every measure is implemented from local, private and/or public stakeholders, that, by signing the following commitments, agree upon implementing voluntary actions aiming to reduce waste production and promoting the UrBAN-WASTE project through the organization of dedicated communication activities.

A voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of UrBAN-WASTE project's measures dated 16.05.2018 ,

between

subscriber A: Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakias AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH), and

[the Subscriber B]: Association of Kavala Restaurants

[the Subscriber C]: Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development

[the Subscriber D]: Municipality of Kavala

[the Subscriber E]: Restaurant "CAMPING ALEXANDROS"

[the Subscriber F]: Restaurant "ΤΟ ΠΑΡΑΛΙΑΚΟΝ"

[the Subscriber G]: Restaurant "Ο ΝΑΥΤΗΣ"

[the Subscriber H]: Restaurant "ΚΥΝΗΓΟΣ"

[the Subscriber I]: Restaurant “KYPA BAΓΓΕΛΙΩ”

[the Subscriber J]: Restaurant “TA BAPEΛIA”

[the Subscriber K]: Restaurant “ΨΑΡΑΚΙ OYZO BAR”

On the aforementioned date, it is subscribed the present voluntary agreement for promoting the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE Project's Measure 1, “Doggy Bag” and Measure 20, “Food Tracking Device”, aimed in particular to involve the local stakeholders [public bodies, waste management companies, tourism service providers, local NGOs, etc...] located in Kavala to apply specific actions to reduce waste production and to improve waste management practices.

Commitment

The parties therefore agree,

to support the implementation of the UrBAN-WASTE measure 1, “Doggy Bag” and Measure 20, “Food Tracking Device”, in Kavala and to take part in the local Community of Practice, that will enhance the measure’s implementation;

to acknowledge the actions to implement, the role and the tasks that are defined in the Operative Plan reported in *Annex I*, and that the signatories of this voluntary agreement undertake to respect and to implement the commitments provided for their own organization, finding them coherent with the respective institutional or commercial mission.

By signing the present voluntary agreement, the parties assume the following commitments that will be better described and specified in the Operative Plan:

- COMMITMENTS OF THE [subscriber A]: Anaptixiaki Anonimi Etairia Diachirisis Aporrimatou Anotilikis Makedonias-Thrakis AE - Diaamath (DIAAMATH),
 - to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
 - to provide technical support for the implementation of the actions;
 - to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;

- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber B: Association of Kavala Restaurants

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to organize communication activities and to distribute communication materials;
- to implement food waste reduction measures in association members;
- to promote the implementation of the measure to other stakeholders and increase awareness;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber C: Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development

- to involve the local stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to organize communication activities and support the production and dissemination of communication materials;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber D:Municipality of Kavala

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to organize communication activities and to support the production and distribution of communication materials;
- to promote the implementation of the measure to other stakeholders and increase awareness;
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;
- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

COMMITMENTS OF THE subscriber E, F, G, H, I, J, K, L :

- to involve the local activities/stakeholders in the implementation of the measure;
- to promote communication materials;
- to promote the implementation of the measure to other stakeholders and increase awareness;
- to implement the measure for reducing waste
- to monitor and record the results of implementation
- to be inclusive of women and men in practices at all levels, including professional, community, and stakeholder;
- to be aware of the impact of all measures on existing gender disadvantages, and seeking to use the measures to reduce disadvantage;

- to promoting gender sensitive communication through eliminating gender stereotypes and using multidimensional representations of women and men.

Term

This voluntary agreements at-will and may be modified by mutual consent. It shall become effective upon signature by the authorized officials from the UrBAN-WASTE project partners on 16.05.2018 and will remain in effect until modified or terminated by any one of the partners by mutual consent. Otherwise, this agreement shall end on 31 December 2018.

We, the undersigned, declare that we have read and accepted the terms and conditions of this contract as described here before.

ANNEX I. Operative Plan

Implementation of the demonstrative waste prevention and management measures

	Measure n. 1 (Doggy bags) and 20 (FTD)
Managing team: roles and responsibilities	<p>The person in charge of the measure’s implementation and monitoring (coordinator): Dr. P. Giourka, DIAAMATH S.A.,</p> <p>The most important stakeholders that need to be involved in the implementation of the measure in order to get organisational and, if possible, financial support (i.e. category associations, charity associations, public or private actors, like waste management company or water network management company):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restaurant Association <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the stakeholder: Disseminate the opportunity to join URBAN WASTE to all hotels in the city of Kavala <p>Municipality of Kavala,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the stakeholder: Disseminate the benefits of the applied measure to citizens and support the implementation of the measure <p>Dimofeleia, Public Benefit Organisation for Tourism Development, President of the Board of Directors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the stakeholder: Disseminate the application of the measures to tourists <p>Regional Government of East Macedonia and Thrace, Mr Chizaris Dimitris, Public Health Surveillance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of the stakeholder: Advice on the guidelines for the promo material especially regarding health and safety issues.
Target audience	<p>The measure is addressed to Restaurants in order to minimise food waste by means of the use of the Doggy bags and monitoring the food waste (FTD). These restaurants are mainly located in the Municipality of Kavala.</p> <p>The kind of tourist the measures are targeting, in order to arrange the appropriate communication approach and materials are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foreign/local

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young people/families/elderly
Involvement of the actors	<p>The target audience shall be involved through the following actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of an informative initiative took place the 21st February 2018 where the operative plan was explained and the collection of expression of interest from the restaurant owners was recorded • Communication and awareness raising through the association of restaurants • Promotion campaign through URBAN WASTE communication materials • Sign a commonly agreed agreement of cooperation at public event • Engage more restaurants during the public event • Restaurant Associations will send an invitation inviting more restaurants to take part in the initiative
Target setting	<p>Targets to be achieved during the implementation phase of the measure (it is important to discuss and agree them with all the stakeholders and actors involved in the process):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restaurants involved: at least 10 restaurants at the initiation phase and involve at least 10 more until the end of project implementation - All restaurants will use the Food Tracking device. Total number of restaurants in the pilot area: 70 Percentage of restaurants involved until the end of the project: 28 % • number of doggy bags distributed i.e 10 doggy bags * 10 restaurants * 21 days = 2100 • tourists (citizens) reached by communication initiative: at least 1000 citizens will be reached by the initiative • kg of avoided production of waste (kg of organic waste) (multiply the capacity (in kg – an average) of a doggy bag for the number of doggy bags distributed)

<p>Setting up the measures</p>	<p>The operative steps foreseen to set up the measures and to achieve the defined targets are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organisation of a Public Event for the signing of the Agreement on 19 April 2018 in Kavala ● organization of a training activity to restaurants on 19 April 2018 in Kavala ● setting up of help-desk activities: participants will have a contact point for any questions or issues raised. The contact point is Dr. Paraskevi Giourka, coordinator of the action. ● DIAAMATH in cooperation with the Lead Partner will provide customised communication material ● DIAAMATH will distribute the material to the involved restaurants. ● organization of preliminary audits: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1st audit will take place before the start date of the implementation of the measure ● 2nd audit will take place the first week of the implementation of the measure ● 3rd audit will take place one the last week of the implementation of the measure ● Organisation of a final event/informative initiative for involving new restaurants showing the reached results.
<p>Resources available and needed</p>	<p>Promotional Material includes: 7 window films, 250 table tabs, 80 promocards, 20 A3 Posters. 5000 Doggy bags will be distributed to 5 restaurants (Camping Alexandros, O Naftis, Ta Varellaia, Psaraki Ouzo Bar, To Paraliakon), in October 2018.</p>
<p>Timing</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organization of a public initiative/launch event - will be during the 4th CoP event: April 2018 2. Start-up phase (about 1 month): final design of materials, organisation of training activities and (if needed) testing of the actions foreseen within a sample of tourist facilities: May 2018 3. Full implementation phase involving all the selected tourist facilities and targeting the different tourist categories with dedicated communication activities which will last for, at least, 5 months: June-October 2018 4. Organisation of a final event/informative initiative for involving new restaurants showing the reached results: October 2018
<p>Monitoring</p>	<p>1. Monitoring of actions, items, stakeholders and people involved</p>

	<p>etc. total</p> <p>Doggy bags “3” printed and distributed to restaurants: 2100</p> <p>Number of Table Tabs:</p> <p>1:xx, 2:xx, 3:xx, 4:xx, 5:xx, 6:xx, 7:xx, 8:xx, 9:xx, 10:xx</p> <p>Total =</p> <p>Number of Window Films: 30</p> <p>Average weight of the food contained by the doggy bag: kg</p> <p>2. Waste production monitoring: general information</p> <p>bin (collecting organic waste) capacity liter bin (collecting unsorted waste) capacity liter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • plastic waste collected (weighted) • paper waste collected (weighted)
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Σύμπραξη Δημοσίου-Ιδιωτικού τομέα για την υλοποίηση των μέτρων του έργου URBAN-WASTE

Περιεχόμενα

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πιλοτικές περιπτώσεις: Φλωρεντία (Ιταλία), Νίκαια (Γαλλία), Λισαβόνα (Πορτογαλία.), Συρακούσες (Ιταλία), Κοπεγχάγη (Δανία), Καβάλα (Ελλάδα), Σανταντέρ (Ισπανία), Λευκωσία (Κύπρος), Πόντα Ντελγάδα (Πορτογαλία), Ντουμπρόβνικ - Νερέτβα (Κροατία), Τενερίφη (Ισπανία) και τα αποτελέσματα θα παρακολουθούνται και θα διαδίδονται διευκολύνοντας τη μεταφορά και προσαρμογή των αποτελεσμάτων του έργου και σε άλλες περιπτώσεις.

2. Η οργάνωση των τοπικών ενδιαφερομένων σε μια επιτροπή που θα ονομάζεται Κοινότητα Πρακτικής (CoP), μέσω μιας συμμετοχικής διαδικασίας για την εμπλοκή διαφόρων ενδιαφερομένων, η οποία θα περιλαμβάνει ίδιο αριθμό γυναικών και ανδρών από την τουριστική βιομηχανία, τις αρχές απορριμμάτων, τις ΜΚΟ κλπ., για το σχεδιασμό των στρατηγικών πρόληψης και διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων. Η Κοινότητα Πρακτικής (CoP) επιλέγει τα μέτρα που πρέπει να εφαρμοστούν στην Καβάλα και καθορίζει το επιχειρησιακό σχέδιο για την εφαρμογή κάθε μέτρου.
3. Διασφάλιση κάθε μέτρου που εφαρμόζεται από τοπικούς, ιδιωτικούς ή / και δημόσιους φορείς, οι οποίοι, υπογράφοντας τις ακόλουθες δεσμεύσεις, συμφωνούν στην υλοποίηση εθελοντικών δράσεων με στόχο τη μείωση της παραγωγής απορριμμάτων και την προώθηση του έργου UrBAN-WASTE, μέσω της διοργάνωσης ειδικών δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας.

Μια εθελοντική συμφωνία για την προώθηση της υλοποίησης των μέτρων του έργου UrBAN-WASTE με ημερομηνία...../...../2018.

μεταξύ των:

Συμμετέχων Α: Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρεία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας-Θράκης ΑΑΕ - ΔΙ.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. Α.Α.Ε, και

Συμμετέχων Β: Σύνδεσμος Ξενοδόχων Καβάλας

Συμμετέχων Γ: ΔΗΜΩΦΕΛΕΙΑ, Δημοτική Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση Καβάλας

Συμμετέχων Δ: Δήμος Καβάλας

Συμμετέχων Ε: Ξενοδοχείο "LUCY"

Συμμετέχων Ζ: Ξενοδοχείο "ΓΙΑΝΝΗΣ"

Συμμετέχων Η: Ξενοδοχείο "AIROTEL GALAXY"

Την προαναφερθείσα ημερομηνία, συνυπογράφηκε η παρούσα εθελοντική συμφωνία για την προώθηση της υλοποίησης του **Μέτρου 2** του έργου UrBAN-WASTE, "**Πρόληψη απορριμμάτων τροφίμων σε μπουφέδες και εστιατόρια**", με στόχο ιδίως τη συμμετοχή των τοπικών φορέων [δημόσιοι φορείς, εταιρείες διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων, πάροχοι

τουριστικών υπηρεσιών, τοπικές ΜΚΟ κλπ. ...] που βρίσκονται στην Καβάλα, ώστε να εφαρμόσουν συγκεκριμένες δράσεις για τη μείωση της παραγωγής απορριμμάτων και για τη βελτίωση των πρακτικών διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων.

Υποχρεώσεις

Συνεπώς τα συμβαλλόμενα μέρη συμφωνούν,

- να υποστηρίξουν την υλοποίηση του **Μέτρου 2, “Πρόληψη απορριμμάτων τροφίμων σε μπουφέδες και εστιατόρια”** του έργου UrBAN-WASTE στην Καβάλα και να συμμετάσχουν στην τοπική Κοινότητα Πρακτικής, η οποία θα ενισχύσει την υλοποίηση αυτού
- να αναγνωρίσουν τις ενέργειες που πρέπει να υλοποιηθούν, τον ρόλο και τα καθήκοντα που ορίζονται στο Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο που αναφέρεται στο *Παράρτημα Ι* και ότι οι συμβαλλόμενοι αυτής της εθελοντικής συμφωνίας δεσμεύονται να τηρούν και να υλοποιούν τις δεσμεύσεις που έχουν αναλάβει για τον δικό τους οργανισμό, θεωρώντας ότι όλα τα προαναφερθέντα συνάδουν με την αντίστοιχη θεσμική ή εμπορική αποστολή τους.

Με τη υπογραφή της παρούσας εθελοντικής συμφωνίας, τα συμβαλλόμενα μέρη αναλαμβάνουν τις ακόλουθες δεσμεύσεις οι οποίες θα περιγραφούν και θα διευκρινιστούν λεπτομερέστερα στο Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο:

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Α: Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας-Θράκης Α.Α.Ε. - Δι.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. Α.Α.Ε

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παροχή τεχνικής υποστήριξης για την υλοποίηση των δράσεων,
- διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Β: Σύνδεσμος Ξενοδόχων Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παροχή τεχνικής υποστήριξης για την εφαρμογή των μέτρων;
- συμμετοχή σε δραστηριότητες επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- προώθηση της υλοποίησης του μέτρου σε άλλα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Γ: ΔΗΜΩΦΕΛΕΙΑ, Δημοτική Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- παραγωγή (εκτύπωση) προωθητικού υλικού επικοινωνίας, δαπάνες διαφήμισης και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Δ: Δήμος Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού που αφορά τα μέτρα υλοποίησης,
- διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,

- προώθηση της υλοποίησης του μέτρου σε άλλα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Ε: Ξενοδοχείο LUCY,

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερομένων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παροχή τεχνικής υποστήριξης για την εφαρμογή των μέτρων;
- συμμετοχή σε δραστηριότητες επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- υλοποίηση μέτρων για τη μείωση των απορριμμάτων τροφίμων στον οργανισμό μου,
- παρακολούθηση και αποτύπωση των αποτελεσμάτων της εφαρμογής του μέτρου
- προώθηση της υλοποίησης του μέτρου σε άλλα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

Όροι

Η παρούσα εθελοντική συμφωνία είναι κατά βούληση και μπορεί να τροποποιηθεί μετά από αμοιβαία συναίνεση. Ισχύει με την υπογραφή των νομίμων εκπροσώπων των φορέων που συμμετέχουν και από τους εταίρους του έργου UrBAN-WASTE και θα παραμείνει σε

ισχύ έως ότου τροποποιηθεί ή τερματιστεί από οποιονδήποτε τους εταίρο μετά από κοινή συναίνεση. Διαφορετικά, η συμφωνία αυτή λήγει στις 31 Δεκεμβρίου 2018.

Εμείς, οι υπογράφοντες, δηλώνουμε ότι έχουμε διαβάσει και αποδεχτεί τους όρους και τις προϋποθέσεις αυτής της σύμβασης όπως περιγράφονται.

ΠΑΡΑΡΤΗΜΑ Ι. Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο

Υλοποίηση των μέτρων πρόληψης και διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων

	Μέτρο Ν° 2 Πρόληψη απορριμμάτων τροφίμων σε μπουφέδες και εστιατόρια"
Ομάδα διαχείρισης: ρόλοι και ευθύνες	<p>Η υπεύθυνη για την εφαρμογή και παρακολούθηση του μέτρου: Δρ. Π. Γκιούρκα, ΔΙΑΑΜΑΘ ΑΕ. Email: pgiourka@gmail.com, Τηλ. +306973251634</p> <p>Οι σημαντικότεροι ενδιαφερόμενοι φορείς που πρέπει να συμμετάσχουν στην εφαρμογή του μέτρου προκειμένου να λάβουν οργανωτική και, εάν είναι δυνατόν, οικονομική υποστήριξη (π.χ. κατηγορίες ενώσεων, φιλανθρωπικές ενώσεις, δημόσιοι ή ιδιωτικοί φορείς, όπως η εταιρεία διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων ή η εταιρεία διαχείρισης δικτύου ύδρευσης) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Σύνδεσμος Ξενοδόχων<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Διάδοση της ευκαιρίας για συμμετοχή στο έργο URBAN WASTE σε όλα τα των ξενοδοχεία της πόλης της Καβάλας• Δήμος Καβάλας, κ. Ηλίας Γιαρματζίδης, strategic@0700.syzefxis.gov.gr.<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Διάδοση των πλεονεκτημάτων του εφαρμοζόμενου μέτρου στους πολίτες, στήριξη της υλοποίησης του και παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού• Δημωφέλεια, Δημοτική Κοινοφελής Επιχείρηση για την Ανάπτυξη του Τουρισμού, κα. Ιωσηφίδου, Πρόεδρος του Διοικητικού Συμβουλίου, +30 2510 831388, Email: develop@kavalagreece.gr<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Διάδοση της εφαρμογής των μέτρων στους τουρίστες και παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού
Το Κοινό-Στόχος	<p>Η κατηγορία των παρόχων τουριστικών υπηρεσιών. Αυτό το επιχειρησιακό σχέδιο απευθύνεται κυρίως σε ξενοδοχεία</p> <p>Το είδος των τουριστών που στοχεύουν τα μέτρα, προκειμένου να οργανωθεί η κατάλληλη επικοινωνιακή προσέγγιση και τα υλικά είναι:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• ξένοι/τοπικοί• νέοι/οικογένειες/ηλικιωμένοι
Συμμετοχή των φορέων	<p>Το κοινό-στόχος θα συμμετέχει μέσω των ακόλουθων δράσεων:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Διοργάνωση μίας ενημερωτικής πρωτοβουλίας που πραγματοποιήθηκε στις 21 Φεβρουαρίου 2018 όπου επεξηγήθηκε το επιχειρησιακό σχέδιο και καταγράφηκε η έκφραση ενδιαφέροντος από τους ιδιοκτήτες των ξενοδοχείων.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Επικοινωνία και ευαισθητοποίηση, που προήλθαν από το σύνδεσμο των ξενοδόχων. 3. Εκστρατεία προώθησης μέσω του υλικού επικοινωνίας του έργου URBAN WASTE. 4. Υπογραφή κοινής συμφωνίας συνεργασίας σε δημόσια εκδήλωση. 5. Προσέλκυση περισσότερων ξενοδοχείων κατά τη διάρκεια της δημόσιας εκδήλωσης. 6. Ο Σύνδεσμος Ξενοδόχων θα στείλει πρόσκληση ώστε να λάβουν μέρος σε αυτή την πρωτοβουλία περισσότερα ξενοδοχεία. 7. Διοργάνωση μιας τελικής ενημερωτικής εκδήλωσης για την παρουσίαση των αποτελεσμάτων της εφαρμογής των μέτρων και την ένταξη και νέων ξενοδοχείων στην πρωτοβουλία
Καθορισμός στόχων	<p>Στόχοι που πρέπει να επιτευχθούν κατά τη φάση υλοποίησης του μέτρου (είναι σημαντικό να συζητηθούν και να συμφωνηθούν με όλους τους ενδιαφερομένους φορείς και παράγοντες που συμμετέχουν στη διαδικασία):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● αριθμός ξενοδοχείων που συμμετέχουν: τουλάχιστον 4-5 ξενοδοχεία κατά την έναρξη της εφαρμογής των μέτρων και θα συμμετέχουν τουλάχιστον ακόμη 4 ξενοδοχεία μέχρι το τέλος της υλοποίησης του έργου ● συνολικός αριθμός των ξενοδοχείων της Καβάλας: 8 ● Ποσοστό των ξενοδοχείων που συμμετέχουν: ● Αρ. Επικοινωνίας / ταμπέλες στον μπουφέ ● προσέγγιση σε τουρίστες (πολίτες) από την πρωτοβουλία επικοινωνίας: Τουλάχιστον σε 200 τουρίστες έγινε προσέγγιση τους δύο πρώτους μήνες της εφαρμογής των μέτρων και συνολικά θα γίνει προσέγγιση σε 500 τουρίστες μέχρι το τέλος της υλοποίησης του έργου. <p>Παρακολούθηση δείγματος παραγωγής απορριμμάτων (3 εβδομάδες: 21 ημέρες)</p> <p>kg αποφευχθείσας παραγωγής απορριμμάτων (kg οργανικών απορριμμάτων)</p>
Θέσπιση μέτρων	<p>Τα επιχειρησιακά βήματα που προβλέπονται για τη θέσπιση των μέτρων και την επίτευξη των καθορισμένων στόχων παρατίθενται παρακάτω:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Διοργάνωση εργαστηρίου με τους ιδιοκτήτες ξενοδοχείων για την ολοκλήρωση των συγκεκριμένων στόχων και των παρακολούθηση των μετρήσεων ● Διοργάνωση Δημόσιας Εκδήλωσης για την υπογραφή της Συμφωνίας στις Μάϊος 2018 στην Καβάλα ● Διοργάνωση εκπαιδευτικής δραστηριότητας σε Ξενοδοχεία (Μάϊος) στην Καβάλα ● Δραστηριότητες υποστήριξης: οι συμμετέχοντες θα έχουν ένα σημείο επικοινωνίας για τυχόν ερωτήσεις ή ζητήματα που προκύπτουν. Η υπεύθυνη επικοινωνίας της δράσης είναι η Δρ. Παρασκευή Γκιούρκα, pgiourka@gmail.com. ● Η ΔΙ.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. σε συνεργασία με τον Επικεφαλή Εταίρο θα παρέχει προσαρμοσμένο υλικό επικοινωνίας - Η ΔΙΑΑΜΑΘ θα διανείμει υλικό στα ξενοδοχεία που συμμετέχουν. ● Διοργάνωση προκαταρκτικών ελέγχων <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ο 1^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί πριν από την ημερομηνία έναρξης της υλοποίησης του μέτρου ○ Ο 2^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί την πρώτη εβδομάδα από την ημερομηνία έναρξης της υλοποίησης του μέτρου ○ ο 3^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί την τελευταία εβδομάδα από

	<p>την υλοποίηση του μέτρου</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Διοργάνωση τελικής εκδήλωσης / ενημερωτικής πρωτοβουλίας για τη συμμετοχή νέων ξενοδοχείων με παρουσίαση των επιτευχθέντων αποτελεσμάτων
Διαθέσιμες και χρήσιμες πηγές	<p>Ο προϋπολογισμός που απαιτείται για την εφαρμογή των προτεινόμενων μέτρων αναλύεται ως εξής:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Εκτύπωση Πινακίδων/ Poster A3: 10* Ευρώ / τεμάχιο = Ευρώ 2. Εκτύπωση Αυτοκόλλητων Βιτρίνας 5* Ευρώ / τεμάχιο = Ευρώ
Χρονοδιάγραμμα	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Διοργάνωση δημόσιας πρωτοβουλίας-εκδήλωσης έναρξης - θα πραγματοποιηθεί κατά τη διάρκεια της 4^{ης} εκδήλωσης της Κοινότητας Πρακτικής: Απρίλιος 2018 2. Φάση έναρξης (περίπου 1 μήνας): τελικός σχεδιασμός υλικών, διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων κατάρτισης και δοκιμή (εάν απαιτείται) των δράσεων που προβλέπονται σε ένα δείγμα τουριστικών εγκαταστάσεων: Μάιος 2018 3. Πλήρης φάση υλοποίησης που περιλαμβάνει όλες τις επιλεγμένες τουριστικές εγκαταστάσεις και στοχεύει στις διάφορες κατηγορίες τουριστών με ειδικές δραστηριότητες επικοινωνίας που θα διαρκέσουν τουλάχιστον 5 μήνες: Ιούνιος-Οκτώβριος 2018 4. Διοργάνωση τελικής εκδήλωσης / ενημερωτικής πρωτοβουλίας για τη συμμετοχή νέων ξενοδοχείων με παρουσίαση των επιτευχθέντων αποτελεσμάτων: Οκτώβριος 2018
Παρακολούθηση	<p>Παρακολούθηση δείγματος παραγωγής απορριμμάτων (3 εβδομάδες: 21 ημέρες)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • kg αποφευχθείσας παραγωγής απορριμμάτων (kg οργανικών απορριμμάτων)

Σύμπραξη Δημοσίου-Ιδιωτικού τομέα για την υλοποίηση των μέτρων του έργου URBAN-WASTE

Περιεχόμενα

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Περιγραφή του έργου UrBAN-WASTE

Το UrBAN-WASTE είναι ένα ευρωπαϊκό έργο χρηματοδοτούμενο στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος Horizon 2020, το οποίο στοχεύει στη στήριξη και χάραξη πολιτικής για την αντιμετώπιση των προκλήσεων που παρουσιάζει ο τουρισμός όσον αφορά την παραγωγή και τη διαχείριση απορριμμάτων. Η ελαχιστοποίηση της παραγωγής απορριμμάτων αποτελεί σημαντικό στοιχείο για την αναγνώριση της τουριστικής προσφοράς και την προώθηση της έξυπνης και βιώσιμης ανάπτυξης στις ευρωπαϊκές τουριστικές πόλεις. Ωστόσο, οι τουριστικές ροές παρουσιάζουν μια σειρά αρνητικών εξωτερικών επιπτώσεων και οι τουριστικές πόλεις πρέπει να αντιμετωπίσουν τις πρόσθετες προκλήσεις που σχετίζονται με την πρόληψη και τη διαχείριση των απορριμμάτων, λόγω των γεωγραφικών και κλιματικών τους συνθηκών, της εποχικότητας της ροής του τουρισμού και της ιδιαιτερότητάς τους.

Λαμβάνοντας υπ' όψιν:

Τον Ιούνιο του 2016 η Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρεία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας – Θράκης ΑΕ – Δ.Ι.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. σε συνεργασία με 27 εταίρους (Κυβέρνηση των Καναρίων Νήσων) (υπεύθυνος έργου), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρεία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας – Θράκης ΑΕ – Δ.Ι.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Περιφέρεια Ηπείρου (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Δήμος Λευκωσίας (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] ξεκίνησαν την υλοποίηση του έργου URBAN WASTE.

Οι στόχοι και οι δράσεις του έργου UrBAN-WASTE είναι:

1. Η ανάπτυξη νέων οικολογικών, καινοτόμων, και με γνώμονα την αρχή ισότητας των φύλων στρατηγικών και ορθών πρακτικών που αποσκοπούν στη μείωση της παραγωγής αστικών απορριμμάτων και στην περαιτέρω υποστήριξη της επαναχρησιμοποίησης, της ανακύκλωσης, της συλλογής και της διάθεσης των απορριμμάτων σε τουριστικές πόλεις. Οι στρατηγικές αυτές θα υλοποιηθούν σε 11

πιλοτικές περιπτώσεις: Φλωρεντία (Ιταλία), Νίκαια (Γαλλία), Λισαβόνα (Πορτογαλία.), Συρακούσες (Ιταλία), Κοπεγχάγη (Δανία), Καβάλα (Ελλάδα), Σανταντέρ (Ισπανία), Λευκωσία (Κύπρος), Πόντα Ντελγάδα (Πορτογαλία), Ντουμπρόβνικ - Νερέτβα (Κροατία), Τενερίφη (Ισπανία) και τα αποτελέσματα θα παρακολουθούνται και θα διαδίδονται διευκολύνοντας τη μεταφορά και προσαρμογή των αποτελεσμάτων του έργου και σε άλλες περιπτώσεις.

2. Η οργάνωση των τοπικών ενδιαφερομένων σε μια επιτροπή που θα ονομάζεται Κοινότητα Πρακτικής (CoP), μέσω μιας συμμετοχικής διαδικασίας για την εμπλοκή διαφόρων ενδιαφερομένων, θα περιλαμβάνει ίδιο αριθμό γυναικών και ανδρών από την τουριστική βιομηχανία, τις αρχές διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων, τις ΜΚΟ κ.λπ., για το σχεδιασμό των στρατηγικών πρόληψης και διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων. Η Κοινότητα Πρακτικής (CoP) επιλέγει τα μέτρα που πρέπει να εφαρμοστούν στην Καβάλα και καθορίζει το επιχειρησιακό σχέδιο για την εφαρμογή κάθε μέτρου.
3. Διασφάλιση κάθε μέτρου που εφαρμόζεται από τοπικούς, ιδιωτικούς ή / και δημόσιους φορείς, οι οποίοι, υπογράφοντας τις ακόλουθες δεσμεύσεις, συμφωνούν στην υλοποίηση εθελοντικών δράσεων με στόχο τη μείωση της παραγωγής απορριμμάτων και την προώθηση του έργου UrBAN-WASTE, μέσω της διοργάνωσης ειδικών δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας.

Μια εθελοντική συμφωνία για την προώθηση της υλοποίησης των μέτρων του έργου UrBAN-WASTE με ημερομηνία/...../2018.

μεταξύ των:

Συμμετέχων Α: Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρεία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας-Θράκης ΑΑΕ - ΔΙ.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. Α.Α.Ε.,

Συμμετέχων Β: Οργανισμός Λιμένα Καβάλας (ΟΛΚ)

Συμμετέχων Γ: ΔΗΜΩΦΕΛΕΙΑ, Δημοτική Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση Καβάλας

Συμμετέχων Δ: Δήμος Καβάλας

Την προαναφερθείσα ημερομηνία, συνυπογράφηκε η παρούσα εθελοντική συμφωνία για την προώθηση της υλοποίησης του **Μέτρου 12** του έργου UrBAN-WASTE, “**Κάδοι χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων σε δημόσιους και τουριστικούς χώρους**”, με στόχο ιδίως τη συμμετοχή των τοπικών φορέων [ΟΛΚ Καβάλας, δημόσιοι φορείς, εταιρείες διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων, πάροχοι τουριστικών υπηρεσιών, τοπικές ΜΚΟ κλπ. ...] που βρίσκονται

στην Καβάλα, ώστε να εφαρμόσουν συγκεκριμένες δράσεις για τη μείωση της παραγωγής απορριμμάτων και για τη βελτίωση των πρακτικών διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων.

Υποχρεώσεις

Συνεπώς τα συμβαλλόμενα μέρη συμφωνούν,

- να υποστηρίξουν την υλοποίηση του Μέτρου 12, “Κάδοι χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων σε δημόσιους και τουριστικούς χώρους” του έργου URBAN-WASTE στην Καβάλα και να συμμετάσχουν στην τοπική Κοινότητα Πρακτικής, η οποία θα ενισχύσει την υλοποίηση αυτού
- να αναγνωρίσουν τις ενέργειες που πρέπει να υλοποιηθούν, τον ρόλο και τα καθήκοντα που ορίζονται στο Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο που αναφέρεται στο *Παράρτημα I* και ότι οι συμβαλλόμενοι αυτής της εθελοντικής συμφωνίας δεσμεύονται να τηρούν και να υλοποιούν τις δεσμεύσεις που έχουν αναλάβει για τον δικό τους οργανισμό, θεωρώντας ότι όλα τα προαναφερθέντα συνάδουν με την αντίστοιχη θεσμική ή εμπορική αποστολή τους.

Με τη υπογραφή της παρούσας εθελοντικής συμφωνίας, τα συμβαλλόμενα μέρη αναλαμβάνουν τις ακόλουθες δεσμεύσεις οι οποίες θα περιγράφουν και θα διευκρινιστούν λεπτομερέστερα στο Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο:

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Α: Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρεία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας - Θράκης ΑΕ - ΔΙ.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. Α.Α.Ε.:

- συμπερίληψη όλων των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παροχή τεχνικής υποστήριξης για την υλοποίηση των δράσεων,
- διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- υλοποίηση μέτρων για τη βελτίωση της συλλογής των διαχωρισμένων απορριμμάτων στην περιοχή που διαχειρίζεται ο οργανισμός μου,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,

- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ [Συμμετέχοντα Β]: Οργανισμός Λιμένα Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- επέκταση της εφαρμογής του μέτρου σε λιμάνια αρμοδιότητας του ΟΛΚ
- παροχή τεχνικής υποστήριξης για την υλοποίηση των δράσεων,
- παροχή οικονομικής υποστήριξης για την προμήθεια και την εγκατάσταση των κάδων ανακυκλώσιμων απορριμμάτων,
- συμμετοχή στις δραστηριότητες επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας για το έργο,
- υλοποίηση του μέτρου για την προμήθεια και εγκατάσταση κάδων χωριστής συλλογής ανακυκλώσιμων για τη βελτίωση της συλλογής των διαχωρισμένων απορριμμάτων στον οργανισμό μου, και στην χερσαία ζώνη Λιμένα Καβάλας,
- προώθηση της υλοποίησης του μέτρου σε άλλα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Γ: Δημοφέλεια, Δημοτική Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση

Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παραγωγή (εκτύπωση) προωθητικού υλικού επικοινωνίας, δαπάνες διαφήμισης και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- διοργάνωση ή/ και συμμετοχή σε δραστηριότητες επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,

- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχων Δ: Δήμος Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού που αφορά τα μέτρα υλοποίησης,
- διοργάνωση/συμμετοχή σε δράσεις επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- προώθηση της υλοποίησης του μέτρου σε άλλα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

Όροι

Η παρούσα εθελοντική συμφωνία είναι κατά βούληση και μπορεί να τροποποιηθεί μετά από αμοιβαία συναίνεση. Ισχύει με την υπογραφή των νόμιμων εκπροσώπων των φορέων που συμμετέχουν και από τους εταίρους του έργου URBAN-WASTE και θα παραμείνει σε ισχύ έως ότου τροποποιηθεί ή τερματιστεί από οποιονδήποτε από τους εταίρους μετά από κοινή συναίνεση. Διαφορετικά, η συμφωνία αυτή λήγει στις 31 Δεκεμβρίου 2018.

Εμείς, οι υπογράφωντες, δηλώνουμε ότι έχουμε διαβάσει και αποδεχτεί τους όρους και τις προϋποθέσεις αυτής της σύμβασης όπως περιγράφονται.

ΠΑΡΑΡΤΗΜΑ Ι. Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο

Υλοποίηση των μέτρων πρόληψης και διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων

Μέτρο Νο 12 Κάδοι χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων σε δημόσιους και τουριστικούς χώρους	
Ομάδα διαχείρισης: ρόλοι και ευθύνες	<p>Η υπεύθυνη για την εφαρμογή και παρακολούθηση του μέτρου: Δρ. Π. Γκιούρκα, ΔΙΑΑΜΑΘ ΑΕ. Email: pgiourka@gmail.com, Τηλ. +306973251634</p> <p>Οι σημαντικότεροι ενδιαφερόμενοι φορείς που πρέπει να συμμετάσχουν στην εφαρμογή του μέτρου προκειμένου να λάβουν οργανωτική και, εάν είναι δυνατόν, οικονομική υποστήριξη (π.χ. κατηγορίες ενώσεων, φιλανθρωπικές ενώσεις, δημόσιοι ή ιδιωτικοί φορείς, όπως η εταιρεία διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων ή η εταιρεία διαχείρισης δικτύου ύδρευσης) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Οργανισμός Λιμένα Καβάλας, κ. Χρήστος Ηλιάδης, Πρόεδρος, iliadis@portkavala.gr, Μ: 6981102532, 6946336385<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Κύριος φορέας για τη χρηματοδότηση και υλοποίηση του έργου και διάδοση της ευκαιρίας για συμμετοχή στο έργο URBAN WASTE και σε άλλους δημόσιους φορείς.• Ανάδοχος Καθαριότητας χερσαίας ζώνης: Νικολαΐδης Νικόλας, Κιν.:6974898607.• Δήμος Καβάλας, κ. Ηλίας Γιαρματζίδης, strategic@0700.syzefxis.gov.gr.<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Διάδοση των πλεονεκτημάτων του εφαρμοζόμενου μέτρου στους πολίτες, στήριξη της υλοποίησης του και παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού που αφορά τα μέτρα υλοποίησης.• Δημωφέλεια, Δημοτική Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση για την Ανάπτυξη του Τουρισμού, κα. Ιωσηφίδου, Πρόεδρος του Διοικητικού Συμβουλίου, +30 2510 831388, Email: develop@kavalagreece.gr<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Διάδοση της εφαρμογής των μέτρων στους τουρίστες και παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού που αφορά τα μέτρα υλοποίησης.
Το Κοινό-Στόχος	<p>Στόχοι που πρέπει να επιτευχθούν κατά τη φάση υλοποίησης του μέτρου (είναι σημαντικό να συζητηθούν και να συμφωνηθούν με όλους τους εμπλεκόμενους φορείς και παράγοντες που εμπλέκονται στη διαδικασία):</p> <p>Ο Οργανισμός Λιμένα Καβάλας θα εγκαταστήσει 25 κάδους για τη διαλογή χαρτιού + πλαστικού + μετάλλου (μαζί) δίπλα στους κάδους των σύμμεικτων απορριμμάτων που έχουν ήδη εγκατασταθεί στην χερσαία ζώνη που διαχειρίζεται το λιμάνι.</p> <p>Το λιμάνι προσελκύει πολλούς τουρίστες, ειδικά κατά τη διάρκεια του καλοκαιριού. Το μέσο βάρος του σάκου των νέων κάδων θα υπολογιστεί και θα πολλαπλασιαστεί με τον αριθμό των σάκων που συλλέγονται ανά ημέρα για να υπολογιστεί πόσα κιλά απορριμμάτων παράγονται για τον μπλε κάδο μετά την εγκατάσταση των κάδων.</p>

	<p>Το είδος των τουριστών που στοχεύουν τα μέτρα, προκειμένου να οργανωθεί η κατάλληλη επικοινωνιακή προσέγγιση και τα υλικά είναι:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ξένοι/τοπικοί • νέοι/οικογένειες/ηλικιωμένοι
Συμμετοχή των φορέων	<p>Το κοινό-στόχος θα συμμετέχει μέσω των ακόλουθων δράσεων:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Διοργάνωση συνάντησης πριν από τη σύναψη της εθελοντικής συμφωνίας όπου: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) θα γίνει παρουσίαση του υλικού επικοινωνίας και ευαισθητοποίησης στον Διευθύνοντα Σύμβουλο του Οργανισμού Λιμένα Καβάλας b) καμπάνια προώθησης μέσω των καναλιών επικοινωνίας του έργου URBAN WASTE 2. Σύναψη κοινής συμφωνία συνεργασίας σε δημόσια εκδήλωση Μάιο, 2018 3. Περίοδος υλοποίησης μέτρων Μάιος - Οκτώβριος 2018 4. Διοργάνωση τελικής εκδήλωσης / ενημερωτικής πρωτοβουλίας για τη συμμετοχή άλλων δημοσίων φορέων με παρουσίαση των επιτευχθέντων αποτελεσμάτων προκειμένου να ενισχυθεί ο αντίκτυπος του έργου
Καθορισμός στόχων	<p>Στόχοι που πρέπει να επιτευχθούν κατά τη φάση υλοποίησης του μέτρου (είναι σημαντικό να συζητηθούν και να συμφωνηθούν με όλους τους ενδιαφερόμενους και εμπλεκόμενους φορείς που συμμετέχουν στη διαδικασία): Αριθμός των κάδων χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων που είναι εγκατεστημένοι σε δημόσιους χώρους, δλδ. στην ηπειρωτική ζώνη που διαχειρίζεται το λιμάνι. Οι κάδοι θα χωρίσουν τα απορρίμματα σε πολλαπλές ροές, δλδ. χαρτί + πλαστικό + σύμμεικτα). Ο λόγος για την επιλογή του λιμανιού ως περίπτωση εγκατάστασης κάδων χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων είναι επειδή αυτή την περιοχή την επισκέπτεται μεγάλος αριθμός τουριστών για να απολαύσει την όμορφη θέα στη θάλασσα.</p>
Θέσπιση μέτρων	<p>Τα επιχειρησιακά βήματα που προβλέπονται για τη θέσπιση των μέτρων και την επίτευξη των καθορισμένων στόχων παρατίθενται παρακάτω:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Διοργάνωση εργαστηρίου με τον Λιμένα της Καβάλας για την ολοκλήρωση των συγκεκριμένων στόχων και των παρακολούθηση των μετρήσεων • Διοργάνωση Δημόσιας Εκδήλωσης για την υπογραφή της Συμφωνίας στις Απρίλιος 2018 στην Καβάλα • Η Δι.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. Α.Α.Ε σε συνεργασία με τον Επικεφαλή Εταίρο θα παρέχει προσαρμοσμένο υλικό επικοινωνίας • Η Δι.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. Α.Α.Ε σε συνεργασία με τους εμπλεκόμενους φορείς θα διανείμει υλικό στο Λιμένα της Καβάλας • Διοργάνωση προκαταρκτικών ελέγχων <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ο 1^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί πριν από την ημερομηνία έναρξης της υλοποίησης του μέτρου ○ Ο 2^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί την πρώτη εβδομάδα από την ημερομηνία έναρξης της υλοποίησης του μέτρου ○ ο 3^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί την τελευταία εβδομάδα από την υλοποίηση του μέτρου
Διαθέσιμες και χρήσιμες πηγές	<p>Ο προϋπολογισμός που απαιτείται για την εφαρμογή των προτεινόμενων μέτρων αναλύεται ως εξής:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Αγορά και εγκατάσταση 25 κάδων χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων για ανακυκλώσιμα προϊόντα. Κόστος 2125,00 Ευρώ. 2. Αυτοκόλλητα, 1 αυτοκόλλητο / κάδο* 50 κάδοι*....Ευρώ =.....Ευρώ 3. Εκτύπωση Καρτών με Υλικό Προώθησης, 500 κάρτες με υλικό προώθησης

	<p>*.....Ευρώ/κάρτα =Ευρώ</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Εκτύπωση poster (A3) : 20 τεμ. 5. Εκτύπωση poster 4 τεμ. 1*2m για τους πυλώνες στο λιμάνι
Χρονοδιάγραμμα	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Διοργάνωση δημόσιας πρωτοβουλίας-εκδήλωσης έναρξης - θα πραγματοποιηθεί κατά τη διάρκεια της 4^{ης} εκδήλωσης της Κοινότητας Πρακτικής: Μάιος 2018 2. Φάση έναρξης (περίπου 1 μήνας): τελικός σχεδιασμός υλικών, διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων κατάρτισης και δοκιμή (εάν απαιτείται) των δράσεων που προβλέπονται σε ένα δείγμα τουριστικών εγκαταστάσεων: Μάιος 2018 3. Πλήρης φάση υλοποίησης που περιλαμβάνει όλες τις επιλεγμένες τουριστικές εγκαταστάσεις και στοχεύει στις διάφορες κατηγορίες τουριστών με ειδικές δραστηριότητες επικοινωνίας που θα διαρκέσουν τουλάχιστον 5 μήνες: Ιούνιος-Οκτώβριος 2018 4. Διοργάνωση τελικής εκδήλωσης / ενημερωτικής πρωτοβουλίας για τη συμμετοχή νέων ξενοδοχείων με παρουσίαση των επιτευχθέντων αποτελεσμάτων: Οκτώβριος 2018
Παρακολούθηση	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Εγκατάσταση κάδων χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων (: χαρτί +πλαστικό + σύμμεικτα): 25 2. Περιοχή της πόλης που καλύπτεται από τους κάδους χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων: χλμ. 3. Μέσος αριθμός ημερήσιων εκκενώσεων: μία φορά την ημέρα 4. kg απορριμμάτων μπλε κάδου <p>Παρακολούθηση "Δείγματος" (3 εβδομάδες: 21 ημέρες):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Δείκτης: Απορρίμματα μπλε κάδου που συλλέχθηκαν (βάρος)

Σύμπραξη Δημοσίου-Ιδιωτικού τομέα για την υλοποίηση των μέτρων του έργου URBAN-WASTE

Περιεχόμενα

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Περιγραφή του έργου UrBAN-WASTE

Το UrBAN-WASTE είναι ένα ευρωπαϊκό έργο χρηματοδοτούμενο στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος Horizon 2020, το οποίο στοχεύει στη στήριξη και χάραξη πολιτικής για την αντιμετώπιση των προκλήσεων που παρουσιάζει ο τουρισμός όσον αφορά την παραγωγή και τη διαχείριση απορριμμάτων. Η ελαχιστοποίηση της παραγωγής απορριμμάτων αποτελεί σημαντικό στοιχείο για την αναγνώριση της τουριστικής προσφοράς και την προώθηση της έξυπνης και βιώσιμης ανάπτυξης στις ευρωπαϊκές τουριστικές πόλεις. Ωστόσο, οι τουριστικές ροές παρουσιάζουν μια σειρά αρνητικών εξωτερικών επιπτώσεων και οι τουριστικές πόλεις πρέπει να αντιμετωπίσουν τις πρόσθετες προκλήσεις που σχετίζονται με την πρόληψη και τη διαχείριση των απορριμμάτων, λόγω των γεωγραφικών και κλιματικών τους συνθηκών, της εποχικότητας της ροής του τουρισμού και της ιδιαιτερότητάς τους.

Λαμβάνοντας υπ' όψιν:

Τον Ιούνιο του 2016 η Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρεία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας – Θράκης ΑΕ – Δ.Ι.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. σε συνεργασία με 27 εταιρείες (Κυβέρνηση των Καναρίων Νήσων) (υπεύθυνος έργου), Technische Universiteit Delft (TUD), Association des Cités et des régions pour le recyclage et la gestion durable des Ressources (ACR+), Aarhus Universitet (AU), Ayuntamiento de Santander (ADS), Universität Für Bodenkultur Wien (BOKU), Kobenhavns Kommune (CPH), Cabildo Insular De Tenerife (CIT), Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρεία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας – Θράκης ΑΕ – Δ.Ι.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ (DIAAMATH), Kobenhavns Universitet (UCPH), Observatoire Régional Des Déchets D'Île-de-France (ORDIF), Bioazul (BIOAZUL), Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet (SLU), Consulta Europa - Projects and Innovation s.r.l. (CE), Agence d'Urbanisme à La Réunion (AGORAH), Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Ambiente Italia s.r.l. (AI), Asociacion Hotelera Y Extrahotelera De Tenerife La Palma La Gomera Y El Hierro (ASHOTEL), Περιφέρεια Ηπείρου (EPI), Fundo Regional Para A Ciencia E Tecnologia (FRCT), Linneuniversitetet (LU), Δήμος Λευκωσίας (NI), Regione Toscana (RT), Comune di Siracusa (SI), Dunea Doo Za Regionalni Razvoj I Poslovne Usluge (DUNEA), Camara Municipal De Lisboa (LI), Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA)] ξεκίνησαν την υλοποίηση του έργου URBAN WASTE.

Οι στόχοι και οι δράσεις του έργου UrBAN-WASTE είναι:

1. Η ανάπτυξη νέων οικολογικών, καινοτόμων, και με γνώμονα την αρχή ισότητας των φύλων στρατηγικών και ορθών πρακτικών που αποσκοπούν στη μείωση της παραγωγής αστικών απορριμμάτων και στην περαιτέρω υποστήριξη της επαναχρησιμοποίησης, της ανακύκλωσης, της συλλογής και της διάθεσης των απορριμμάτων σε τουριστικές πόλεις. Οι στρατηγικές αυτές θα υλοποιηθούν σε 11 πιλοτικές περιπτώσεις: Φλωρεντία (Ιταλία), Νίκαια (Γαλλία), Λισαβόνα

(Πορτογαλία.), Συρακούσες (Ιταλία), Κοπεγχάγη (Δανία), Καβάλα (Ελλάδα), Σανταντέρ (Ισπανία), Λευκωσία (Κύπρος), Πόντα Ντελγάδα (Πορτογαλία), Ντουμπρόβνικ - Νερέτβα (Κροατία), Τενερίφη (Ισπανία) και τα αποτελέσματα θα παρακολουθούνται και θα διαδίδονται διευκολύνοντας τη μεταφορά και προσαρμογή των αποτελεσμάτων του έργου και σε άλλες περιπτώσεις.

2. Η οργάνωση των τοπικών ενδιαφερομένων σε μια επιτροπή που θα ονομάζεται Κοινότητα Πρακτικής (CoP), μέσω μιας συμμετοχικής διαδικασίας για την εμπλοκή διαφόρων ενδιαφερομένων, θα περιλαμβάνει ίδιο αριθμό γυναικών και ανδρών από την τουριστική βιομηχανία, τις αρχές απορριμμάτων, τις ΜΚΟ κ.λπ., για το σχεδιασμό των στρατηγικών πρόληψης και διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων. Η Κοινότητα Πρακτικής (CoP) επιλέγει τα μέτρα που πρέπει να εφαρμοστούν στην Καβάλα και καθορίζει το επιχειρησιακό σχέδιο για την εφαρμογή κάθε μέτρου.
3. Διασφάλιση κάθε μέτρου που εφαρμόζεται από τοπικούς, ιδιωτικούς ή / και δημόσιους φορείς, οι οποίοι, υπογράφοντας τις ακόλουθες δεσμεύσεις, συμφωνούν στην υλοποίηση εθελοντικών δράσεων με στόχο τη μείωση της παραγωγής απορριμμάτων και την προώθηση του έργου UrBAN-WASTE, μέσω της διοργάνωσης ειδικών δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας.

Μια εθελοντική συμφωνία για την προώθηση της υλοποίησης των μέτρων του έργου UrBAN-WASTE με ημερομηνία 16.05.2018.

μεταξύ των:

Συμμετέχων Α: Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρεία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας-Θράκης ΑΑΕ - ΔΙ.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. Α.Α.Ε., και

Συμμετέχων Β: Σύνδεσμος Εστιατορίων Καβάλας

Συμμετέχων Γ: ΔΗΜΩΦΕΛΕΙΑ, Δημοτική Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση Καβάλας

Συμμετέχων Δ: Δήμος Καβάλας

Συμμετέχων Ε: Εστιατόριο "CAMPING ALEXANDROS"

Συμμετέχων Ζ: Εστιατόριο "ΤΟ ΠΑΡΑΛΙΑΚΟΝ"

Συμμετέχων Η: Εστιατόριο "Ο ΝΑΥΤΗΣ"

Συμμετέχων Θ: Εστιατόριο "ΚΥΝΗΓΟΣ"

Συμμετέχων Ι: Εστιατόριο "ΚΥΡΑ ΒΑΓΓΕΛΙΩ"

Συμμετέχων Κ: Εστιατόριο "ΤΑ ΒΑΡΕΛΙΑ"

Συμμετέχων Λ: Εστιατόριο "ΨΑΡΑΚΙ ΟΥΖΟ BAR"

Την προαναφερθείσα ημερομηνία, συνυπογράφηκε η παρούσα εθελοντική συμφωνία για την προώθηση της υλοποίησης των μέτρων του έργου UrBAN-WASTE, Μέτρο 1 "Σακούλα/Συσκευασία τροφίμων για το σπίτι" ("Doggy Bag") και του Μέτρου 20, "Συσκευή Ζύγισης Τροφίμων", με στόχο ιδίως τη συμμετοχή των τοπικών φορέων ήτοι: Δ. Καβάλας, Δημωφέλεια, Σωματείο Εστιατόρων και Συναφών Επαγγελματιών Καβάλας, Ιδιοκτήτες εστιατορίων που βρίσκονται στην Καβάλα, ώστε να εφαρμόσουν συγκεκριμένες δράσεις για τη μείωση της παραγωγής απορριμμάτων και για τη βελτίωση των πρακτικών διαχείρισής τους.

Υποχρεώσεις

Συνεπώς τα συμβαλλόμενα μέρη συμφωνούν,

- να υποστηρίξουν την υλοποίηση των **Μέτρων 1 "Σακούλα/Συσκευασία τροφίμων για το σπίτι" ("Doggy Bag") και 20, "Συσκευή Ζύγισης Τροφίμων"**, του έργου UrBAN-WASTE στην Καβάλα και να συμμετάσχουν στην τοπική Κοινότητα Πρακτικής, η οποία θα ενισχύσει την υλοποίηση αυτού.
- να αναγνωρίσουν τις ενέργειες που πρέπει να υλοποιηθούν, τον ρόλο και τα καθήκοντα που ορίζονται στο Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο που αναφέρεται στο *Παράρτημα I* και ότι οι συμβαλλόμενοι αυτής της εθελοντικής συμφωνίας δεσμεύονται να τηρούν και να υλοποιούν τις δεσμεύσεις που έχουν αναλάβει για τον δικό τους οργανισμό, θεωρώντας ότι όλα τα προαναφερθέντα συνάδουν με την αντίστοιχη θεσμική ή εμπορική αποστολή.

Με τη υπογραφή της παρούσας εθελοντικής συμφωνίας, τα συμβαλλόμενα μέρη αναλαμβάνουν τις ακόλουθες δεσμεύσεις οι οποίες θα περιγραφούν και θα διευκρινιστούν λεπτομερέστερα στο Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο:

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Α: Αναπτυξιακή Ανώνυμη Εταιρία Διαχείρισης Απορριμμάτων Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας - Θράκης Α.Α.Ε. - ΔΙ.Α.Α.Μ.Α.Θ. Α.Α.Ε

- συμπερίληψη των τοπικών των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παροχή τεχνικής υποστήριξης για την υλοποίηση των δράσεων,
- διοργάνωση/συμμετοχή σε δράσεις επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Β: Σύνδεσμος Εστιατορίων Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των τοπικών δραστηριοτήτων/ των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- υλοποίηση μέτρων για τη μείωση των απορριμμάτων τροφίμων
- προώθηση της υλοποίησης του μέτρου σε άλλα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά το φύλο και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Γ: Δημωφέλεια, Δημοτική Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των τοπικών δραστηριοτήτων/ των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού που αφορά τα μέτρα υλοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ ΤΟΥ Συμμετέχοντα Δ: Δήμος Καβάλας

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού που αφορά τα μέτρα υλοποίησης,
- διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων επικοινωνίας και διανομή υλικού επικοινωνίας,

- προώθηση της υλοποίησης του μέτρου σε άλλα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και όλων των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά την ισότητα των φύλων και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής των μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

ΥΠΟΧΡΕΩΣΕΙΣ των Συμμετεχόντων Ε, Ζ, Η, Θ, Ι, Κ, Λ:

- συμπερίληψη των ενδιαφερόμενων μερών στην υλοποίηση του μέτρου,
- προώθηση υλικού επικοινωνίας,
- υλοποίηση μέτρων για τη μείωση των απορριμμάτων τροφίμων
- παρακολούθηση και αποτύπωση των αποτελεσμάτων της εφαρμογής του μέτρου
- προώθηση της υλοποίησης του μέτρου σε άλλα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη και αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης,
- συμπερίληψη των γυναικών και των ανδρών σε πρακτικές σε όλα τα επίπεδα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των επαγγελματιών, της κοινότητας και των ενδιαφερομένων,
- επίγνωση του αντίκτυπου όλων των μέτρων στα υφιστάμενα μειονεκτήματα όσον αφορά το φύλο και επιδίωξη εφαρμογής μέτρων για τη μείωση των μειονεκτημάτων,
- προώθηση της επικοινωνίας η οποία είναι ευαίσθητη σε θέματα ισότητας φύλων μέσω της εξάλειψης των στερεοτύπων των φύλων και των πολυδιάστατων εκπροσωπήσεων γυναικών και ανδρών.

Όροι

Η παρούσα εθελοντική συμφωνία είναι κατά βούληση και μπορεί να τροποποιηθεί μετά από αμοιβαία συναίνεση. Ισχύει με την υπογραφή των νόμιμων εκπροσώπων των φορέων που συμμετέχουν και θα παραμείνει σε ισχύ έως ότου τροποποιηθεί ή τερματιστεί από οποιονδήποτε τους εταίρο μετά από κοινή συναίνεση. Διαφορετικά, η συμφωνία αυτή λήγει στις 31 Δεκεμβρίου 2018.

Εμείς, οι υπογράφωντες, δηλώνουμε ότι έχουμε διαβάσει και αποδεχτεί τους όρους και τις προϋποθέσεις αυτής της σύμβασης όπως περιγράφονται.

ΠΑΡΑΡΤΗΜΑ Ι. Επιχειρησιακό Σχέδιο

Υλοποίηση των μέτρων πρόληψης και διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων

	Μέτρο Ν° 12 Κάδοι χωριστής συλλογής απορριμμάτων σε δημόσιους και τουριστικούς χώρους
Ομάδα διαχείρισης: ρόλοι και ευθύνες	<p>Η υπεύθυνη για την εφαρμογή και παρακολούθηση του μέτρου:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Δρ. Π. Γκιούρκα, ΔΙΑΑΜΑΘ ΑΕ. Email: pgiourka@gmail.com, Τηλ. +306973251634 <p>Οι σημαντικότεροι ενδιαφερόμενοι φορείς που πρέπει να συμμετάσχουν στην εφαρμογή του μέτρου προκειμένου να λάβουν οργανωτική και, εάν είναι δυνατόν, οικονομική υποστήριξη (π.χ. κατηγορίες ενώσεων, φιλανθρωπικές ενώσεις, δημόσιοι ή ιδιωτικοί φορείς, όπως η εταιρεία διαχείρισης απορριμμάτων ή η εταιρεία διαχείρισης δικτύου ύδρευσης) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Σύνδεσμος Εστιατορίων• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Διάδοση της ευκαιρίας για συμμετοχή στο έργο URBAN WASTE σε όλα τα των ξενοδοχεία της πόλης της Καβάλας• Δήμος Καβάλας, κ. Ηλίας Γιαρματζίδης, strategic@0700.syzefxis.gov.gr. Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Διάδοση των πλεονεκτημάτων του εφαρμοζόμενου μέτρου στους πολίτες και στήριξη της υλοποίησης του.• Δημωφέλεια, Δημοτική Κοινωφελής Επιχείρηση για την Ανάπτυξη του Τουρισμού, κα. Ιωσηφίδου, Πρόεδρος του Διοικητικού Συμβουλίου, +30 2510 831388, Email: develop@kavalagreece.gr<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Διάδοση της εφαρμογής των μέτρων στους τουρίστες και παροχή οικονομικής στήριξης για την παραγωγή προωθητικού υλικού• Περιφέρεια Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας και Θράκης, κ. Χίζαρης Δημήτρης, Επόπτης Δημόσιας Υγείας, 6948084900, 2510291366, health969@hotmail.com<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ρόλος του ενδιαφερομένου: Συμβουλές σχετικά με τις κατευθυντήριες γραμμές για το υλικό προώθησης, σε θέματα υγείας και ασφάλειας.
Το Κοινό-Στόχος	<p>Τα μέτρα αυτά απευθύνονται σε εστιατόρια με στόχο να μειωθούν τα απορρίμματα τροφής με τη χρήση συσκευασιών για το σπίτι και παρακολούθησης του όγκου/kg απορριμμάτων τροφής. Τα εστιατόρια που συμμετέχουν στην εφαρμογή των μέτρων βρίσκονται στον Δήμο της Καβάλας.</p> <p>Το είδος των τουριστών που στοχεύουν τα μέτρα, προκειμένου να οργανωθεί η κατάλληλη επικοινωνιακή προσέγγιση και τα υλικά είναι:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• ξένοι/τοπικοί• νέοι/οικογένειες/ηλικιωμένοι
Συμμετοχή των	Το κοινό-στόχος θα συμμετέχει μέσω των ακόλουθων δράσεων:

<p>φορέων</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Διοργάνωση μίας ενημερωτικής πρωτοβουλίας που πραγματοποιήθηκε στις 21 Φεβρουαρίου 2018 όπου εξηγήθηκε το επιχειρησιακό σχέδιο και καταγράφηκε η έκφραση ενδιαφέροντος από τους ιδιοκτήτες των εστιατορίων. 2. Επικοινωνία και ευαισθητοποίηση, που προήλθαν από το σύνδεσμο εστιατορίων. 3. Εκστρατεία προώθησης μέσω του υλικού επικοινωνίας του έργου URBAN WASTE. 4. Υπογραφή κοινής συμφωνίας συνεργασίας σε δημόσια εκδήλωση. 5. Προσέλκυση περισσότερων εστιατορίων κατά τη διάρκεια της δημόσιας εκδήλωσης. 6. Ο Σύνδεσμος Εστιατορίων θα στείλει πρόσκληση ώστε να λάβουν μέρος σε αυτή την πρωτοβουλία περισσότερα εστιατόρια.
<p>Καθορισμός στόχων</p>	<p>Στόχοι που πρέπει να επιτευχθούν κατά τη φάση υλοποίησης του μέτρου (είναι σημαντικό να συζητηθούν και να συμφωνηθούν με όλους τους ενδιαφερόμενους φορείς και παράγοντες που συμμετέχουν στη διαδικασία):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Συμμετοχή Εστιατορίων: τουλάχιστον 10 εστιατόρια στη φάση έναρξης και τουλάχιστον 10 ακόμη μέχρι το τέλος της υλοποίησης του έργου. - Όλα τα εστιατόρια θα χρησιμοποιούν τη Συσκευή Ζύγισης Τροφίμων. Συνολικός αριθμός εστιατορίων στην πιλοτική περιοχή: 38 ● Ποσοστό των εστιατορίων που συμμετέχουν μέχρι το τέλος του έργου: 50% ● αριθμός "Σάκων/Συσκευασιών τροφίμων για το σπίτι" (Doggy Bag) που διανεμήθηκαν δηλ. 10 σακούλες/συσκευασίες τροφίμων για το σπίτι (Doggy Bag) * 10 εστιατόρια * 21 ημέρες = 2100 ● προσέγγιση σε τουρίστες (πολίτες) από την πρωτοβουλία επικοινωνίας: τουλάχιστον σε 1000 πολίτες θα γίνει προσέγγιση μέσω αυτής της πρωτοβουλίας ● kg αποφευχθείσας παραγωγής απορριμμάτων (kg οργανικών απορριμμάτων) (πολλαπλασιασμός της μέσης χωρητικότητας της σακούλας σε kg με τον αριθμό από τις σακούλες που θα διανεμηθούν)

<p>Θέσπιση μέτρων</p>	<p>Τα επιχειρησιακά βήματα που προβλέπονται για τη θέσπιση των μέτρων και την επίτευξη των καθορισμένων στόχων παρατίθενται παρακάτω:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Διοργάνωση Δημόσιας Εκδήλωσης για την υπογραφή της Συμφωνίας στις 19 Απριλίου 2018 στην Καβάλα • Διοργάνωση εκπαιδευτικής δραστηριότητας σε εστιατόρια στις 19 Απριλίου 2018 στην Καβάλα • Δραστηριότητες υποστήριξης: οι συμμετέχοντες θα έχουν ένα σημείο επικοινωνίας για τυχόν ερωτήσεις ή ζητήματα που προκύπτουν. Η υπεύθυνη επικοινωνίας της δράσης είναι η Δρ. Παρασκευή Γκιούρκα, pgiourka@gmail.com. • Η ΔΙΑΑΜΑΤΗ σε συνεργασία με τον Επικεφαλή Εταίρο θα παρέχει προσαρμοσμένο υλικό επικοινωνίας - θα ολοκληρωθεί σύντομα • Η ΔΙΑΑΜΑΘ θα διανείμει υλικό στα εστιατόρια που συμμετέχουν • διοργάνωση προκαταρκτικών ελέγχων <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ο 1^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί πριν από την ημερομηνία έναρξης της υλοποίησης του μέτρου • Ο 2^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί την πρώτη εβδομάδα από την ημερομηνία έναρξης της υλοποίησης του μέτρου • ο 3^{ος} έλεγχος θα πραγματοποιηθεί την τελευταία εβδομάδα από την υλοποίηση του μέτρου • Διοργάνωση μιας τελικής ενημερωτική εκδήλωσης με σκοπό την εμπλοκή και νέων εστιατορίων αφού παρουσιαστούν τα αποτελέσματα του έργου.
<p>Διαθέσιμες και χρήσιμες πηγές</p>	<p>Ο προϋπολογισμός που απαιτείται για την εφαρμογή των προτεινόμενων μέτρων αναλύεται ως εξής:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Σακούλες/Συσκευασίες τροφίμων για το σπίτι (<i>Doggy Bag</i>): [No. of Bags]..... * Ευρώ / τεμάχιο = Ευρώ 2. Εκτύπωση αυτοκόλλητων βιτρίνας [αριθμός εστιατορίων]..... * Ευρώ / τεμάχιο = Ευρώ 3. Εκτύπωση ενημερωτικών φυλλαδίων τραπεζιού Promocard (A5) [Αριθμός πινάκων] * Ευρώ / τεμάχιο = Ευρώ
<p>Χρονοδιάγραμμα</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Διοργάνωση δημόσιας πρωτοβουλίας-εκδήλωσης έναρξης - θα πραγματοποιηθεί κατά τη διάρκεια της 4^{ης} εκδήλωσης της Κοινότητας Πρακτικής: Απρίλιος 2018 2. Φάση έναρξης (περίπου 1 μήνας): τελικός σχεδιασμός υλικών, διοργάνωση δραστηριοτήτων κατάρτισης και δοκιμή (εάν απαιτείται) των δράσεων που προβλέπονται σε ένα δείγμα τουριστικών εγκαταστάσεων: Μάιος 2018 3. Πλήρης φάση υλοποίησης που περιλαμβάνει όλες τις επιλεγμένες τουριστικές εγκαταστάσεις και στοχεύει στις διάφορες κατηγορίες τουριστών με ειδικές δραστηριότητες επικοινωνίας που θα διαρκέσουν τουλάχιστον 5 μήνες: Ιούνιος-Οκτώβριος 2018 4. Διοργάνωση τελικής εκδήλωσης / ενημερωτικής πρωτοβουλίας για τη συμμετοχή νέων εστιατορίων με παρουσίαση των επιτευχθέντων αποτελεσμάτων: Οκτώβριος 2018
<p>Παρακολούθηση</p>	<p>1. Παρακολούθηση των δράσεων, των αντικειμένων, των ενδιαφερομένων, των εμπλεκόμενων κ.λπ.</p> <p>Σακούλες/Συσκευασίες τροφίμων για το σπίτι (<i>Doggy Bag</i>) τύπου "3" τυπωμένες και διανεμημένες στα εστιατόρια:.....</p> <p>Αριθμός ενημερωτικών φυλλαδίων τραπεζιού:</p> <p>1:.....,</p> <p>2:.....,</p>

	<p>3:.....,</p> <p>4:.....,</p> <p>5:.....,</p> <p>6:.....,</p> <p>7:.....,</p> <p>8:.....,</p> <p>9:.....,</p> <p>10:.....</p> <p>Σύνολο =</p> <p>Αριθμός Αυτοκόλλητων Βιτρίνας: [αριθμός εστιατορίων].....</p> <p>Μέσος όρος βάρους του φαγητού που περιέχεται στη σακούλα/συσκευασία τροφίμων για το σπίτι (<i>Doggy Bag</i>): kg</p>

**URBAN
WASTE**
URBAN STRATEGIES FOR
WASTE MANAGEMENT
IN TOURIST CITIES

